

International Scientific Conference

APPLIED RESEARCH. GLOBAL SOLUTIONS

Istanbul, Turkey – March 11, 2026

International Scientific Conference

**APPLIED RESEARCH.
GLOBAL SOLUTIONS**

Part 1

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**MATHEMATICAL EVIDENCE OF THE CREATION
OF ACCELERATION ON PLANET EARTH TOWARDS
THE CENTER OF THE INTERMEDIATE BELASHOV LAYER**

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Abstract. *This article is dedicated to the mathematical demonstration of the generation of acceleration on planet Earth directed towards the center of the intermediate Belashov layer. Planet Earth originated from a hot material body situated in the cosmic environment, where the average temperature is 260 °C. Following the gradual cooling of its outer shell, a lithosphere forms, possessing magnetic properties and rotating around the inner portion of the planet's core in varying directions. This rotation induces a mechanism that generates gravitational acceleration of bodies in space, with gravitational forces directed toward the center of the intermediate Belashov layer located beneath the Mohorovičić discontinuity. The gravitational mechanism can arise exclusively within a single material body as a result of the rotation of two forces acting in different directions. Meanwhile, the outer shell of the material body may remain stationary, while its internal part is in perpetual motion.*

Keywords: *creation of acceleration on planet Earth, new laws of physics, cosmic space substance, gravitation.*

There exist numerous perspectives concerning the mechanism of acceleration formation on our planet. Following a thorough analysis of the formation of gravitational forces on planet Earth, it was established that our planet, existing within the substance of outer space at an average temperature of -260 °C, originated from a hot material body. Thereafter, with the gradual cooling of its outer shell, a lithosphere possessing magnetic properties is formed, which rotates around the inner part of the Earth's core in various directions. This rotational interaction generates a mechanism responsible for the creation of free-fall acceleration of bodies in space, characterized by gravitational forces directed toward the center of the intermediate Belashov layer located beneath the Mohorovičić discontinuity.

In the mathematical proof of the creation of acceleration on planet Earth towards the center of the intermediate Belashov layer, we proceed from Newton's second law.

$$\vec{a} = \frac{\vec{F}}{m}$$

where:

a — acceleration of the body, m/s²

F — force acting on the body, N

m — mass of the body, kg.

The mechanism of the formation of free-fall acceleration of bodies in space, Fig. 1, on any planet of the Solar system consists of force 1 arising from the rotation of the outer shell 2 in one direction, and the rotation of the inner part of the core 3 in the opposite direction, as on planet Earth. At the same time, the inner shell 3 can be stationary as on the Moon, where the outer shell is stationary while its inner part remains in continuous motion.

Fig.1

For example, on planet Earth, the outer shell 2 rotates in one direction, while the inner part 3 rotates in a different direction. When the outer shell of our planet rotates in one direction and the inner part in another, gravitational acceleration of bodies in space is generated.

It is necessary to specifically emphasize that in the description of the invention application No. 2005129781 dated September 28, 2005, and in the description of the invention application No. 2005140396 dated December 26, 2005, the following mechanisms were clearly presented:

- the mechanism of formation and of thermoelectric phenomena on planet Earth,
- the mechanism of formation of the magnetic field on planet Earth,
- the mechanism of formation of the magnetic poles on planet Earth,
- the mechanism of initiation of Earth's counterclockwise rotation,
- mechanism of autonomous rotation of planet Earth,
- mechanism of earthquake genesis on planet Earth,

- mechanism of volcanic activity genesis on planet Earth,
- mechanism of formation of geopathogenic zones on planet Earth,
- mechanism of tsunami genesis on planet Earth,
- mechanism of tornado genesis on planet Earth.

However, it is essential to remember that in addition to the free-fall acceleration generated by celestial bodies in space acting on planet Earth, any material body located on the surface of our planet is subjected to the mass of the atmospheric column above it.

Furthermore, when the measuring instrument is moved upward away from the surface of our planet, the gravitational acceleration of bodies in space decreases; however, if the measuring instrument is moved deeper into our planet, the gravitational acceleration of bodies in space increases. The gravitational acceleration of bodies in space on planet Earth, originating from a hot material body, is demonstrated based on a specific law, which was presented in the scientific-analytical journal «Scientific Observer» No. 1 (25), 2013, pp. 68–73. Infinity Publishing, Ufa.

The law of acceleration of free-falling bodies in the space of A. N. Belashov is formulated as follows:

The magnitude of the acceleration of free-falling bodies in space equals the square of the sum of the vector angular velocity of the outer shell of the material body directed one way and the vector angular velocity of the inner part of the material body directed oppositely, divided by the difference between the radius of the outer shell and the radius of the inner part of the material body at the median line of the intermediate Belashov layer, plus the sum or difference of the measured distance upward or downward from the surface of the outer shell of the material body.

$$g = \frac{(V_{\varepsilon\kappa} + V_{nc})^2}{R_{\varepsilon} - R_{nc} + h} = \frac{(M/c + M/c)^2}{M} = \frac{M^2}{M \cdot c^2} = \frac{M}{c^2}$$

where:

g — magnitude of the free-fall acceleration of bodies in space, m/s^2

$V_{\varepsilon\kappa}$ — velocity of rotation of the outer shell of the material body along the equatorial circumference counterclockwise, m/s

V_{nc} — velocity of rotation of the inner section of the material body along the median line of the intermediate Belashov layer, m/s

h — height or depth of measurement from sea level at the equator to the surface of the outer shell of the material body, m

R_{nc} — radius of the inner section of the material body, m

R_{ε} — radius of the outer shell of the material body, m .

For instance, according to the law governing the free-fall acceleration of bodies in space, we determine the magnitude of free-fall acceleration at the equator of planet Earth.

$$g = \frac{(V_{\text{эк}} + V_{\text{nc}})^2}{R_{\text{э}} - R_{\text{nc}} + h} = \frac{(M/c + M/c)^2}{M} = \frac{M^2}{M \cdot c^2} = \frac{M}{c^2}$$

$$g = \frac{(465,103305311273274 + 458,740927542699182)^2}{6378160 - 6290910 + 0 = 87250 \text{ м}} = 9,7820993304016607517746568 \text{ м/с}^2$$

where:

g — magnitude of free-fall acceleration at the equator of planet Earth, m/s^2

h — height above sea level at the equator = 0 m

$R_{\text{э}}$ — radius of the outer part of the material body = 6,378,160 m

R_{nc} — radius of the inner part of the material body up to the midline of the intermediate layer of Belashov = 6,290,910 m

V_{ex} — angular velocity of the outer shell of the material body along the equatorial circumference counterclockwise = 465.10330531127328447687882460188 m/s

V_{ps} — angular velocity of the inner section of the material body along the median line of the intermediate layer = 458.74092754269918253045420097272 m/s

It is essential to emphasize that as a material body moves away from the Earth's surface, the magnitude of gravitational acceleration in space decreases proportionally, whereas as the material body approaches the median line of the intermediate Belashov layer, the magnitude of gravitational acceleration in space increases proportionally.

For example, according to the law governing the free-fall acceleration of bodies in space, we determine the magnitude of the free-fall acceleration of bodies at an altitude of 1000 m above sea level on the equator of planet Earth.

$$g = \frac{(V_{\text{эк}} + V_{\text{nc}})^2}{R_{\text{э}} - R_{\text{nc}} + h} = \frac{(M/c + M/c)^2}{M} = \frac{M^2}{M \cdot c^2} = \frac{M}{c^2}$$

$$g = \frac{(465,103305311273274 + 458,740927542699182)^2}{6378160 - 6290910 + 1000 = 88250 \text{ м}} = 9,6712540122101405166270686 \text{ м/с}^2$$

where:

g — magnitude of free-fall acceleration at the equator of planet Earth, m/s^2

$R_{\text{э}}$ — radius of the outer part of the material body = 6,378,160 m

h — height above sea level at the equator = 1000 m

V_{ex} — rotational velocity of the outer shell of the material body along the equatorial circumference counterclockwise = 465.103305311273284476 m/s

V_{ps} — angular velocity of the inner section of the material body along the median line of the intermediate layer = 458.74092754269918253045420097272 m/s

R_{ps} — radius of the inner part of the material body to the median line of the intermediate Belashov layer = 6290910 m.

For example, according to the law governing the acceleration due to gravity of bodies in space, we determine the magnitude of the free-fall acceleration of bodies at a depth of 1000 m from the surface of the Earth's crust at the equator of planet Earth.

$$g = \frac{(V_{\text{эк}} + V_{nc})^2}{R_{\text{э}} - R_{nc} - h} = \frac{(M/c + M/c)^2}{M} = \frac{M^2}{M \cdot c^2} = \frac{M}{c^2}$$

$$g = \frac{(465,103305311273274 + 458,740927542699182)^2}{6378160 - 6290910 - 1000 = 86250 \text{ м}} = 9,8955149748121147894763919 \text{ м/с}^2$$

where:

g — magnitude of free-fall acceleration at the equator of planet Earth, m/s^2

h — depth within the shaft at the equator = 1000 m

$R_{\text{э}}$ — radius of the outer part of the material body = 6,378,160 m

$V_{\text{эк}}$ — rotational velocity of the outer shell of the material body along the equatorial circumference counterclockwise = 465.103305311273284476 m/s

V_{ps} — angular velocity of the inner section of the material body along the median line of the intermediate layer = 458.74092754269918253045420097272 m/s

R_{ps} — radius of the inner part of the material body to the median line of the intermediate Belashov layer = 6290910 m.

However, the free-fall acceleration of bodies in space can also be determined by an alternative physical law.

For example, the law for determining the distance from the surface of the Sun to the surface of a measured material body located in the space of the Solar System was discovered by A. N. Belashov and is formulated as follows:

The distance from the surface of the Sun to the surfaces of the planets in the Solar System is directly proportional to the free-fall acceleration of bodies in the space of the measured material body multiplied by the diameter of the measured material body, and inversely proportional to the acceleration of antigravitational interaction and the Sun's opposing force.

$$L_u = \frac{g_u \cdot D_u}{g_c} = \frac{M}{c^2} \cdot \frac{c^2}{M} \cdot \frac{M}{M} = M$$

where:

L_u — distance from the surface of the Sun to the surface of the studied material body, m

g_u — gravitational acceleration of the measured material body, m/s^2

g_c — acceleration of antigravitational interaction and counteraction of the Sun, m/s^2

$D_{\text{н}}$ — diameter of the measured material body, m.

For example, according to the law defining acceleration of antigravitational interaction and counteraction of the Sun, we will verify the acceleration of free-fall of bodies in space within the Solar System on planet Earth.

$$g_3 = \frac{L \cdot g_c}{D_3} = \frac{M}{c^2} \cdot \frac{M}{M} \cdot \frac{M}{c^2} = \frac{M}{c^2}$$

$$g_3 = \frac{14950000000,000 \text{ м} \cdot 0,0008367597908361204013390488452674 \text{ м/с}^2}{12756200 \text{ м}} = 9,80665000000 \text{ м/с}^2$$

where:

g_3 — acceleration of free-fall of bodies in space on planet Earth, m/s^2

g_c — acceleration of antigravitational interaction and counteraction of the Sun = 0.0008367597908361204013390488452674 m/s^2

L — average distance from the Sun's surface to the Earth's surface = 1,495 m00000000 m

D_z — diameter of planet Earth = 12,756,200 m.

In conclusion, it can be stated that our material world is highly diverse, and all processes occurring within it, resulting from randomly combined circumstances over time, influence each other to varying degrees; hence, a new theory of multidimensional dependence is proposed. In this world, all phenomena are interconnected, and each natural occurrence depends to varying extents on others. More active material bodies dominate over less active material bodies; therefore, there cannot be independent and constant constants, laws, or physical parameters. For example, the new law of antigravitational interaction and opposition between two material bodies located within the space of the Solar or another system is closely related to the new law of gravitational attraction of a material body situated within the Solar system to the central star, the Sun. Simultaneously, the laws of gravitational attraction, cosmic interaction, and counteraction remain continuously dependent on the new law of activity of a material body situated in space, as well as on the new law of acceleration of free-falling bodies in space. Furthermore, these laws are closely linked to the new law of energy between two material bodies located within the Solar System and to the new law of energy of a single material body within the Solar System, relative to the central star, the Sun, among many others...

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**MATHEMATICAL PROOF OF THE INCONSISTENCY
OF THE LAW OF UNIVERSAL GRAVITATION
AND THE GRAVITATIONAL CONSTANT**

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Abstract. *The article is devoted to the mathematical demonstration of the inconsistency of the current law of universal gravitation and its “gravitational constant.” The primary obstacle to an accurate calculation of gravitational forces between two material bodies situated within the substance of cosmic space is that the presently refined Newtonian law does not account for the degree of activity of each material body. The new law proposed by Belashov A. N. explains the formation of gravitational forces between two material bodies situated in the substance of cosmic space, incorporating the degree of activity of each material body and the variable distance between the measured objects as they move along an elliptical orbit. The gravitational constant is a fixed value and cannot differentiate the true gravitational force between two material bodies located at apogee or perigee, since the distances differ both between the material bodies themselves and from each measured material body to the surface of our star, the Sun.*

Keywords: *law of universal gravitation, gravitational constant, new laws of physics, cosmic space substance, gravitation.*

After an in-depth analysis of the scientific and technical foundations of gravitational forces between two material bodies located in the cosmic space of the Solar System, the current law of Newtonian universal gravitation was critically examined, resulting in the discovery of new physical laws. These new laws mathematically explain the formation of gravitational forces between two material bodies located in space.

The discoverer of the law of gravitation is the English physicist, astronomer, mathematician, and mechanic Isaac Newton; however, prior to Newton this idea was actually proposed by distinguished scholars such as the Italian scientist Galileo Galilei and the ancient Greek philosopher Epicurus.

In 1687, Isaac Newton stated in his book *Mathematical Principles of Natural Philosophy* that ‘Gravity exists between all bodies at all times; under all conditions, bodies attract each other with a force whose magnitude is proportional to the product of their masses and inversely proportional to the square of the distance between them.’ Isaac Newton’s strategic insight was correct, as he derived this law of gravitation from the fundamental empirical laws of Kepler, which was originally formulated as follows.

$$F = \frac{m_1 m_2}{r^2}$$

where:

F — gravitational force

m_1 — mass of the first object, kg

m_2 — mass of the second object,

r — distance between the centers of mass.

This law did not comply with the dimensional units of physical quantities and did not represent the true value of the gravitational forces between two material bodies situated in space; therefore, the scientific community introduced the “gravitational constant” into Isaac Newton’s law of gravitation, which then took the following form.

$$F = G \frac{m_1 m_2}{r^2}$$

where:

F- gravitational force,

m_1 — mass of the first object,

m_2 — mass of the second object,

G — gravitational constant,

r — distance between the centers of mass.

For example, according to the classical law of universal gravitation, let us determine the gravitational force between the Moon and the planet Earth.

$$F = G \frac{m_1 m_2}{r^2}$$

$$F_T = \frac{6,6740 \cdot 10^{-11} \cdot 5,9736 \cdot 10^{24} \cdot 7,3477 \cdot 10^{22}}{384400000 \cdot m^2} = 198249547427005991201, 066 H$$

where:

F_U — universal gravitational force, N

m_m — mass of the Moon = 7.3477×10^{22} kg

bodies; this force is inversely proportional to twice the product of the distance from the surface of the Sun to the surface of the first material body and the distance from the surface of the Sun to the surface of the second material body.

$$F_T = \frac{[(m_1 \cdot g_1) + (m_2 \cdot g_2)] \cdot L \cdot M^2}{2 \cdot (L_{c_1} \cdot L_{c_2})} = \frac{H \cdot M^2}{M^2} = H$$

where:

F_T — gravitational force between two material bodies located within the space of the Solar System, N

L_{c_1} — distance from the surface of the Sun to the surface of the first material body, m

L_{c_2} — distance from the surface of the Sun to the surface of the second material body, m

L_m — distance from the surface of the first material body to the surface of the second material body, m

g_1 — magnitude of the free-fall acceleration of the first material body, m/s^2

g_2 — magnitude of the free-fall acceleration of the second material body, m/s^2

m_1 — mass of the first material body, kg

m_2 — mass of the second material body, kg

For example, according to the new law, the gravitational force between the planet Earth and its satellite the Moon at the mean distance separating them is determined.

$$F_T = \frac{[(m_1 \cdot g_1) + (m_2 \cdot g_2)] \cdot L \cdot M^2}{2 \cdot (L_{c_1} \cdot L_{c_2})} = \frac{H \cdot M^2}{M^2} = H$$

$$FT = \frac{[(5.9736 \cdot 10^22 \text{ kg} \cdot 9.8 \text{ m/s}^2) + (7.3477 \cdot 10^22 \text{ kg} \cdot 1.62 \text{ m/s}^2)] \cdot 384400000 \text{ m}^2}{2 \cdot (149597870700 \text{ m} \cdot 149597870700 \text{ m})} = 193655712431467929534,544 \text{ H}$$

where:

FT — gravitational force between the planet Earth and its satellite the Moon, N

L_{c_1} — distance from the surface of the Sun to the surface of the planet Earth = 149597870700 m

L_{c_2} — distance from the surface of the Sun to the surface of the Moon satellite = 149597870700 m

L_m — distance from the surface of planet Earth to the surface of the Moon = 384400000 m

g_1 — magnitude of free-fall acceleration on planet Earth $\approx 9.8 \text{ m/s}^2$

g_2 — magnitude of free-fall acceleration on the Moon $\approx 1.62 \text{ m/s}^2$

m_m — mass of the Moon = 7.3477×10^{22} 00000000000000000000 kg

m_e — mass of the planet Earth = 5.9736×10^{24} 00000000000000000000 kg.

We determine the calculation error between the old law of universal gravitation and the new law introduced by Belashov A. N..

198249547427005991201.0663536616 N = 100 %

193655712431467929534.54408643792 N = X %

X = 97.682801774248953812459158215296 %

This error originated from the static magnitude of the «gravitational constant,» since it is unknown for which point in cosmic space it is intended, as well as from incorrect data on the free-fall acceleration of bodies on the Moon. If the distance in the new law of universal gravitation between the Moon as a satellite and the planet Earth, or the acceleration of free fall on the Moon, is altered, then the «gravitational constant» can exactly correspond to the classical law of universal gravitation; however, this would constitute falsification.

The average distance from the planet Earth to the Moon $\approx 384,400,000$ m.

The distance from the planet Earth to the Moon at Perigee $\approx 363,300,000$ m.

The distance from the planet Earth to the Moon at Apogee $\approx 405,500,000$ m.

In calculating the gravitational forces between planet Earth and its satellite, the Moon, it is imperative to consider the sensational discoveries concerning the properties and composition of the Moon published in the scientific-practical journal «Higher School», No. 2, 2018, pp. 27–33. Publishing House «Infinity», Ufa.

The Moon is a gaseous satellite composed of a solid shell of frozen gas, which is covered by cosmic dust. Given the average density of the Moon, it is challenging to ascertain the internal gaseous composition, as the overall density of the Moon is $0.6252010691300386859433902$ kg/m³. The gas contained within the lunar sphere may consist of many chemical components, but even gas mixtures composed of helium and hydrogen can form the Moon's outer shell and remain in a solid state at the temperature of open space, equal to -270.45 °C.

Inside the solid shell, the gas mixture containing cosmic dust particles is in constant motion, since one side of the Moon is continuously heated. The sunlit side of the Moon can heat up to a temperature of $+107$ °C, whereas the side of the Moon in shadow can reach a temperature of -268.9 °C, which causes the gaseous mixture within the Moon's sphere to continuously rotate by means of natural convection. In this process, internal energy is transferred by streams and flows of gas and arises spontaneously within the material due to its uneven heating in the gravitational field. The rotation of the gaseous mixture inside the sphere generates an acceleration of free fall in space that exceeds that of Earth by a factor of 3.6.

The new law of gravitational forces between two material bodies located in outer space proposed by Belashov A. N. is dynamic and accounts for all subtle nuances occurring in outer space. The old law of universal gravitation, when measuring

gravitational forces between two measurable material bodies in outer space possessing different degrees of activity, cannot accomplish this, as it is inconsistent.

From the calculations performed, it is evident that the gravitational force exerted by the Moon on planet Earth varies depending on the change in distance from the surface of the Moon to the surface of planet Earth. Notably, concurrently with the variation in the distance from the surface of planet Earth to the surface of the Moon, the gravitational force exerted by planet Earth on the Moon also varies. We demonstrate this natural phenomenon through a new law, providing specific mathematical proofs.

To characterize the properties of antigravity emanating from the surface of the Sun, it is necessary to understand the law of gravitation of a single material body within the Solar System's spatial domain towards the central star, the Sun, as formulated by Belashov A. N.:

The gravitational force exerted by one investigated material body located within the Solar System on the central star, the Sun, equals the product of the mass of the measured material body, the magnitude of the free-fall acceleration of the measured material body, and the diameter of the measured material body, and is inversely proportional to the distance from the surface of the Sun to the surface of the measured material body.

$$F_{\text{тсo}} = \frac{m u \cdot g u \cdot D u}{L c} = \frac{\kappa z \cdot M \cdot M}{c^2 \cdot M} = H$$

where:

$F_{\text{тсo}}$ — gravitational force of one investigated material body located within the Solar System acting on the Sun, N

Lc — distance from the surface of the Sun to the surface of the measured material body, m

$g u$ — free-fall acceleration of the measured material body, m/s^2

$D u$ — diameter of the measured material body, m

$m u$ — mass of the measured material body, kg.

For example, according to this law, we determine the gravitational force between the surface of planet Earth and the surface of the Sun.

$$F_{\text{тсo}} = \frac{m u \cdot g u \cdot D u}{L c} = \frac{\kappa z \cdot M \cdot M}{c^2 \cdot M} = H$$

$$F_{\text{тсo}} = \frac{5.972 \times 10^{24} \text{ kg} \cdot 9.80 \text{ m/s}^2 \cdot 12756320 \text{ m}}{149500000000 \text{ m}} = 4997631526747812709030,1 H$$

where:

$F_{\text{тсo}}$ — gravitational force of planet Earth toward the Sun, N

L_c — average distance from the surface of the Sun to the surface of planet Earth = 149500000000 m

$g_{и}$ — magnitude of the free fall acceleration on Earth = 9.806650000 m/s²

$D_{и}$ — diameter of the planet Earth = 12,756,320 m

$m_{и}$ — mass of the planet Earth 5.972×10^{24} 00000000000000000000 kg.

According to the law discovered by A. N. Belashov, we determine the acceleration of antigravitational interaction and solar counteraction, formulated as follows:

The acceleration of antigravitational interaction and solar counteraction is directly proportional to the gravitational force exerted by a single investigated material body situated within the Solar system relative to the Sun and inversely proportional to the product of the density and the volume of the investigated material body.

$$g = \frac{F_{тco}}{p \cdot V} = \frac{\kappa_2 \cdot M}{c^2} \cdot \frac{M^3}{\kappa_2} \cdot \frac{1}{M^3} = \frac{M}{c^2}$$

where:

g — acceleration of antigravitational interaction and counteraction, m/s²

$F_{тco}$ — gravitational force of one studied material body located in the space of the Solar system directed towards the central star Sun, N

p — density of the studied material body, kg/m³

V — volume of the studied material body, m³.

For example, according to this law, the force of antigravitational interaction and counteraction emanating from the surface of the Sun is determined.

$$g = \frac{F_{тco}}{p \cdot V} = \frac{\kappa_2 \cdot M}{c^2} \cdot \frac{M^3}{\kappa_2} \cdot \frac{1}{M^3} = \frac{M}{c^2}$$

$$g = \frac{4997631526747812709030,1003344482 H}{5495,419 \kappa_2/M^3 \cdot 1086832411937628837875003797 M^3} = 0,00083675979083612040133779264214048 \text{ m/c}^2$$

where:

g — acceleration of antigravitational interaction and solar counteraction, m/s²

$F_{тso}$ — gravitational force of the Earth toward the Sun = 4997631526747812709030.100334 N

p — density of planet Earth = 5495.41947258631784241409 kg/m³

V — volume of planet Earth = 1086832411937628837875.00379714 m³.

According to the law discovered by A. N. Belashov, the acceleration of antigravitational interaction and solar counteraction in the Solar System space = 0.000 83675979083612040133779264214048 m/s².

The law determining the distance from the surface of the Sun to the surface of a measured material body located within the space of the Solar System was discovered by Belashov A. N. and is formulated as follows:

The distance from the surface of the Sun to the surface of the planets in the Solar System is directly proportional to the free-fall acceleration of bodies measured at the location of the material body multiplied by the diameter of that material body, and inversely proportional to the acceleration of antigravitational interaction and solar counteraction.

$$L_u = \frac{g_u \cdot D_u}{g_c} = \frac{M}{c^2} \cdot \frac{c^2}{M} \cdot M = M$$

where:

L_u — the distance from the surface of the Sun to the surface of the studied material body, m

g_u — gravitational acceleration of the measured material body, m/s^2

g_c — antigravitational interaction and solar counteraction, m/s^2

D_u — diameter of the measured material body, m.

For example, according to the law defining antigravitational interaction and solar counteraction, let us verify the acceleration due to gravity of bodies within the Solar System at planet Earth.

$$g_3 = \frac{L \cdot g_c}{D_3} = \frac{M}{c^2} \cdot \frac{M}{M} \cdot \frac{M}{c^2}$$

$$g_3 = \frac{14950000000,000 \text{ м} \cdot 0,00083675979083612040133904884526 \text{ м/с}^2}{12756200 \text{ м}} = 9,80665000000 \text{ м/с}^2$$

where:

g_3 — acceleration due to free fall of bodies in space on planet Earth, m/s^2

g_c — acceleration of antigravitational interaction and solar counteraction = 0.0008367597908361204013390488452674 m/s^2

L — average distance from the surface of the Sun to the surface of the Earth = 149500000000 m

D_3 — diameter of the Earth = 12756200 m.

For example, based on the law defining antigravitational interaction and solar counteraction, we determine the acceleration of free-falling bodies in the Solar system space when the Moon is at perigee.

$$g_n = \frac{L \cdot g_c}{D_n} = \frac{M}{c^2} \cdot \frac{M}{M} \cdot \frac{M}{c^2}$$

$$g_n = \frac{149139523720 \text{ м} \cdot 0,00083675979083612040133779264214 \text{ м/с}^2}{3476280 \text{ м}} = 35,8987068571420648590 \text{ м/с}^2$$

where:

g_{π} — free fall acceleration of bodies on the Moon at perigee, m/s^2

g_c — free fall acceleration of bodies in the space surrounding

the Sun = 0.00083675979083612040133779264214044 m/s^2

L — distance from the surface of the Sun to the surface of the Moon at perigee = 149139523720 m

D_{π} — diameter of the Moon = 3476280 m.

In conclusion, it can be stated that all existing calculations must be revisited, since our material world is exceedingly diverse, and all processes occurring within it — resulting from randomly established circumstances unfolding over time — influence one another to varying degrees; thus, a new theory of multifaceted dependence is proposed. In this world, everything is interconnected, and one natural phenomenon depends to varying extents on another. More active material bodies dominate over less active material bodies; therefore, truly independent and constant constants, laws, or physical quantities cannot exist. For example, the new law of antigravitational interaction and counteraction between two material bodies, which are located within the spatial domain of the Solar or another system, is closely related to the new law of gravitational attraction of a single material body within the Solar system to the central star, the Sun. At the same time, the laws of gravitational attraction, cosmic interaction, and counteraction are continually dependent upon the new law of activity of a material body situated in space and the new law of free-fall acceleration of bodies within space. Moreover, the aforementioned laws are closely linked to the new law of energy between two material bodies located within the Solar System, as well as to the new law of energy of a single material body situated within the Solar System relative to the central star, the Sun, among many others...

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NATURAL RESOURCES OF MEDICINAL PLANTS OF KOPETDAG

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Abstract. *In recent years, the resource potential of medicinal and other plants of Kopetdag, which are sources of biologically active substances and objects of economic use, has been intensively studied. Despite the relatively small area of the mountain ecosystems in Turkmenistan, the flora of this region is characterized by significant species diversity and a large number of medicinal plants. The resources of wild medicinal plants are of utmost importance for the healthcare system in Turkmenistan, as they are a source of biologically active substances.*

Keywords: *raw materials, medicinal plants, dorema, total biological reserve, and operational reserve of raw materials.*

In recent years, the resource potential of medicinal and other plants of Kopetdag, which are sources of biologically active substances and objects of economic use, has been studied quite intensively. Despite the relatively small area of mountain ecosystems in Turkmenistan, the flora of this region is distinguished by significant species diversity and a large number of medicinal plants.

Taking into account the unique landscape, lithological, and natural conditions of Kopetdag, raw material resources were studied from various gorges. To plot them on a map, a system of conventional symbols and a topographic base at a scale of 1:50,000 were used.

Kopetdag dorema (*Dorema kopetdaghense* M. Pimen.) is a perennial herbaceous plant of the Celery family (*Apiaceae* Lindl.) with a height of 150–200 cm. It is a taproot monocarpic plant. The stem is cylindrical, tapering, round, branching in the middle into a pyramidal panicle, and slightly pubescent. The leaves are grayish-pubescent, ternately dissected, and their segments are, in turn, twice pinnately

dissected into oblong-lanceolate sections. Umbels are 5–12 flowered and almost sessile. It flowers in May–June and bears fruit in June–July [5; 7].

It grows in the foothills and the lower mountain belt. It settles on stony and fine-earth gravelly slopes, terraces, and dry riverbeds. In the Central Kopetdag, it is noted in: Germab, Gokdere, Archabil Gorge, Vannovsky, Neftonovsky, Yablonovsky, Kurtsuv, Babazav, Dushakerekdag, Kheirabad, Karaagach, Mergenolen, Kurkulab Arvaz, Gaudan, etc. [4; 5; 7].

The above-ground mass of Kopetdag dorema contains 0.09–0.12 % essential oil, coumarins, and flavonoids. In the roots, the following were found: 19 % resin, terpenoids, and coumarins (umbelliferone). The extract from dorema roots possesses weak antitumor properties [5; 6].

The resin can be used in the paint and varnish industry. On the whole, the useful (including medicinal) properties of the *Dorema* species of Turkmenistan have not yet been sufficiently studied. The wide distribution of certain species of the genus, as well as sufficiently high stocks of raw materials, make *Dorema* promising objects for in-depth research and practical use.

In the Central Kopetdag, dense thickets of the plant, despite its wide distribution, are not common. One such area was described by us in the Suncha tract. Here, an area of about 30 hectares is occupied by thickets of Kopetdag dorema. The plant density ranges from 5–6 to 30–35 per 100 m². The average weight of a raw root is 2080.3 g. The above-ground mass of the plants is 929.6 g. The yield of air-dry raw material is 30 % and 28 %, respectively. Taking the number of plants in the massif to be 36,000 thousand (averaging 12 plants per 100 m²), we assume that the total biological reserve of air-dry raw material in the area consists of 22.5 tons of underground and 9.4 tons of above-ground phytomass [1].

For the harvesting of dorema roots, perennial, well-developed vegetative individuals are used, and for the harvesting of the herb, generative shoots are also used. Roots are best dug after the plant has finished its growing season. The herb is harvested at the moment of maximum leaf mass development before it dries out. Cut leaves and shoots are pre-crushed and dried in small ricks in the shade. After digging, the roots are cleaned of soil residues and immediately crushed into pieces no larger than 5–10 cm. The roots are dried in the shade or in the sun by active drying, spreading them in a thin layer and constantly turning them over. Dry raw materials are stored in bales or bags in dry, well-ventilated rooms separately from the raw materials of other medicinal plants.

Thus, using accumulated experience, when harvesting raw materials, we recommend putting no more than 15–20 % of the plants into operation annually at the commercial site, which ensures the normal self-renewal of dorema thickets and its stability in the herbage.

Horsetail ephedra (*Ephedra equisetina* Bunge) is a valuable dioecious medicinal plant of the Ephedraceae family, a shrub up to 1.5 m tall. The flowers are small and unisexual. The fruits are spherical, red or orange, fleshy, and single-seeded. Mature cone-berries have a length of 6–7 mm. It flowers in May and bears fruit in July [3; 7]. It grows from the lower to the upper mountain belt, rarely entering the high foothills. It prefers fine-earth, gravelly, and stony substrates on open sunny areas along the slopes of southern, western, and eastern exposures. A good root system allows it to grow in places inaccessible to other species.

All organs of the plant contain alkaloids, ephedrine, and pseudoephedrine, with the largest amount (up to 3.5%) accumulating in the green annual branches. The ephedrine content is 90%, vitamin C — 660 mg, and tannins — up to 14%. Alkaloids have also been found in the fruits [1]. In the Central Kopetdag, ephedra is distributed quite widely and may be of interest for industrial raw material harvesting. To this end, we have examined two massifs with its thickets in detail.

The Ipaykala commercial massif is located in the tracts adjacent to the Arvaz River valley, on the segment from the Yaylak gorge (in the west) to the Niyazymata gorge (in the east). Here, in the tracts of Aksuv, Gokgedik, Gaplanly, Chat, Goshaarcha, Berkav, Niyazymata, Yaylak, and others, the thickets occupy an area of 133 hectares, with the most productive ones in the tracts of Akgaya (21 ha), Yaylak (27 ha), and Niyazymata (35 ha). At the Ipaykala site, we identified 3 classes of plants by productivity: I — large (height 60–100 cm, crown diameter 80x100 cm); II — medium (40–60 and 40–70 cm, respectively); III — small (20–40 and 20–40 cm). The operational reserve of raw materials was calculated by us only for plants of classes I and II. Thus, for plants of classes I and II, the operational reserve of raw materials at the Ipaykala massif is 155.6 tons, and the volume of possible annual harvesting without damage to the thickets was established by us in the amount of 77.8 tons of air-dry raw material mass. The second commercial massif is located approximately 8 km north of the first, in the Karayalchi tract. Here, in the Karanki and Kalinkhoz gorges with their adjacent territory, an area of about 100 hectares is occupied by thickets. Ephedra communities are part of the tragacanth milkvetch and ephemeral-wormwood formations, distinguished by high productivity. Biometric indicators: Class I — large plants (height 150–170 cm, crown diameter 280x250 cm); II — medium (130–150 and 160x200 cm); III — small (100–130 and 100x160 cm, respectively). The operational reserve of raw materials was identified for plants of all three classes and amounted to 219 tons, including 109 tons — the volume of possible annual raw material harvesting. Harvesting must be carried out in early spring (April). The apical parts of the plant up to 25 cm long are collected, in which the alkaloid content is at least 1.6%, and moisture and lignified parts are, respectively, no more than 12% and 10%. The identified reserves of horsetail ephedra do not exhaust its true raw material resources in the Central Kopetdag. Thickets of

industrial significance are noted in the area of the Dushakerekhdag ridge, the tracts of Suncha, Tejeve, Mergenolen, Sarymsakli, and others. The reserves of raw materials in this region allow for its use to obtain ephedrine on a scale that meets the needs of the healthcare and medical industry of Turkmenistan.

Turkmen henbane (*Hyoscyamus turcomanicus*) is a perennial herbaceous plant of the Nightshade family (*Solanaceae*), 60–100 cm tall, with a thick, woody, multi-headed rhizome and pubescence of sticky intertwining hairs, which are always long and shaggy on the petioles, parts of the inflorescences, and the upper part of the stems, and short felt-like in their lower part. The stems are thick and strong. Stem leaves are 18–20 cm long and 4–11 cm wide. The flowers are initially clustered at the ends of the branches, elongating after flowering. The corolla is whitish with a purple network of veins and a throat of the same color (inside). It flowers in March — May and bears fruit in May — June.

Growing locations — Shamli, Gokdere, Chaek, Kheirabad, Mergenolen, Sarymsakli, Tagarev, Arvaz, Kurykhovdan, Vakhcha, Sherlock, Asylma, Dagish, Dashtoy, Bolshiye Karanki, Archabil, Chopandag, Boziyamov, Misinyov, Gaudan. It occurs in small thickets and clusters on stony and fine-earth slopes. It is an endemic of Turkmenistan [2; 3; 5; 7].

All organs of the plant contain atropine alkaloids — hyoscyamine, tropine, scopolamine (hyoscine), apoatropine, etc.; seeds contain up to 34% fatty oils, and the leaves contain flavonoids (primarily rutin) and phospholipids (0.9%). The oil is used for rheumatic and neuralgic pains; substances contained in the leaves are used to obtain anti-asthmatic drugs. It is widely used in the folk medicine of many countries of the world and in homeopathy [3].

We have studied 3 areas where the density of thickets is such that it allows for the harvesting of raw materials. The area of the Sulyukli-Degirmanli massif is about 8 hectares. Here, on the gravelly-fine-earth gentle slopes along the Sulyukli — Degirmanli road, cluster-type thickets (10–20 (50) m² each) are noted. The biological reserve of the raw material mass is 384.8 centers (tsentners), the operational reserve (excluding “inconvenient lands”) is 346.3 centers, and the volume of possible harvesting is 173.2 centers/year.

The Germab-Kheirabad massif covers an area of 12 hectares and is confined to plateau-like inter-ridge spaces along the Germab — Kheirabad road. Clusters with an area of 2060 m² are developed on fine-earth and stony substrates, while less dense ones (10–15 m²) are recorded from Chaek to Gokdere. The biological and operational reserves of the raw material mass are 457.2 and 411.5 centers, respectively, and the volume of possible harvesting is 205.8 centers.

The area of the Kurykhovdan massif is about 20 hectares (Kurykhovdan — Sherlock area). The density of thickets here is minimal — 0.8–2 specimens/m². The indicators given above are, respectively, 458 centers, 412, and 206 centers.

Rosette and stem leaves collected during mass flowering are used as medicinal raw materials (the plant is very poisonous, so certain rules must be followed during collection). The raw material must be stored according to List B, that is, separately from other plants in dry, well-ventilated rooms (in bales on racks). The shelf life is 2 years. The moisture content in the raw material is no more than 14%, organic impurities — 1%, mineral — 1%, and alkaloids — 0.05%.

Kopetdag everlasting (*Helichrysum kopetdagense*) is a perennial herbaceous plant with flocculent-white-tomentose pubescence of the Aster family (*Asteraceae*), 30–50 cm tall. Basal leaves are oblong-obovate, and stem leaves are linear-lanceolate. Flower baskets are small, straw-yellow, collected in a terminal compact corymbose inflorescence. It flowers in May — July and bears fruit in July — August. It usually grows in steppe and semi-savanna communities of the lower and middle mountain zones on fine-earth-gravelly substrates with sparse vegetation.

Growing locations — Khendyvar, Kheirabad, Dushakerekdag, Mergenolen, Sulyukli, Prokhladnoye, Tagarev, Arvaz, Kurykhovdan, Asylma, Babazav, Dagish, Dashtoy, Dugridora, Bolshiye Karanki, Archabil, Chopandag, Kurkulab, Misinev, Gaudan, Karayalchi. It is an endemic of Turkmenistan [2; 3; 5; 7].

The inflorescences contain essential oil, flavonoid glycosides, naringenin, apigenin, and other substances of a phenolic nature, vitamins C and K, phthalides, high-molecular alcohols, steroid compounds, tannins, sugars, fatty acids, etc. [3; 6].

It is a component of the steppe thickets of juniper forests and is most often represented by a synusial structure along gravelly slopes and rock crevices. It does not form thickets or pure clusters (accumulations). Small groups and individual plants are scattered throughout the open juniper woodland. We studied a site in a fescue-xerophytic-herbage juniper forest, where this plant occupies an area of about 500 m². About 300 specimens/m² were recorded here, the air-dry weight of which (including baskets — 42 g) is 98 g. Collected inflorescences are dried in the shade, spreading them on a tarpaulin in a layer of 2–3 cm, bringing them to a state where they become brittle and the moisture content is no more than 12%.

The raw material must be stored on racks in dark and cool rooms, and at home — in boxes or closed tins. Shelf life — up to 3 years.

Wavy ferula (*Ferula undulata*) is a perennial monocarpic plant of the Aster family, 80–100 cm tall, with a reddish-brown and rather thick stem, branching from the middle into an oval panicle. Leaves wither quickly, smooth above, more or less pubescent below; basal leaves are on short petioles. The number of leaves in adult plants is 2–4 (5), their length is 40–50 cm, width is 50–60 cm; stem leaves are significantly smaller. It flowers in May and bears fruit in June — July. It grows on fine-earth-gravelly, often almost bare talus in the middle mountains (shiblyak belt) to the lower belt of juniper forests among sparse xerophilic shrubs and mountain xerophytes in wormwood-cereal communities.

Growing locations — Vannovsky, Gokdere, Chaek, Kheirabad, Germab, Sulyukli, Prokhladnoye, Kurykhovdan, Sherlok, Babazav, Dashtoy, Archabil, Chopandag, Yablonovsky, Kurtusuv, Gaudan. It is an endemic of Turkmenistan [2; 3; 5; 7].

The chemical composition has not been studied. In folk medicine, it is used to treat colds.

Thickets of economic importance occupy the territory adjacent to the Gokdere — Chaek road. Here, in the wormwood-cereal communities of shiblyak on an area of 150–160 hectares, fairly sparse groups of this plant are noted. On a 100 m² transect, there are an average of 11 specimens. The productivity of above-ground and underground mass was determined from 112 individuals (excluding annuals): the average weight of one plant was 173.1 and 192.2 g, respectively. The weight of the largest roots is 500 g, the yield of their air-dry raw material is 31%, and that of the above-ground mass is 28%. The operational reserve of raw above-ground mass is about 8 tons, and the underground phytomass is 10 tons.

In order to ensure normal conditions for the development of the coenopopulation within the coeno-range of the plant, it is necessary to put into operation no more than 1/8 of its thickets annually, trying to choose the largest specimens.

It is not recommended to dig up generative individuals, and the above-ground mass — the leaves — is collected before they dry out, without damaging the root collar. Roots are also harvested manually, selecting the largest vegetative individuals. No more than 1/10 of their part is dug up, cleaned of soil residues, and immediately crushed into pieces 2–3 cm thick. The crushed raw material is dried in the open sun or in the shade, “shoveling” it 2–3 times a day. Its volume decreases by 3 times. For long-term storage, dry raw materials are packed in cellophane bags and stored separately, as it has a persistent specific odor. Shelf life — 2 years.

Turkmen barberry (*Berberis turcomanica*) is a highly branched thorny shrub 3–4 m tall from the Barberry family (*Berberidaceae*). The branches are brownish or purple, angular with simple and strong spines. The berries are obovate or oblong, purple-red to dark blue with a bloom, 7–8 mm long. It flowers in April, bears fruit in June, and the fruits ripen in September — October. It grows from the low foothills to the upper mountain belt on stony and gravelly slopes and along gorges. It develops better in damp places, near springs and rivers (the most characteristic habitat is permanent or temporary moisture sources and shallow aquifers). Single plants of various sizes are found in dry valleys, gorges, and rock crevices. It is an endemic of Turkmenistan [2; 3].

The chemical composition has not been sufficiently studied. The roots, bark of the trunks, shoots, leaves, and fruits contain the alkaloids berberine, berberrubine, columbamine, palmatine, jatrorrhizine, and berbamine. The leaves contain carbohydrates, alkaloids of the protoberberine group, vitamins C and E, carotene, phenolcarboxylic acids, and anthocyanins, while the fruits contain carbohydrates

(pectins), organic acids (up to 3.72%), vitamin C, carotene, tannins (0.3%), and carotenoids (56%) [3].

In the territory under consideration, it is difficult to find a habitat where barberry does not participate in one combination or another with the dominant vegetation in the form of dense thickets, sparse clusters, or individual plants. More often, it occupies a unique ecological niche in communities of xerophilic shrubs such as shiblyak or juniper forests, and also penetrates into tugai groupings and coenoses of xeromesophilic broad-leaved forests. It grows in clusters of 5–10 bushes over an area of 200–300 m², and sometimes occurs as single bushes among herbage-cereal-wormwood groupings or sparse juniper forests on rocky outcrops. On the massif from Sulyukli to Prokhladnoye, 1600–1800 bushes of varying productivity were counted, occupying an area of 3–3.2 thousand hectares.

Taking into account the bioecological characteristics of this plant and the anthropogenic pressure on the communities, we have conventionally accepted 1/10 of the leaf mass and 2/3 of the fruit mass of the operational reserve as the volume of possible annual raw material harvesting.

Thus, every year on the specified massif, 1.66 centers (tsentners) of leaves and 33.3 centers of fruits can be harvested as raw materials, including 0.46 and 13.4 centers, respectively, in highly productive thickets.

Given the slow recovery of the root system, re-digging of roots is recommended no more than once every 5–10 years. In this case, roots of only every second bush are dug up. Shoots can be used as raw material, in which case the thickets recover after 3–4 years. Leaves are collected from mid-May to mid-June, during the budding and flowering phase. Shelf life — 3 years. Roots are dug in early spring before the buds open or in autumn after the fruit ripens. Fruits are collected in the phase of full maturity — in September — October. Shelf life — 3 years.

Panicled almond (*Amygdalus scoparia*) is a shrub from the Rose family (*Rosaceae*) up to 3 m high, with numerous closely spaced, straight, protruding branches. It flowers in April and bears fruit in July. It grows on stony, less often on stony-gravelly and gravelly mountain slopes and outcrops of bedrock at an altitude of 600–900 (1000) m above sea level. The largest clusters are noted in the gorge between Bakherden and Archman.

The total biological reserve is 25.8 tons. The seeds contain vitamins and fatty oil (43.6%), which includes linoleic (21.6%) and oleic (65.9%) acids. It possesses antibacterial properties.

Cina-like wormwood (*Artemisia ciniformis*) from the Aster family — an almost glabrous subshrub 30–45 cm tall. Endemic to Turkmenistan [2; 3; 5; 7].

The root is taproot-like, thickened, and woody. Perennial shoots are shortened, woody, ascending, covered in grayish-brown peeling bark. The number of fruiting branches is 10–20; they are more or less straight or arcuate-curved at the base,

initially pubescent, and over time glabrous. The length of the leaves is 1.5–3 cm, oval in outline, twice-thrice pinnately dissected. The panicle is multi-flowered and narrow. It flowers in September and bears fruit in November [7].

It grows on clayey and gravelly soil up to an altitude of 2500 m above sea level, often together with Turkmenian wormwood, but unlike the latter, it does not form large massifs.

The essential oil content in the above-ground mass is 0.4–0.5%, and it contains up to 15% aldehydes and a insignificant amount of santonin [3; 6].

The biometric characteristic of the plants is similar to Turkmenian wormwood. The root is taproot-like and woody. Non-fruiting shoots are shortened and woody in gray bark. Fruiting shoots are numerous, white-tomentose, rigid, and rod-like. Leaves are densely arachnoid-pubescent, 1–2 cm long. The panicle is narrow-pyramidal. It flowers in August and bears fruit in November [7].

In Turkmen folk medicine, inflorescences are used to prepare wormwood tea, which has an anthelmintic effect. In addition, wormwood oil is produced, used for fever, drowsy, and scorpion or karakurt bites [3]. The raw material is used in the food and perfume industries.

The productivity of the raw material mass was determined by us in the area of the Dushakerekdag mountain range. The operational reserve of raw materials is 9 t/100 ha, and the volume of possible annual harvesting (90% of it) is 8.1 t.

Thus, the resources of wild medicinal plants are of paramount importance for the healthcare of Turkmenistan; they are a source of biologically active substances. However, when developing plans for their development, it is necessary to take into account the state and characteristics of the development of each plant community and individual specimens. At the current stage, a number of new requirements have been formed for the conduct of work on the procurement of raw materials, the most important of which are:

- ensuring the possibility of forecasting the dynamics of raw material reserves of plants that represent industrial resource potential;
- full coverage of all main resource indicators for a specific plant species;
- development of effective practical measures for the protection and rational use of the studied species;
- introduction into practice of remote sensing methods and integrated study of the medicinal plant resources of Kopetdag.

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CONDITIONS FOR KEEPING A NORTHERN FUR SEAL AT THE CHITA CITY ZOO

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Abstract. *Zoos and other institutions are playing an increasingly significant role in the conservation of species threatened with extinction. However, this approach necessitates a measured consideration: on the one hand, these institutions aid in protecting rare species, but on the other hand, maintaining animals in artificial environments can adversely affect their physical and psychological well-being. According to studies, restricted living conditions in captivity frequently lead to stereotypic behaviors in various species. This article describes the conditions for keeping the northern fur seal at MBUK ‘Chita City Zoo.’*

Keywords: *Zabaykalsky Krai, northern fur seal, zoo.*

The Municipal Budgetary Cultural Institution ‘Chita City Zoo’ (MBUK ‘Chita City Zoo’) is located in the city of Chita, Zabaykalsky Krai. The main activity type according to OKVED-2 91.04 is the operation of botanical gardens, zoos, state nature reserves, and national parks. The founder is the administration of the urban district of the city of Chita.

The Chita City Zoo is located within the Trans-Baikal Krai, in the city of Chita. The zoo occupies an area of over 14 hectares and comprises approximately 250 animal species. In July 2006, the Chita City Zoo established a structural subdivision – the ‘Amodovo’ zoo nursery – a center for the reproduction of rare animal species listed in the Russian Red Data Book and the International Red Data Book, occupying an area of 11.9914 hectares [1].

The climate of the region is characterized by cold winters and dry summers. The average temperature in the city of Chita during winter is approximately –18 °C,

while in summer it ranges from 20 to 22 °C. These climatic conditions necessitate special care for the animals maintained in the zoo.

The northern fur seal (*Callorhinus ursinus*) is among the popular species kept in zoos not only in Russia but also worldwide. Within Russia, this mammalian species is maintained in several zoological institutions, including the Chita City Zoo.

There is only a single species within the genus – the northern fur seal. Sexual dimorphism is strongly pronounced: males reach a body length of up to 2.1 m and a weight of up to 300 kg, while females measure up to 1.5 m in length and weigh up to 65 kg. The body conformation of males is robust, whereas that of females is slender and graceful [2].

The flippers are very long and devoid of hair. The cartilaginous tips of the digits, which support the edges of the flippers, are highly developed. The claws on the front flippers are barely perceptible. The hind flippers are capable of folding backward to facilitate terrestrial locomotion. The snout is shortened and pointed. The eyes are small and widely spaced. The external pinnae measure up to 5 cm in length. The vibrissae are smooth, yellowish-white, and range from 30 to 35 cm in length.

Northern fur seals are the only members of the Otariidae family that, except for the first three months of life, possess a waterproof dense fur coat throughout their lifespan, which, due to the unique structure of the fur, does not become waterlogged [2].

At the Chita City Zoo resides a northern fur seal named Mark, born in 2011. He was brought to the zoo in 2014.

The average body length is approximately 200 cm. Unfortunately, his weight is unknown. The fur color is dark with brown patches, and a scruff on the nape.

During the summer months, from April to October, Mark is housed in an outdoor enclosure measuring 120 m². The enclosure features pathways paved with large stones, which Mark uses for movement. The enclosure is enclosed with 3D mesh and divided into two sections. The primary section contains the main pool, with a volume of 13 m³, a depth of 1.70 m, and is equipped with an emaux v350 filter. Mark spends most of his time here, as it is his preferred zone; he feeds, sleeps, and swims in this area. He sleeps not in the water, but on the broad ledge of the pool. The second section also contains a small additional pool with a volume of 4 m³, which Mark uses during the cleaning of the main pool. The area was previously designated as a feeding and visitor-free resting zone; additionally, part of the enclosure is enclosed by a green fence composed of shrubs. In summer, the surface water temperature ranges from 18 to 22 °C. The water in the pools is artificially prepared by dissolving salt in tap water. The salinity of the pool water is 3‰, with a pH of 7.

During the winter period, from October to March, Mark is kept in a separate building that is closed to visitors. The room measures 25 m² and contains a small pool with a volume of 7 m³. The room is heated. The ambient temperature is

maintained at 12–15 °C. An ultraviolet lamp is installed on the wall, which is used when the northern fur seal is absent from the enclosure. There are also resting platforms, consisting of heavy wooden pallets; during the winter, Mark spends most of his time on these platforms, occasionally entering the water for periods of 3 to 5 days.

All pools are cleaned exclusively by mechanical methods. Without the use of chlorine-containing, chemical, or other cleaning agents.

During the rutting period, which typically lasts 1.5–2 months for Mark and occurs from late March to early June, the male becomes active, displays threatening lunges towards unfamiliar personnel, and exhibits aggressive behavior and hostility towards strangers. His feeding is excellent. He spends considerable time both in the water and on the haul-out site that he has personally selected – a wide corner of the pool, which also serves as a feeding area.

Mark is sensitive to weather changes and, prior to adverse weather, tends to sleep extensively, swim sluggishly, and occasionally refuse food. This condition may persist for several days.

A distinctive characteristic of the feeding behavior of marine mammals is its diversity, even among species exhibiting more or less pronounced trophic specialization.

Mark is very selective and capricious with food, especially during periods of low motivation. If the seal detects a vitamin supplement in the fish, it refuses to feed.

In captivity, the diet of marine animals is diverse. Frozen fish is used in the conditions of the Chita City Zoo. Typically, Mark receives pink salmon, herring, capelin, anchovy, baltic herring, perch, navaga, pollock, and squid. He also regularly receives the essential vitamins B1, C, and E. For the northern fur seal, the vitamin preparation Aquavit 692006 is used; it is concealed in fish and administered once daily during feeding.

At the Chita City Zoo, the northern fur seal is fed three times daily according to a set schedule. The first feeding takes place at 9:00, the second feeding at 14:00, and the third at 17:00. Each feeding consists of 2 to 3 kg of fish. The daily intake ranges from 6 to 12 kg of fish, depending on the season. One feeding comprises 60% pink salmon, with the remaining 40% made up of fish such as herring, Baltic herring, capelin, and squid (selection depends on the dietary preferences of the pinniped).

The northern fur seal at the Chita City Zoo exhibits specific food preferences. He prefers pink salmon above all. An attempt was made to accustom him to sockeye salmon, but the fish did not elicit interest from the seal.

From 2015 to 2018, his diet included fish species such as capelin, anchovy, occasionally squid, and herring. In early June 2018, the northern fur seal began to refuse food, ignoring it and showing no interest. Nevertheless, his condition was assessed as satisfactory. This period lasted approximately one week.

Feeding subsequently resumed with pink salmon. During feeding, Mark showed enjoyment of the fish, eating carefully and with abundant salivation. Currently, the primary component in the northern fur seal's diet remains pink salmon. Initially, it was provided sliced without bones and fins; subsequently, it was served including bones and fins.

At present, the northern fur seal can readily consume an entire medium-sized pink salmon, tearing it into pieces while firmly gripping the head with its canines. Mark makes several sharp and powerful lateral lunges until the fish softens.

The weekly diet is also not always evenly distributed throughout the days of the week. Transition periods should be taken into account, for example, when changing seasonal feeding standards, during which the animal gradually adapts to consuming larger amounts of feed. The same occurs when changing the type of feed if the newly introduced feed item is less preferred.

Occasionally, routine procedures of special feeding are planned for preventive veterinary purposes, such as during routine health screenings, periods of deworming, and similar situations. In cases of animal illnesses, veterinary specialists develop special diets and feeding regimens. However, all the aforementioned regimes fall under the responsibility of the veterinary service and are determined in each specific case by its specialists.

The habitat and conditions for keeping northern fur seals in the zoo differ significantly from their natural living environment. Despite this, the Chita City Zoo endeavors to establish high-quality conditions for the animals' captivity that are as close as possible to their natural environment. Overall, the Chita City Zoo has established satisfactory conditions for the habitation of the northern fur seal.

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AGING AND SOCIETY IN AZERBAIJAN: CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES

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Abstract. *The North-West region of Azerbaijan, comprising both urban and rural populations, faces unique demographic trends due to an aging population. This article explores the socio-economic and medico-biological challenges posed by an aging society in this region, including issues of healthcare, social welfare, employment, and intergenerational dynamics. Additionally, the study highlights local initiatives and government policies aimed at addressing these challenges and fostering a more inclusive and supportive environment for older populations. Data from recent census reports, field studies, and national surveys are analyzed to provide an in-depth understanding of the region's aging trends and their implications for the future. This study examines the physiological health conditions, also demographic-social atmosphere of older individuals in the North-West region of Azerbaijan. Factors such as chronic diseases, functional limitations, and access to healthcare services are analyzed. The findings highlight the interplay between regional socio-economic conditions, medico-biological conditions, migration trends, and traditional family structures in shaping older individuals' health outcomes. Policy recommendations are discussed to improve healthcare access and quality of life for the aging population in these rural communities.*

Key words: *Aging, gerontological age groups, longitudinal studies, physiological and sociological studies.*

Introduction: Aging populations are increasing globally, with significant demographic and health implications. Population aging is a critical demographic phenomenon affecting countries worldwide, including Azerbaijan Republic (4,5,10,15,24). Azerbaijan, like many countries worldwide, is experiencing a demographic shift

characterized by a growing older population. The United Nations defines the elderly as individuals aged 60 and above (2,3,7,8). In recent decades, Azerbaijan's fertility rate has declined, while life expectancy has risen, contributing to a gradual aging of the population. According to data from the State Statistical Committee of Azerbaijan, the proportion of people aged 65 and over has been steadily increasing, and projections indicate this trend will continue in the future.

Demographic changes in Azerbaijan, driven by declining fertility rates and increasing life expectancy, are projected to result in an aging population structure, with the proportion of older individuals (aged 60 and above) expected to rise significantly by 2050. According to projections, by 2050 the proportion of individuals aged 60 and above, particularly those in the 80+ age group, is expected to increase significantly (3). In particular, the North-West region of Azerbaijan, which includes districts faces distinct challenges and opportunities related to its aging population. The region is a mixture of urban and rural areas, with a significant rural population that has its own unique needs when it comes to elderly care and services. Life expectancy in Azerbaijan has been increasing. The average life expectancy in Azerbaijan was approximately 73 years in 2020, and this number is expected to continue rising. The older population in Azerbaijan is expected to make up a significant portion of the overall demographic by 2050, with projections estimating that the population aged 60 and over will account for over 20% of the total population (7,14).

Population aging has become an increasingly important demographic issue in Azerbaijan. Although the country still maintains a relatively young population structure compared to many European nations, the proportion of older adults has been gradually rising. This trend is especially visible in rural, foothill and mountainous regions, where youth migration and socio-economic transformations intensify demographic aging. The North-West region represent a distinct socio-cultural and geographic context. These regions are characterized by rural settlements, agricultural livelihoods, multiethnic communities (such as the Azerbaijani, Avar, Tsakhur, Rutul, Ingiloy and et al.), and strong family traditions. However, recent migration patterns, declining fertility, and limited economic diversification have accelerated the aging of their local populations. Understanding the social and economic implications of aging in these areas is crucial for informing regional development policies, health-care planning, and community support systems.

Unlike long-livers, older age groups, such as the elderly and the senile population, often experience disruptions in carbohydrate and lipid metabolism, high blood pressure, diabetes mellitus, obesity, metabolic disorders, elevated levels of prothrombin in the blood, stress, genetic predisposition, and other related symptoms. Also decrease in physical activity is a significant risk factor for the development of coronary artery disease in elderly individuals, and in older individuals, this decline directly contributes to the onset of such diseases.

The significant physiological changes observed in gerontological age groups – particularly those affecting the cardiovascular system, the functions of the nervous system, and disorders within the endocrine system – undoubtedly influence the rate of aging in older individuals and accelerate the overall aging process of the organism (4,5,10,11,12,13,14,15,24). It is well established that one of the key indicators determining the rate of aging in the organism is the condition of the cardiovascular, endocrine, and nervous systems. In gerontological age groups, including the elderly, senile, and long-livers, no significant differences were found between men and women in terms of overall physiological health status. At the same time, similarities were observed in the levels of life satisfaction, nutritional conditions, and lifestyle habits.

Although there are similarities in the predictors of life satisfaction between men and women, differences emerge when considering various life circumstances. First, age plays a role in the gender differences observed in life satisfaction. Older men are more likely to report higher levels of life satisfaction than women, whereas the opposite tends to be true among younger age groups. In Canada, 89.6% of men and 90.6% of women aged 65 and older reported being satisfied or very satisfied with their lives, indicating a high level of subjective well-being among older adults in both genders (16,18).

Health is a key predictor of life satisfaction, as poor physical and mental health, along with low self-rated general health, are associated with reduced quality of life and lower subjective well-being. The relationship between health and life satisfaction is observed in both men and women and may be influenced by both biological sex and socially constructed gender roles. Although women tend to live longer than men, older women more frequently report health problems – such as depression – that can negatively affect life satisfaction (6,18,20). Social and economic factors may also underlie the differences in life satisfaction between men and women. These factors are often rooted more in gender-based social norms, roles, and cultural expectations than in biological sex, and they may also be influenced by generational experiences (16,28).

In the Caucasus region, particularly in Azerbaijan, older individuals are treated with great kindness and care within families and even in the broader society. It is possible that one of the factors contributing to the longevity of people in the Caucasus is precisely these sincere, nurturing, and affectionate family relationships, as well as the high regard given to the social roles of elders – such as respected male and female elders (as it is traditionally stated in the Azerbaijani context – *agsaqal* and *agbirchek*). The sense of being valued and considered important both within the family and in the community may play a significant role in promoting their long life.

Studying the aging process in the North-West region is crucial due to its unique socio-economic composition. This area is marked by a mixture of agricultural areas

and urban centers, and as such, it represents both traditional and more modern approaches to older care. The population density is lower in rural areas, which often lack sufficient healthcare and social services for the older people. Moreover, the migration of younger populations to urban centers like Baku and abroad has left many older individuals without adequate support networks. Understanding these dynamics can guide more effective policy responses and community-based interventions to better address the needs of an aging population. Additionally, this region's cultural traditions play a crucial role in how older people are treated and supported by their families and communities, making it an interesting subject of study for aging research. In the North-West region of Azerbaijan, comprising districts such as Balakan, Zagatala, and Gakh, rural communities are particularly affected due to migration of younger populations to urban centers and abroad, leaving older individuals with reduced family support.

This study aims to investigate the physiological health conditions of older residents (gerontological age groups) in this region, with specific attention to chronic diseases, functional limitations, healthcare accessibility, and medico-biological, socio-economic factors that influence overall well-being.

Methodology: This study was conducted in the North-West region of Azerbaijan. The research focuses on three administrative regions in the North-West region of Azerbaijan: Balakan, Zagatala and Gakh. These regions are predominantly rural, mountainous, foothills, plains and characterized by limited healthcare infrastructure. Across the region, we included 233 elderly individuals (n=233), 205 senile individuals (n=205), and 125 long-liver persons (n=125) in the study.

Results: The primary objective of our research was to assess the physiological health status of older individuals. In this region, we included elderly, senile, and long-liver residents from all three regions in the study. Older residents in Balakan, Zagatala and Gakh (10,11,13,14) are prone to various age-related physiological conditions:

Cardiovascular diseases: Hypertension, ischemic heart disease, and arrhythmias are prevalent due to lifestyle factors, dietary patterns, and limited access to specialized care.

Neurodegenerative disorders: Alzheimer's disease, Parkinson's disease, Dementia, Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis.

Metabolic disorders: Diabetes mellitus, obesity, and dyslipidemia are frequently observed, exacerbated by sedentary lifestyles in older age. Reduced activity levels in old age contribute to disease progression.

Musculoskeletal disorders: Arthritis, osteoporosis, and mobility limitations are common, affecting daily functioning and independence.

Sensory impairments: Hearing and vision loss are reported, particularly among those over 80 years old.

Functional Limitations: Many elderly and senile individuals experience reduced mobility and difficulties in performing activities of daily living, such as cooking, bathing, or transporting themselves to healthcare facilities. Rural infrastructure and limited transportation exacerbate these challenges.

However, among the long-liver residents, there are also those with mobility limitations and certain changes in their health. They are provided with moral support by family members or close relatives.

But many of the long-livers living in these regions and reaching the age of 90 have maintained their physical activity. Some of them even engage in certain forms of physical labor within their household premises. Moreover, many have been able to maintain their working capacity up to this age and possess the ability to independently manage their personal needs.

Several factors such as age, sex, illness, functional decline, and social circumstances that are associated with life satisfaction are likewise related to the need for and utilization of various health and long-term care services. Consequently, the factors that increase the need for care may simultaneously diminish life satisfaction, indicating that changes in these factors are linked to corresponding changes in both the need for and receipt of care, overall life satisfaction (23,25).

When confronted with health problems, individuals employ a variety of coping strategies, which are in turn associated with their level of life satisfaction. These coping strategies differ by age and gender. Receiving care can be viewed as one form of coping; however, it differs from active strategies – such as planning or acceptance – in that it involves a degree of dependence on another person (22). As an individual begins to require informal assistance, their dependence on others increases (17). The human organism functions gradually wearing down over time. The rate and extent of this deterioration are proportional to the amount of stress or trauma it has experienced (21).

In studies conducted in numerous countries reviewed identified a higher prevalence of chronic diseases among retired workers compared to their non-retired counterparts, both in terms of the number of conditions and the years prior to the onset of chronic illnesses. Previous reviews focused on cardiovascular disease have indicated that retirement is associated with an increase in cardiovascular disease events among European retirees, while no significant effect was observed in the United States (29). The findings of Gabriela Nazar, Maria-Francisca Cabezas, et al. (9) also suggest that retirement may exert indirect effects on chronic conditions through changes in lifestyle behaviors and social group membership. The relationship between health and retirement is multifaceted, influenced by both work-related factors (e. g., job demands) and individual factors.

Older individuals in the North-West region of Azerbaijan exhibit a high prevalence of chronic, age-related disorders (10,13).

Demographic Characteristics of Aging in the North-West region of Azerbaijan: This region is ethnically diverse, with Azerbaijani, Avar, Tsakhur, Ingiloy and other ethnic populations. It is predominantly rural, with agriculture forming a significant part of the local economy. According to the State Statistical Committee of Azerbaijan, the population of the region was approximately 1.3 million people as of 2020. The older population (aged 60 and above) in this region currently represents around 15–17% of the total population, slightly higher than the national average, which is around 14%. Age pyramids for the North-West show an increasing older age dependency ratio. This means that the working-age population is shrinking in comparison to the growing older population, which could have long-term economic implications for the region.

Discussion: The physiological health status of older populations in the North-West region of Azerbaijan is strongly influenced by demographic trends, environmental, such as rural living conditions, and socio-economic factors. The combination of chronic diseases, limited mobility, and insufficient healthcare infrastructure poses a significant challenge. Regional and national policies need to prioritize access to healthcare, active aging initiatives, and community-based support programs to improve health outcomes and quality of life for the elderly and senile.

As an individual's health and functioning decline with age, the need for assistance to manage daily activities at home typically increases. This support may come from informal sources, such as family and friends, or from formal paid services, commonly known as formal home care. The primary goal of home care is to mitigate the negative impacts of poor health and to enhance both health outcomes and quality of life within the home environment. As health declines, life satisfaction may also diminish, reflecting the well-established correlation between health and overall life satisfaction. Life satisfaction is generally defined as an individual's global evaluation of their life circumstances and is widely regarded as a key indicator of well-being (1,18,19).

Just as successful aging has been defined in multiple heterogeneous ways, frailty may likewise encompass a range of definitions that are equally valid and specific to an individual at a particular moment. This individualized perspective may be precisely what clinicians should seek during clinical encounters (21,26,27).

The main factors such as health and functional ability, which are associated with life satisfaction, are also closely related to care needs. Addressing these health and functional requirements through home care may help maintain or improve health and functional capacity, thereby preventing the need for additional care and positively influencing life satisfaction. However, the factors that explain the need for care do not fully account for the decline in life satisfaction observed among those receiving informal care. As the population of older adults continues to grow, and as more older men and women are cared for at home, formal home care services

should be tailored to individual needs – taking into account both health and social factors – to effectively support overall well-being (18).

Conclusion: Aging in the North-West region of Azerbaijan is characterized by an increasing prevalence of chronic diseases, functional limitations, and socio-economic vulnerabilities. Interventions addressing healthcare access, social support, and economic security are essential to ensure dignified and healthy aging. Future research should focus on longitudinal studies and localized surveys to better understand the evolving needs of this population.

The aging of the population in this region is shaped by regional socio-economic realities, migration trends, and traditional family structures. While strong cultural norms continue to provide older adults with respect and community identity, major challenges persist in healthcare access, social support, and financial security. Addressing these issues requires coordinated action from local authorities, national policymakers, and community organizations to ensure a healthy and dignified aging experience for the region's older population.

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MICROBIAL ORIGIN CONDUITS AS A PROMISING MATERIAL FOR REGENERATIVE BIOMEDICINE¹

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Abstract. Using an original design of a simple bioreactor, conduits based on bacterial cellulose (BC) were obtained by culturing *Komagataeibacter sucrofermentans* B-11267 on Hestrin-Schramm medium, molasses medium, and molasses medium supplemented with 1% polyvinyl alcohol (PVA). The structure and physicochemical properties of the conduits were characterized by scanning electron microscopy (SEM), X-ray tomography, X-ray diffraction, and thermogravimetric analysis. It was shown that the highest degree of crystallinity was observed in conduits produced in the molasses-based medium. According to thermogravimetric analysis, the most thermally stable samples were those obtained in Hestrin-Schramm medium and in the molasses medium without the addition of PVA. Thus, conduits based on BC produced on a molasses medium demonstrated great potential for application in regenerative biomedicine for damaged organs and tissues.

Keywords: conduits, bacterial cellulose, regenerative biomedicine.¹

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Introduction

Regenerative biomedicine, which has emerged at the intersection of fundamental natural sciences, currently represents a fundamentally new direction in the diagnosis and treatment of various diseases based on advanced gene and cell technologies. The results of biomedical research underpin the analysis of various biochemical and genetic processes, enabling the elucidation of their mechanisms and the prevention of the development of numerous severe pathological conditions. Nevertheless, the successful advancement of modern biomedicine is inextricably connected to the achievements of biotechnology, specifically the application of various biomaterials in the treatment of numerous diseases. At present, there exist several acute and unresolved challenges, namely the restoration of function in damaged cellular and tissue structures. A promising approach is the development of biopolymer conduits, which can be employed both to accelerate the regeneration of damaged nerve conductors and to replace sclerotized segments of blood vessels [1].

Currently, conduits composed of various materials of synthetic and natural origin are under active investigation. Among synthetic polymers used in conduits, polyglycolic acid, poly-L-lactic acid, and polyvinyl alcohol combined with chitosan are frequently cited in the literature. Nevertheless, materials of natural origin are always preferable compared to those obtained by chemical synthesis. Biocompatible materials applied in the fabrication of conduits include collagen, gelatin, fibronectin, silk fibroin, chitosan, and hyaluronic acid. In recent years, among biopolymers of natural origin, BC has attracted particular attention due to its high biocompatibility, low cytotoxicity [2, 3], and unique nanofibrillar structure [4]. Fibers of BC form a three-dimensional porous network that provides high mechanical strength and permeability to gases and liquids [5, 6, 7], which is critically important for conduits. The high crystallinity of BC confers resistance to enzymatic degradation, which is beneficial for long-term *in vivo* applications [8].

Based on the above, the objective of this study was to produce conduits from bacterial cellulose using standard Hestrin and Schramm medium, molasses medium, and molasses medium supplemented with 1% PVA, followed by a comparative analysis of their structure and physicochemical properties.

Materials and Methods

Conduits based on BC were produced by fermentation of *K. sacrofermentans* B-11267 in a container equipped with two silicone tubes, each 200 cm long and with an internal diameter of 5 mm, using the standard Hestrin and Schramm (HS) medium (g/l): glucose (20) (LLC «Promsintez», CAS number 5996–10–1, Chap-ayevsk, Russia, specially pure), peptone (5) (Research Center of Pharmacotherapy, Saint Petersburg, Russia), yeast extract (5) (State Research Center of Applied

Microbiology and Biotechnology, Obolensk, Russia), citric acid (1.15) (chemical reagent, Nizhny Novgorod, Russia, CAS number 77–92–9, specially pure, purity 99.8%), and disodium hydrogen phosphate (2.7) (LabTech, Moscow, Russia, CAS No. 7783–28–0, Pro Analysis), pH 6.0; media based on molasses and by adding 1% PVA to the molasses medium. The media were inoculated with 10% (w/w) inoculum obtained by the method described previously [9]. For this purpose, under aseptic conditions, liquid nutrient medium and inoculum were added to the container. *K. Komagataeibacter sucrofermentans B-11267* was cultivated for 7 days with the nutrient medium being stirred twice in each tube. A peristaltic dosing pump LOIP LS-301 (LOIP, Saint Petersburg, Russia) operating at a rotor speed of 200 rpm was used for stirring. To release the obtained conduits from the silicone tubes, a procedure analogous to medium agitation was performed, during which the biopolymer was flushed out of the tubes by a water flow. The tubular BC structures were autoclaved at 121 °C for 20 minutes.

The surface morphology of the BC conduits was investigated using SEM coupled with a scanning probe microscope SPM 9600 ‘Shimadzu’ (Japan) and X-ray tomography on a micro-CT scanner Skyscan 1172 ‘Bruker’ (Belgium). The degree of crystallinity was determined by X-ray structural analysis using an EMPYREAN diffractometer (PANalytical, Netherlands) equipped with a PJXce13D detector in reflection mode (CuK_α-radiation). Selected samples measuring 30×30 mm were mounted in the apparatus for measurement. Substrate – amorphous silicon. Programmable target with an illuminated length of 16 mm. The degree of crystallinity was calculated using the formula:

$$X = \frac{I_{002} - I_{am}}{I_{002}} \times 100\%$$

where I_{002} is the total intensity of the crystalline 002 peak; $I_{002} - I_{\text{ext}\{am\}}$ – intensity of the crystalline 002 peak with the background signal subtracted.

Thermogravimetric analysis to determine the thermal stability and degradation of bacterial cellulose-based conduits was performed using a TG 209 F1 Libra thermobalance (Netzsch, Germany).

The obtained experimental data were subjected to statistical processing using Microsoft Excel 2016 spreadsheets. Comparison of experimental variants was performed at a 5% significance level using analysis of variance (ANOVA).

Research results

Using SEM, it was established that the obtained conduits possess a unique nanoscale mesh structure composed of thin fibers with diameters one hundred times smaller than those of plant fibers. The thickness of BC conduit fibrils synthesized on all types of media employed ranges from 50 to 60 nm. The use of

X-ray tomography demonstrated that the conduits exhibit a homogeneous porous structure across all experimental series. X-ray diffraction analysis was employed to assess the crystalline structure of conduits produced in various media. It was demonstrated that the conduits possess an identical chemical structure but differ in their degree of crystallinity. The results indicated that in the medium containing molasses, the degree of crystallinity of the conduits (83%) was higher compared to the standard HS medium (79%) and the medium supplemented with 1% PVA (64%). These findings are most likely associated with the fact that PVA impedes the ordering of the cellulose chains in the composites, thereby reducing the amount of the crystalline phase. Furthermore, thermal stability is a key property that enables the thermal treatment of the produced conduits and is considered one of the most important characteristics for their use in regenerative biomedicine. The conducted studies analyzed the thermal stability and degradation characteristics of conduits synthesized on various media to evaluate their potential application under high-temperature conditions, such as thermal processing, using thermogravimetric analysis. Conduit samples obtained on Hestrin and Schramm medium and on molasses medium retained thermal stability up to 305 °C, while the sample modified with 1% PVA remained stable up to 290 °C. At higher temperatures, the materials underwent degradation. Moreover, samples obtained on Hestrin and Schramm medium and on molasses medium demonstrated greater thermal stability, as at 340 °C their mass loss amounted to 30%, compared to a 47% mass loss in the modified BC sample. It is known that the thermal stability of any material depends on its crystallinity. Since higher crystallinity corresponds to stronger polymer chains, interchain breakage will consequently be hindered [10, 11]. Thus, the conduit synthesized in a molasses-based medium exhibits the highest degree of crystallinity and thermal stability compared to other samples, making its application in regenerative medicine promising.

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ASSESSMENT OF RIVER PORT SOIL CONTAMINATION BY OIL PRODUCTS USING GEOPHYSICAL METHODS

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Abstract. Existing methods for determining the type and concentration of ecotoxicants require expensive equipment, qualified personnel, considerable time expenditures, and regular calibration. A solution to the current problem is the use of an automated soil contamination monitoring system that detects electrically contrasting ecotoxicants, specifically oil and petroleum products, at industrial sites. Identification of ecologically hazardous zones was conducted based on anomalies in specific electrical resistivity (UES) detected through electrical sounding methods. It was established that the magnitude of the UES of the sandy-clay layer is governed by the proportions and texture of the three-phase pore filler (air – soil moisture – oil products). The formation of continuous water pathways reduces the UES to 200–400 Ohm·m, while their disruption by oil products increases resistivity to 800–4000 Ohm·m. Along three profiles ranging from 50 to 120 m in length, zones of oil and moisture saturation were delineated. These areas have been designated for the installation of sensors within a system for continuous remote monitoring of spatiotemporal processes.

Keywords: ecotoxicant; oil product; monitoring; geology; ground-penetrating radar. Electrical sounding.

Introduction. The intensive development of enterprises within the fuel and energy sector of the Russian Federation (oil, gas, and coal industries) is accompanied by increasing challenges related to environmental pollution. A primary task is the prompt localization and characterization of technogenic contamination zones at industrial sites prior to the initiation of reclamation measures [1–4]. The main soil contaminants at industrial sites are hydrocarbons, including fuels, lubricants, bitumens, petrochemical feedstocks, and organic solvents [5–8].

A suite of geological, chemical, and biological methods is employed to identify the composition, concentration, and migration of ecotoxicants. Thus, in the study [9], toxicity assessment of oil-contaminated soils was conducted using bioindicators

(*Daphnia magna Straus*), while in the studies [10–12], the content of oil products was determined by fluorimetric, photometric, and spectroscopic methods.

The aforementioned methods require costly equipment, highly qualified personnel, and considerable time resources. An alternative may be the use of an automated soil contamination monitoring system employing electrically contrasting ecotoxicants, currently being developed at KuzGTU [13]. To justify the placement of the monitoring system at the selected site, preliminary engineering-geological and geophysical surveys are necessary, including vertical electrical sounding (VEZ) and electrical profiling (EP).

Ground-penetrating radar (non-contact subsurface electromagnetic sounding using GPR) effectively detects anomalous zones by their dielectric properties over extensive areas. Electrical prospecting methods (VEZ and EP) are based on measuring the apparent specific electrical resistivity (UES) with depth and along the profile. Their combined application provides a comprehensive understanding of the soil body structure. The informativeness and reliability of these methods have been confirmed through field investigations [14–17].

The objective of this work is to develop a methodology for the industrial implementation of a system for continuous remote monitoring of soil contamination processes by oil products at an industrial site, based on detecting spatiotemporal anomalies in the electrical conductivity properties of the ecotoxicant.

Research Methodology. The research program included the following: analysis of the geological structure of industrial enterprise foundation soils, identification of sources and pathways of pollutant migration, a comprehensive regional forecast of the baseline level of soil contamination by oil products, localization of main contamination areas, implementation of a continuous eco-monitoring system based on anomalies in electrical conductivity, compilation of databases, and calibration of equipment.

The subject of the study is a river port situated on the riverbank with a total area of 315303 m². Previously, the Siberian Federal University (SFU) conducted comprehensive geophysical and engineering-geological surveys, which allowed for clarifying the geological structure of the massif, identifying sources of oil contamination, and providing a regional forecast of its spread. Based on the SFU surveys, three sites have been selected for detailed electrical soundings, where the KuzGTU continuous eco-monitoring system is planned to be deployed. Electrical survey methods (VEZ and EP) were performed by KuzGTU using the computerized device ‘Electrotest-2Pm/bt’ operating under direct current with automatic electrode polarization compensation.

Results and their analysis. The study confirmed the presence of soil and groundwater contamination by oil products. The primary source of contamination is an out-of-service oil depot located on the adjacent site. Four contamination

zones were identified by ground-penetrating radar methods, with their conditional delineation based on the concentrations of oil products in soils and the degree of contamination hazard to the river's water basin (Fig. 2 a, b).

Figure 1. Results of ground-penetrating radar (a), engineering-geological, and environmental (b) investigations at SFU:

- – boreholes; ☁ – concentration of oil products $K > 20$ g/kg; ☁ – $K = 3-20$ g/kg;
- ☁ – $K = 0.5-3$ g/kg; ☁ – $K < 0.5$ g/kg; → – direction of groundwater flow

The most hazardous area ($K > 20$ g/kg) with a size of approximately 200 m² is confined to the shoreline. No lenses containing free oil products were identified by ground-penetrating radar methods. The geological profile at depths of 2.5–4 m comprises dry, dense sand-gravel deposits, while at depths of 4–10 m, moist sand-gravel soil is present. The depth of groundwater occurrence varies within the range of 7 to 14 m.

The second section ($K = 3–20$ g/kg) is located along the shoreline, covering an area of approximately 4000 m². Contaminated soils are found at depths up to 8 m, with the volume of contaminated soils reaching 24,000 m³. The boundary of the frontal occurrence of soils and soil deposits contaminated with oil products from the river shoreline ranges from 4 to 6 m.

The third section ($K = 0.5–3$ g/kg) is located along the railway tracks and occupies an area of about 25,000 m². Oil products are located at depths of 2–11 m, with maximum concentrations observed at depths of 4–11 m. Soil contaminated by oil products is in contact with groundwater. The total volume of contaminated soil in this area reaches up to 225,000 m³.

The fourth, non-hazardous zone ($K < 0.5$ g/kg — background contamination) is situated in the northeastern part of the river port, along the railway tracks extending to the river shoreline, covering a total area of approximately 71,000 m².

Based on the regional forecast performed by SFU, a detailed delineation of identified pollution hotspots was carried out for the subsequent establishment of continuous monitoring within their territories. Electrical soundings (VEZ and EP) were conducted along three designated profiles; the results are presented in Figures 3 and 4.

Figure 3. VEZ results along profiles 1 (a), 2 (b), and 3 (c):
 ■ – anomalous zone contaminated with oil products

A combined analysis of the VEZ and EP results along with engineering-geological data revealed the following characteristics of the geoelectric section.

The wavelike shape of the UES curves is characteristic of multilayer media. The main contribution to the results of the soundings is made by the layer of loosened moist sandy-gravel soil, the UES of which is entirely determined by the volumetric ratio and texture of the three-phase pore filler (air — soil moisture — oil products). Air and oil products act as dielectrics, whereas soil moisture acts as a conductor. When continuous water pathways are formed, ρk decreases to 200–400 Ohm·m; if the oil filler disrupts these pathways or insulates the pore surfaces with increasing concentration, the value of ρk increases in the range of 800–4000 Ohm·m.

A depth coefficient equal to 0.15 was established, resulting in an effective depth of investigation $h = 0.15 AB$. At a current electrode spacing $AB < 15$ m ($h < 2.25$ m), the oil-saturated layer is not detected. The rational value of the sounding base is $AB = 35$ m ($h = 5.25$ m), which corresponds to the midpoint of the oil-saturated layer.

The following zones were delineated based on the sounding results:

- in the VEZ graph of profile 1 (Fig. 3, a), an oil-saturated soil zone was identified at the depth interval $h = 1.75$ –7.5 m, while in the EP graph (Fig. 4, a), an oil-saturated soil zone was detected at the profile interval $x = 7.5$ –95 m and an oil- and moisture-saturated soil zone at the interval $x = -25$ –7.5 m;

- on the VEZ graph of profile 2 (Fig. 3b), a zone of oil- and moisture-saturated soils was identified at the depth interval $h = 2.25$ –6.75 m; on the EP graph (Fig. 4b), a zone of oil-saturated soils was observed at the profile interval $x = 2$ –25 m, and a zone of oil- and moisture-saturated soils at the interval $x = -27$ –2 m;

- on the VEZ graph of profile 3 (Fig. 3c), a zone of moisture-saturated soils was identified at the depth interval $h = 2$ –6.5 m; on the EP graph (Fig. 4c), two zones of oil-saturated soils were observed at the profile intervals $x = 13$ –36 m and $x = 55$ –65 m, a zone of moisture-saturated soils at the profile interval $x = -20$ –13 m, and a zone of oil- and moisture-saturated soils at the interval $x = 36$ –55 m.

The identified zones of oil and moisture saturation are indicated on the site plan (Fig. 5). These areas have been designated for the installation of sensors in the continuous remote monitoring system of spatiotemporal changes within ecologically hazardous zones.

Figure 4. Results of EP for profiles 1 (a), 2 (b), and 3 (c):

1 – electrode spacing $AB = 15$ m; 2 – electrode spacing $AB = 35$ m;
 3 – zone of oil-contaminated soils; 4 – zone of oil- and moisture-saturated soils

Figure 5. Detailing of oil-contaminated zones based on VEZ and EP results along profiles 1 (a), 2 (b), and 3 (c) on the site plan:

- 1 – profile; 2 – VEZ points; 3 – zones of oil-saturated soils;
- 4 – zones of oil- and moisture-saturated soils

Conclusions.

1. Identification of ecologically hazardous zones was conducted based on anomalies in specific electrical resistivity (UES) detected through electrical sounding methods. It was established that the magnitude of the UES of the sandy-clay layer is governed by the proportions and texture of the three-phase pore filler (air – soil moisture – oil products). The formation of continuous water pathways reduces UES to 200–400 Ohm·m, whereas their disruption by oil contamination increases resistivity to 800–4000 Ohm·m.

2. Along three profiles ranging from 50 to 120 m in length, zones of oil and moisture saturation were delineated. These areas have been designated for the

installation of sensors within a system for continuous remote monitoring of spatiotemporal processes.

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COMPARATIVE ASSESSMENT OF THE CIRCADIAN RHYTHM OF TOTAL PERIPHERAL VASCULAR RESISTANCE IN CHILDREN WITH SEVERE COMBINED TRAUMATIC BRAIN INJURY

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Abstract. Data from monitoring children hospitalized at the Republican Scientific Center for Emergency Medical Care during the periods from 2016 to 2021 with severe combined traumatic brain injury (group 1), and from 2022 to 2024 (group 2) were analyzed. Emergency specialized care within the first 24 hours enabled normalization of the mesor level of the Total Peripheral Resistance circadian rhythm (TPR circadian rhythm) across all groups and subgroups. The observed strong inverse correlation between cardiac output (CO) and TPR throughout the entire observation period, along with the correlation between stroke volume (SV) and TPR – more pronounced during the first 10 days and remaining on days 11 to 30 in group 1 and subgroups 1 and 3 – indicated a predominance of a hyperdynamic hemodynamic response type with both conservative and surgical treatment methods. The duration of inversion of the Total Peripheral Resistance circadian rhythm corresponded to the severity of the sustained injury and was longer in patients who underwent surgical correction. The level of the Mesor of total peripheral resistance circadian rhythm observed in subgroup 3, which was closest to normative values compared to groups 1 and 2, was due to a more intensive stress-limiting pharmacotherapy.

Keywords: circadian rhythm, total peripheral vascular resistance, severe combined traumatic brain injury, children.

Significance. Postoperative mortality in patients with severe combined traumatic brain injury (SCTBI) is reported to be 46.8%. More than half of patients

with severe traumatic brain injury (TBI) commonly present with multiple injuries that lead to significant blood loss, systemic hypotension, and hypoxia. Prevention or appropriately targeted intensive therapy of these secondary pathological processes allows for a significant improvement in TBI outcomes in most cases. The hyperkinetic circulatory type may be associated with a marked increase in blood adrenaline concentration. Impaired oxygen delivery to the brain, concurrent with increased oxygen demand, renders the brain more vulnerable to additional damaging factors such as blood pressure fluctuations, hypoxia, and disturbances in blood rheological properties. These secondary damaging factors exacerbate the clinical status of patients with traumatic brain injury in over 50% of cases. The normal range for total peripheral vascular resistance (TPVR) is considered to be fluctuations within $1000 \text{ dyn}\cdot\text{s}\cdot\text{cm}^{-5}$ [1–6]. Due to the lack of sufficient data on hemodynamic changes in severe combined traumatic brain injury, we aimed to investigate alterations in the phase structure during the acute period and to assess the response of the circadian rhythm of total peripheral vascular resistance in children with severe combined traumatic brain injury.

Objective of the study. To study and identify the characteristics of the circadian rhythm of total peripheral vascular resistance in children with severe combined traumatic brain injury.

Materials and methods. Monitoring data of children undergoing inpatient treatment at the Russian Scientific Center for Emergency Pediatric Surgery and Trauma (RNCEPM) from 2016 to 2021 for severe combined traumatic brain injury (Group 1) and from 2022 to 2024 (Group 2) were analyzed. Children in Group 1 were admitted due to road traffic accidents (23 cases) and falls from height (11 cases); in Group 2, road traffic accidents accounted for 32 cases, and polytrauma for 5 children. An analysis of the parameters was conducted in three subgroups within both groups. In Group 1, patients in Subgroup 1 ($n=13$) received conservative therapy; children in Subgroup 2 ($n=16$) underwent extracranial surgical corrective procedures based on clinical indications; 8 patients in Subgroup 3 underwent combined cranial and extracranial surgical interventions involving a neurosurgeon, general surgeon, and traumatologist as indicated. In Group 2, 13 children received conservative therapy, 16 patients underwent extracranial operations, and 8 children underwent combined cranial and extracranial surgical procedures. No statistically significant differences in injury severity or the degree of acute cerebral insufficiency at admission to the clinic were identified between the subgroups of group 1. A slight tendency toward a decrease in the severity of traumatic injuries according to the ISS scale was noted across the subgroups of group 2. Thus, the differences amounted to 25% in subgroup 1 (>0.05), 44% in subgroup 2 ($p<0.05$), and 27% in subgroup 3 ($p<0.05$). As the condition improved with stabilization of hemodynamics and respiration, and restoration of reflexes and consciousness, patients were transferred to the specialized

department. The results indicate the absence of significant differences in the severity of CNS shock according to the Glasgow scale among the groups and subgroups.

Results and Discussion.

Table 1. Mean values of the phase structure of the circadian rhythm of total peripheral vascular resistance (TPVR) in severe combined traumatic brain injury (SCTBI), $\text{dyn}^*\text{s}*\text{cm}^{-5}$

Groups	Mesor	At acrophase	At bathyphase	Amplitude	Daily range
Group 1 Subgroup 1, 10 days	1169±97	1425±188	1007±67	255±93	418±128
Group 2 Subgroup 1, 10 days	1486±289	1881±423	1253±227	395±178	628±235
Group 1 Subgroup 2, 10 days	1098±46	1377±118	904±86	279±94	474±160
Group 2 Subgroup 2, 10 days	1566±251*	1987±316*	1269±204*	421±129	718±237
Group 1, Subgroup 3, 10 days	1008±78	1311±237	830±49	303±181	481±219
Group 2, Subgroup 3, 10 days	1070±124	1424±308	770±110	353±197	653±269
Group 1, Subgroup 1, 26 days	1120±113	1407±159	930±115	287±115	478±142
Group 2, Subgroup 1, 29 days	1621±297*	2306±546	1212±216	685±302	1094±462
Group 1, Subgroup 2, 30 days	1084±86	1400±183	870±99	316±122	529±168
Group 2, Subgroup 2, 21 days	1462±217*	1953± 196*	1133±202	491±185	820±262
Group 1, Subgroup 3, 30 days	1061±85	1324±165	872±69	263±108	452±155
Group 2, Subgroup 3, 28 days	1072±154	1468±258	716±95	396±137	752±244

* – statistically significant relative to the indicator in Group 1.

In Group 1, the average level of the Mesor of total peripheral resistance circadian rhythm during the first 10 days, as well as throughout the ICU stay across all three subgroups, remained within the physiological norm. In group 2, significantly higher values of the Mesor of total peripheral resistance circadian rhythm were observed in the second subgroup (10 days) by 42% ($p<0.05$), in the first subgroup (29 days)

by 44% ($p < 0.05$), and in the second subgroup (21 days) by 35% ($p < 0.05$) (Table 1). Additionally, a significant increase in total peripheral resistance during the acrophase was detected in the second subgroup of group 2 at 10 days by 44% ($p < 0.05$) and at 21 days by 39% ($p < 0.05$). An increase in total peripheral vascular resistance (TPVR) during the batiphase was detected in subgroup 2 of group 2 (day 10) by 40% ($p < 0.05$). The detected differences corresponded to a more pronounced stress response of peripheral hemodynamics in patients of group 2, characterized by an increase in the mesor of the circadian rhythm of TPVR, predominantly in children undergoing extracranial surgeries as well as during conservative therapy (day 29). The identified dynamics occurred in subgroup 2 of group 2, which was characterized by a reduction in the duration of intensive therapy in the ICU. Apparently, changes in peripheral hemodynamics are predominantly compensatory in nature; they not only do not cause complications but also improve the outcomes of surgical intervention and postoperative intensive care, serving as an indicator of preserved adequate regulatory functional activity of the circulatory system in less severe traumatic brain injury cases that do not require surgical treatment.

On the day of admission to the clinic, no significant deviations from the norm or differences in the Mesor of total peripheral resistance circadian rhythm were detected in the subgroups of both groups. In subgroup 1 of group 1, an increase in the Mesor of total peripheral resistance circadian rhythm was observed on days 5, 6, 7, and 8 by 28%, 32%, 30%, and 21%, respectively ($p < 0.05$). In subgroup 1 of group 2, a statistically significant increase in total peripheral resistance was also detected on days 4 through 10 by 33%, 40%, 34%, 90%, 77%, 80%, and 68%, respectively ($p < 0.05$), remaining at this level up to day 25 during subsequent days of intensive therapy. Significant differences in the level of the Mesor of total peripheral resistance circadian rhythm in the 2nd group compared to the 1st group were observed dynamically on days 5, 7, 8, 9, 10, and all subsequent days up to 25 days, indicating a more pronounced stress-induced mobilization of sympathetic regulation of peripheral hemodynamics during conservative management of traumatized children (Table 2). No significant changes in the level of the Mesor of total peripheral resistance circadian rhythm were observed over time in the 2nd subgroup of the 1st group of children. However, in the 2nd subgroup of the 2nd group, a statistically significant increase in the Mesor of total peripheral resistance circadian rhythm was detected during days 4–16, which seemingly resulted from a more gentle stress-limiting therapy in the postoperative period in cases of moderate traumatic brain injury. This approach involved limiting the administration of hypnotics, tranquilizers, and muscle relaxants, with the goal of earlier restoration of respiration, reflexes, consciousness, and independent motor activity. A significant difference in subgroup 3, present in both group 1 and group 2 of patients, was consistently the closest to normative values of the mesor of total peripheral resistance circadian rhythm in both groups. This finding

is associated with more intensive stress-limiting pharmacological therapy aimed at inhibiting mechanisms of secondary brain injury and damage to other organs in children who underwent combined cranial and extracranial surgeries intended to restore organ integrity through radical surgical intervention.

Table 2. Comparative assessment of the dynamics of the Mesor of total peripheral resistance circadian rhythm in two groups, $\text{dyn}^* \cdot \text{s} \cdot \text{cm}^{-5}$

Days	Group 1, Subgroup 1	Group 2, Subgroup 1	Group 1, Subgroup 2	Group 2, Subgroup 2	Group 1, Subgroup 3	Group 2, Subgroup 3
1	1008±87	1030±114	1031±121	1284±121	1062±197	1354±281
2	990±39	998±60	1025±57	1132±96	828±47	1084±113
3	1125±110	1242±105	1102±58	1145±88	910±51	769±77
4	1162±102	1377±101*	1177±69	1445±88"	897±52	787±66
5	1291±109 *	1434±64 ***	1130±98	1782±155 "	1022±60	1084±77
6	1337±121 *	1389±105 *	1103±56	1734±131 "	1045±72	1109±97
7	1306±141 *	1965±294 ***	1098±52	1671±148 "	1095±91	1034±130
8	1227±91 *	1824±150 *	1009±46	1678±118 "	1039±73	1133±200
9	1156±49	1854±122 *	1207±121	1880±345 "	1109±74	1147±161
10	1092±60	1746±266 *	1102±75	1905±133 "	1074±84	1203±212
11	1176±77	1620±187 *	1040±84	1320±147 "	1136±90	1165±166
12	1178±67	1650±179 *	1057±99	1564±243 "	1027±82	906±99
13	1272±67	1362±401	1053±81	1499±167 "	1034±114	863±125
14	1153±87	1746±290 *	1185±117	1538±150	1204±75	983±181
15	1301±55	1807±314 *	1062±44	1517±216 "	1075±71	1057±119
16	1228±101	1855±270 *	1099±85	1541±139 "	1023±55	834±63
17	1076±95	1663±230 *	1179±100	1487±167	977±64	974±119
18	1193±166	1674±253 *	1303±162	1486±107	1122±81	1027±125
19	1155±123	1763±229 *	1056±83	922±108	1004±78	841±130
20	1053±113	1755±218 *	1174±104	976±106	971±81	968±138
21	991±72	1877±268	989±90	1194±389	931±54	1016±142
22	1121±115	2299±407	940±89		946±113	1167±205
23	1013±98	1881±263	923±81		1068±66	964±138
24	828±79	2599±341	913±70		985±85	990±207
25	832±85	1914±354	1159±159		1066±77	1121±140
26	848±130	996±174	1448±199		1091±90	974±125
27		1282±165	1061±98		1176±170	2256±1685
28		1198±196	1061±111		1212±125	1193±258
29		1221±129	991±86		1240±153	
30			841±125		1465±78	

* – statistically significant compared to the indicator on day 1.

" – statistically significant compared to the indicator in Group 1.

Fig. 1. Mesor of total peripheral resistance circadian rhythm in Group 1, dyn*s*cm^{-5}

Fig. 2. Mesor of total peripheral resistance circadian rhythm in Group 2, dyn*s*cm^{-5}

Fig. 3. Total Peripheral Resistance circadian rhythm. dyn*sec*cm^{-5}

Fig. 4. Total Peripheral Resistance circadian rhythm at 10 s. dyn*sec*cm^{-5}

Fig. 5. Total Peripheral Resistance circadian rhythm in 3 subgroups at 10 s. dyn*sec*cm^{-5}

Fluctuations of the Mesor of total peripheral resistance circadian rhythm in the three subgroups of the first group of children ranged between 1000 and 1300 (Fig. 1), whereas in the second group, the level of total peripheral resistance changes in the third subgroup remained within normal limits. This is associated with a more

radical stress-protective therapy administered after combined cranial and extracranial surgeries, aimed at blocking mechanisms of secondary organ and tissue damage — primarily of the brain — in the most severe patients (Fig. 2).

Some differences were observed during the first 10 days post-injury. In children from subgroup 1 of group 1, the Total Peripheral Resistance circadian rhythm fluctuated within normative ranges (Fig. 3), whereas in group 2, the amplitude of peripheral resistance fluctuations increased by 27% ($p < 0.05$) over 10 days and by 45% ($p < 0.05$) over 29 days (Fig. 6). In subgroup 2, the difference amounted to 43% ($p < 0.05$). In subgroup 3, no differences between the indicators in groups 1 and 2 were identified (Fig. 5, 8).

Fig. 6. Total Peripheral Resistance circadian rhythm in subgroup 1 in the ICU.

Fig. 7. Subgroup 2 in the ICU. Fig. 8. Subgroup 3 in the ICU. $\text{dyn} \cdot \text{s} \cdot \text{cm}^{-5}$

Amplitude dynamics, $\text{dyn} \cdot \text{s} \cdot \text{cm}^{-5}$.

Fig. 9. Amplitude in subgroup 1. $\text{dyn} \cdot \text{s} \cdot \text{cm}^{-5}$.

Fig. 10. Amplitude in subgroup 2. $\text{dyn} \cdot \text{s} \cdot \text{cm}^{-5}$.

Fig. 11. Amplitude in subgroup 3. $\text{dyn} \cdot \text{s} \cdot \text{cm}^{-5}$

In subgroup 1 of children, the amplitude of the Total Peripheral Resistance circadian rhythm in group 1 was $287 \pm 115 \text{ dyn*s*cm}^{-5}$, whereas in group 2 it was nearly three times higher ($685 \pm 302 \text{ dyn*s*cm}^{-5}$), compared to group 1 ($p > 0.05$) (Fig. 9). In subgroup 2, it was $313 \pm 123 \text{ dyn*s*cm}^{-5}$ in group 1 and $491 \pm 185 \text{ dyn*s*cm}^{-5}$ in group 2 ($p > 0.05$). In subgroup 3, the values did not differ significantly, amounting to $266 \pm 111 \text{ dyn*s*cm}^{-5}$ and $426 \pm 168 \text{ dyn*s*cm}^{-5}$ in group 2 ($p > 0.05$).

Table 3. Correlation relationships of the mesor of the circadian rhythm of total peripheral vascular resistance

Parameters	First 10 days						Days 11–30					
	Group 1, Subgroup 1	Group 2, Subgroup 1	Group 1, Subgroup 2	Group 2, Subgroup 2	Group 1, Subgroup 3	Group 2, Subgroup 3	Group 1, Subgroup 1	Group 2, Subgroup 1	Group 1, Subgroup 2	Group 2, Subgroup 2	Group 1, Subgroup 3	Group 2, Subgroup 3
TPR/CO	-0,94	-0,97	-0,89	-0,86	-0,80	-0,86	-0,97	-0,91	-0,93	-0,82	-0,89	-0,60
TPR/SV	-0,88	-0,92	-0,60	-0,81	-0,57	-0,77	-0,90	-0,91	-0,44	-0,64	-0,90	-0,34
TPR/MAP	0,70	0,58	0,29	0,71	0,60	0,52	0,02	-0,33	0,34	0,71	0,82	0,15
TPR/SBP	-0,42	0,53	-0,52	-0,22	-0,28	-0,17	-0,35	-0,52	-0,53	0,70	-0,46	-0,08
TPR/DBP	0,81	0,69	0,63	0,65	0,78	0,66	0,28	-0,18	0,23	0,50	0,90	0,19
TPR/HR	0,74	0,78	0,20	0,69	0,65	0,40	-0,03	-0,51	-0,25	0,80	0,52	0,09
TPR/T	0,59	0,49	0,31	0,14	-0,82	-0,58	0,49	0,24	-0,56	-0,36		

A pronounced inverse strong correlation between cardiac output (CO) and total peripheral resistance (TPR) was observed throughout the entire monitoring period. Similarly, the correlation between stroke volume (SV) and TPR was more prominent during the first 10 days and persisted during days 11 to 30 in Group 1, Subgroups 1 and 3, indicating a predominance of a hyperdynamic hemodynamic response under both conservative and surgical treatment approaches (Table 3). An upward trend in mean arterial pressure (MAP) was directly associated with increases in TPR in Subgroup 1 of Group 1 ($r = 0.7$), Subgroup 2 of Group 2 ($r = 0.71$), and Subgroup 3 of Group 1 ($r = 0.6$) during the first 10 days. Also observed in the 2nd subgroup of the 2nd group (0.71) and in the 3rd subgroup of the 1st group within 30 days after surgery. A concurrent increase in systolic arterial pressure with rising total peripheral vascular resistance was observed during the first 10 days in the 1st subgroup of children in group 1 (0.74) and in group 2 (0.78); throughout the entire observation period in the ICU, a direct correlation between changes in systolic arterial pressure and total peripheral vascular resistance was recorded in the 2nd subgroup of group 2 children (0.8).

Table 4. Comparative assessment of the inversion of the Total Peripheral Resistance circadian rhythm in groups 1 and 2

Groups	9–11 hours	12–22 hours	23–8 hours
Group 1, Subgroup 1, 10 days	0	70% (7)	30% (3)
Group 2, Subgroup 1, 10 days	10% (1)	40% (4)	50% (5)
Group 1, Subgroup 2, 10 days	20% (2)	30% (3)	50% (5)
Group 2, Subgroup 2, 10 days	20% (2)	20% (2)	30% (3)
Group 1, Subgroup 3, 10 days	10% (1)	60% (6)	30% (3)
Group 2, Subgroup 3, 10 days	0	40% (4)	60% (6)
Group 1, Subgroup 1, 26 days	6% (1)	50% (13)	44% (12)
Group 2, Subgroup 1, 29 days	10% (3)	34% (10)	56% (16)
Group 1, Subgroup 2, 30 days	6% (2)	30% (9)	64% (19)
Group 2, Subgroup 2, 21 days	9% (2)	33% (7)	58% (11)
Group 1, Subgroup 3, 30 days	10% (3)	13	40% (12)
Group 2, Subgroup 3, 28 days	7% (2)	46% (13)	47% (13)

The longest inversion of the Total Peripheral Resistance circadian rhythm was detected in Subgroup 2 of Group 1, accounting for 64% of the total duration (30 days) of ICU stay. A slightly shorter inversion of the Total Peripheral Resistance circadian rhythm was observed in Subgroup 3 of Group 2, comprising 60% during the early postoperative period (10 days), in Subgroup 2 of Group 2 (21 days) at 58%, and in Subgroup 1 of Group 2 (29 days) at 56% throughout the ICU stay. Thus, the duration of the circadian rhythm inversion corresponded to the severity of the sustained trauma and was longer in patients who underwent surgical correction (Table 4). Given that the increase in total peripheral vascular resistance (TPR), associated with heightened peripheral vascular tone, spasm, possible rheological changes, and an increased tendency toward hypercoagulation, is accompanied by homeostatic disturbances in the early post-traumatic period, this not only amplifies the sympathotonic response – exacerbating catabolic changes and raising the risk of an acute energy-deficit state – but also impairs reparative and regenerative processes, as well as the overall physiological adaptation of the organism in the post-traumatic period. The findings indicate that targeted intensive therapy should be accompanied by a more effective correction of deviations in the phase characteristic parameters of the Total Peripheral Resistance circadian rhythm, particularly inversion, through the administration of vasodilators and sedatives, while preventing surges of hyper-sympathetic activity during nighttime hours.

Conclusion. Emergency specialized care enabled normalization of the mesor of the Total Peripheral Resistance circadian rhythm within 1 day across all groups and subgroups. The identified strong inverse correlation between cardiac output (CO) and total peripheral vascular resistance (TPVR) throughout the entire

observation period, as well as between stroke output (SO) and TPVR – more pronounced during the first 10 days and persisting from days 11 to 30 in group 1 and subgroups 1 and 3-indicated a predominance of a hyperdynamic hemodynamic pattern with both conservative and surgical treatment methods. The duration of inversion of the Total Peripheral Resistance circadian rhythm corresponded to the severity of the sustained injury and was longer in patients who underwent surgical correction. The level of the Mesor of total peripheral resistance circadian rhythm observed in subgroup 3, which was closest to normative values compared to groups 1 and 2, was due to a more intensive stress-limiting pharmacotherapy.

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COMPARATIVE ASSESSMENT OF THE CIRCADIAN RHYTHM OF MYOCARDIAL OXYGEN DEMAND IN CHILDREN WITH SEVERE COMBINED TRAUMATIC BRAIN INJURY

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Annotation. *In the absence of significant deviations of the mesor CR PMK from physiologically permissible values in both groups, a 6.5% decrease in the mesor CR PMK was noted during the first 10 days in children of group 2. The highest risk of myocardial ischemia in children of subgroup 3 within group 2 was identified on postoperative days 11 to 15. The amplitude index of CR PMK and circadian fluctuations in all subgroups of group 2 were greater than in the corresponding subgroups of group 1. The shift of the acrophase peak of CR PMK to nighttime hours reflected a pathological direction of myocardial metabolism with a predisposition to myocardial ischemia and an increased risk of developing acute heart failure, most significantly in children of subgroup 3 in group 2. The observed data confirm the rationale for conducting preventive interventions aimed at the prophylaxis of acute mitochondrial myocardial insufficiency in SCTBI in children.*

Keywords: *circadian rhythm, myocardial oxygen demand, severe combined traumatic brain injury, children.*

Significance. Extracranial complications in severe combined traumatic brain injury (SCTBI) typically occur at the time of injury, progressing or, conversely, subsiding during the patient's stay in the intensive care unit. These complications can influence both mortality and neurological outcomes in patients with SCTBI. Among these extracranial complications, cardiac injury is a relatively common occurrence, affecting approximately 25–35% of patients with TBI. One of the initial protective responses of the body to trauma is the hemodynamic stress reaction, manifested by the development of a more physiologically appropriate hyperdynamic circulation type. In more severe, complicated injuries, we have previously observed the

emergence of a hypodynamic hemodynamic pattern. The pathophysiology underlying cardiac injury in TBI involves a complex interaction between the brain and the heart. Acute cerebral injury triggers a systemic inflammatory response and a catecholamine surge, leading to the release of neurotransmitters and cytokines that worsen brain damage and cellular dysfunction. Heart damage after TBI is a relatively common complication with a complex pathophysiology that can contribute to the high mortality rate among patients. Heart injuries such as regional wall motion abnormalities, elevated troponin levels, myocardial stunning, or Takotsubo cardiomyopathy (a non-ischemic cardiomyopathy typically affecting the apex of the left ventricle) have been described [1–5]. Due to the lack of sufficient data, we sought to investigate changes in the structure of the phase characteristic and to provide a comparative assessment of the circadian rhythm response of PMK to severe combined traumatic brain injury during various stages of intensive comprehensive conservative therapy and early surgical correction of traumatic injuries.

Objective of the study. To study and provide a comparative assessment of changes in the circadian rhythm of myocardial oxygen demand in children with severe combined traumatic brain injury.

Materials and methods. Thirty-six children (group 1) hospitalized at the RNCMPM from 2016 to 2021 and 35 children (group 2) hospitalized from 2023 to 2024 for severe combined TBI were admitted following road traffic accidents (30 cases) and falls from height (5 cases). Each patient group was subdivided and studied in three subgroups. Traumatized patients in group 1 were studied in randomized subgroups: subgroup 1 (n=13) received conservative therapy according to indications; subgroup 2 (n=14) underwent extracranial corrective surgeries as indicated; and 9 patients in subgroup 3 underwent both cranial and extracranial surgical interventions based on clinical indications. Patients in group 2 were distributed as follows: 13 children without surgery in subgroup 1; 14 patients underwent extracranial surgeries; and within the first hours of admission, 8 children received cranial and extracranial surgeries involving a neurosurgeon, abdominal surgeon, and traumatologist, as clinically indicated. No significant age differences were found between the groups. Monitoring was performed by comprehensive hourly recording of body temperature, hemodynamic, and respiratory parameters. Mechanical respiratory support was initiated with mechanical ventilation (MV) for a short period, followed by a transition to SIMV. As the patient's condition improved, with stabilization of hemodynamics and respiration, and restoration of reflexes and consciousness, patients were transferred to specialized units.

Results and Discussion. In the absence of significant deviations of the mesor CR PMK from physiologically permissible values in both groups, a significant decrease in the mesor CR PMK was found only in subgroup 2 during the first 10 days in children of group 2 by 6.5% ($p<0.05$).

Table 1. Mean values of the phase structure of the circadian rhythm of PMK in SCTBI, %.

Groups	Mesor	At acrophase	At bathyphase	Amplitude	Daily range
Group 1 Subgroup 1, 10 days	109±5	123±6	97±3	15±4	26±6
Group 2 Subgroup 1, 10 days	111±6	122±7	102±8	11±3	20±5
Group 1 Subgroup 2, 10 days	122±4	134±4	109±6	12±2	25±5
Group 2 Subgroup 2, 10 days	114±3*	127±7	100±6	13±4	27±8
Group 1 Subgroup 3, 10 days	127±7	143±9	116±7	15±4	27±5
Group 2 Subgroup 3, 10 days	113±7	137±13	94±9*	24±11	43±18
Group 1 Subgroup 1, 26 days	112±6	128±9	99±6	15±3	29±3
Group 2 Subgroup 1, 29 days	114±6	132±11	96±7	19±5	132±11*
Group 1 Subgroup 2, 30 days	120±6	133±6	106±7	13±3	27±6
Group 2 Subgroup 2, 21 days	112±5	129±8	97±7	17±6	32±10
Group 1 Subgroup 3, 30 days	124±7	140±9	110±7	16±4	30±7
Group 2 Subgroup 3, 28 days	122±19	158±27	93±17	36±15	66±25*

* – difference significant compared to the value in Group 1

A downward trend in the studied parameter was observed in Subgroup 3 over 10 days by 11 % ($p>0.05$) and in Subgroup 2 of Group 2 by 6 % ($p>0.05$) during treatment in the ICU (Table 1). No differences in the PMK parameter at acrophase between groups were detected. Only in subgroup 3 during the first 10 days was a significant decrease in PMK during the bathyphase by 18 % observed ($p<0.05$).

Daily fluctuations of PMK significantly increased by 355% and 120% in subgroups 1 and 3 of group 2, respectively ($p<0.05$). Thus, within the first 10 days, a decrease in the mesor CR PMK was observed in subgroup 2, and a decrease in the PMK indicator during the bathyphase was observed in subgroup 3 of group 2, which can be interpreted as favorable preventive effects and an optimization of intensive care therapy in subgroups 2 and 3 of group 2. An increase in daily fluctuations of PMK during the later period (days 11–30) indicates increased vulnerability of cellular metabolism, with a high risk of acute mitochondrial insufficiency in subgroups 1 and 3 of group 2, substantiating the rationale for supportive, preventive pharmacological intervention aimed at myocardial ischemia prevention. The use of beta-blockers remains controversial due to their side effect profile, age-related heightened sensitivity, and the insufficiently studied characteristics of adrenoceptors to all ‘blocker’ drugs of the sympathoadrenal system in pediatric patients.

No significant deviations of the mesor CR PMK from physiological norms were detected during the first 24 hours. Over time, a significant decrease in the mesor CR PMK was observed on days 6 and 13 by 11% and 14% ($p < 0.05$, respectively) in the first subgroup of the first group (Table 2). In the second subgroup of the first group, a statistically significant decrease in the mesor CR PMK was found only on days 17 and 18 by 17% and 13% ($p < 0.05$, respectively). In the 3rd subgroup of Group 1, a decrease in mesor CR PMK was observed on days 6, 7, and 9 by 9%, 8%, with an increase in mesor CR PMK on day 9 by 16% ($p < 0.05$, respectively).

In subgroup 1 of group 2, a decrease in mesor CR PMK was observed as early as days 5 and 9 (in group 1 on days 6 and 13) by 4% and 16%, respectively ($p < 0.05$). The more severe condition in subgroup 2 of group 1 was characterized by higher mesor CR PMK values on days 2 through 8, increasing by 16%, 14%, 10%, 18%, 16%, and 10%, respectively ($p < 0.05$). The most traumatic period for the myocardium was postoperative days 2 to 8 following extracranial surgeries (Table 2).

Table 2. Comparative assessment of the dynamics of mesor CR PMK

Days	Group 1, 1st subgroup	Group 2, 1st subgroup	Group 1, 2nd subgroup	Group 2, 2nd subgroup	Group 1, 3rd subgroup	Group 2, 3rd subgroup
1	115 ± 8	120 ± 12	124 ± 8	113 ± 7	127 ± 6	104 ± 10 ^{'''}
2	110 ± 4	113 ± 4	128 ± 5 [°]	112 ± 4 ^{'''}	132 ± 4 [°]	113 ± 6 ^{'''}
3	113 ± 6	117 ± 3	128 ± 5 [°]	112 ± 4 ^{'''}	131 ± 6 [°]	107 ± 4 [^]
4	111 ± 6	119 ± 3	123 ± 5 [°]	113 ± 2 ^{'''}	127 ± 7 [°]	121 ± 6
5	102 ± 7	115 ± 4 ^{'''}	121 ± 6 [°]	108 ± 4 ^{'''}	116 ± 6 [°]	118 ± 3 [*]
6	102 ± 3 [*]	105 ± 4	119 ± 5 [°]	107 ± 6 ^{'''}	115 ± 3 [*]	112 ± 11
7	104 ± 4	111 ± 3	121 ± 4 [°]	115 ± 5	116 ± 4 [*]	99 ± 5 ^{'''}
8	105 ± 5	104 ± 4	126 ± 3 [°]	122 ± 7	128 ± 7	107 ± 11 ^{'''}
9	109 ± 4	100 ± 5 [*]	112 ± 4	117 ± 6 [^]	147 ± 6 [*]	120 ± 13 ^{'''}
10	118 ± 5	103 ± 5 ^{'''}	115 ± 7	118 ± 11	137 ± 8 [°]	129 ± 20
11	112 ± 5	114 ± 5	122 ± 5	110 ± 7	124 ± 6 [°]	137 ± 16 [^]
12	115 ± 3	117 ± 10	116 ± 5	130 ± 9	131 ± 6 [°]	138 ± 8 [^]
13	98 ± 5 [*]	114 ± 6	110 ± 6	117 ± 15	126 ± 5 [°]	164 ± 16 ^{''' ^}
14	113 ± 5	119 ± 12	113 ± 6	111 ± 7	116 ± 5	170 ± 12 ^{''' ^}
15	106 ± 6	112 ± 9	115 ± 4	110 ± 5	128 ± 5	170 ± 12 ^{''' ^}
16	108 ± 6	100 ± 12	115 ± 3	109 ± 8	134 ± 7	154 ± 8 ^{''' ^}
17	117 ± 5	119 ± 9	102 ± 6 [*]	104 ± 7	126 ± 6	115 ± 11
18	105 ± 11	123 ± 9	108 ± 5 [*]	111 ± 4	116 ± 5	117 ± 8
19	115 ± 6	106 ± 8	134 ± 4	113 ± 6	113 ± 6	115 ± 25
20	112 ± 5	105 ± 8	122 ± 7	98 ± 10	112 ± 7	84 ± 9
21	106 ± 7	114 ± 9	112 ± 7	103 ± 7	126 ± 10	99 ± 13

Days	Group 1, 1st subgroup	Group 2, 1st subgroup	Group 1, 2nd subgroup	Group 2, 2nd subgroup	Group 1, 3rd subgroup	Group 2, 3rd subgroup
22	120± 10	121±10	128± 9		118±13	131±25
23	129 ± 8	112±11	119± 6		116± 4	122±32
24	127 ±10	110±9	122± 4		120± 5	100±21
25	122 ± 6	125±7	117± 8		116± 6	131±32
26	128 ± 6	143±13	114± 8		114±5	92±19
27		113±16	121± 4		137±10	95±16
28		115±12	118± 7		122±10	158±37
29		106±9	125± 5		118± 7	
30			148± 11		123±7	

* – significant difference relative to the value on day 1.

™ – significant compared to the indicator of group 1.

° – significant relative to the indicator in subgroup 1 of group 1.

^ – significant relative to subgroup 1 of group 2.

No statistically significant changes were observed after extracranial surgeries in Group 2. In the postoperative period, subgroup 3 of Group 2 exhibited a statistically significant 13% increase in PMK on day 5 ($p < 0.05$). Comparative analysis of the effect of injury severity on myocardial metabolism revealed certain differences in Group 2. In children of subgroup 2 compared to subgroup 1, PMK was higher by 17% on day 9 ($p < 0.05$, respectively). In subgroup 3 of group 2, although PMK decreased by 8% on day 3, significantly higher PMK values were recorded on days 11–16, with increases of 20%, 17%, 43%, 42%, 51%, and 54% ($p < 0.05$, respectively). The highest risk of myocardial ischemia in children of subgroup 3 of group 2 was observed during days 11–15 of the postoperative period. In group 1, the comparative analysis of injury severity revealed a stress response in myocardial metabolism characterized by a significant increase in PMK, more pronounced in subgroup 2 at 16:00, 18:00, 19:00, 22:00, 23:00, 05:00, and 06:00 hours. A more severe condition in children who underwent combined cranial and extracranial surgical operations in subgroup 3 of group 1 was associated with a significant increase in PMK at 08:00, 09:00, 11:00, 16:00, 17:00, 18:00, from 19:00 to 24:00, and at 02:00 hours, on average by 20–25% ($p < 0.05$, respectively). That is, this group of patients required continuous metabolic support using preventive measures against acute mitochondrial insufficiency (Table 3). In the second group, among the three injured subgroups, no significant differences in PMK values were observed during the first 10 days compared to the indicators in the first subgroup. The latter is apparently due to the more extensive stress-protective therapy administered, including therapeutic anesthesia, anticonvulsants, and muscle relaxants.

Table 3. Comparative analysis of CR PMK during the first 10 days of traumatic disease

Hours	Group 1 Subgroup 1	Group 2 Subgroup 1	Group 1 Subgroup 2	Group 2 Subgroup 2	Group 1 Subgroup 3	Group 2 Subgroup 3
8	116±7	111±5	127±4	117±6	134±7*	122±17
9	113±8	112±6	125±4	117±6	134±8*	121±12
10	116±8	109±8	125±5	115±4	130±10	122±13
11	112±8	111±7	124±6	117±6	130±6*	120±13
12	111±6	112±6	124±8	114±7	128±7	114±12
13	113±7	111±5	124±5	112±9	126±8	114±10
14	111±5	113±9	120±8	113±8	128±11	111±9
15	107±7	111±10	121±7	113±6	125±10	111±10
16	106±8	110±7	123±8*	114±4	125±9*	113±12
17	106±5	108±7	124±4	113±4	128±12*	116±11
18	109±5	112±6	123±5*	113±4	133±9*	111±8
19	110±5	113±6	122±6*	115±6	129±9*	111±10
20	107±6	110±6	120±7	115±8	129±9*	118±12
21	106±7	112±8	122±7	114±5	129±9*	118±12
22	103±6	108±7	123±6*	112±8	125±11*	114±14
23	105±5	108±6	122±6*	111±6	126±8*	114±15
24	106±6	111±4	119±7	111±7	125±10*	114±13
1	106±8	108±6	117±7	111±7	123±10	113±10
2	105±7	109±6	117±6	112±6	125±10*	104±9
3	108±7	108±8	117±7	114±7	124±11	112±12
4	108±6	109±10	118±7	114±5	125±11	106±8
5	106±5	110±9	118±4*	114±7	125±10	107±11
6	108±6	110±8	122±5*	116±9	127±12	105±10
7	111±7	112±8	120±5	115±7	127±11	109±6

* – significantly different compared to the indicator in subgroup 1 of group 1.

The comparative analysis of CR PMK parameters during days 11 to 30 showed no significant differences, which was attributed to a larger variability of values within the groups.

Wave-like fluctuations in the amplitude of CR PMK during conservative therapy were notable, with peak values occurring in subgroup 1 of group 1 on days 5, 23, and 24, and in group 2 on days 1, 14, 16, 17, and 26 (Fig. 1). Following extracranial surgeries in group 2, the amplitude of CR PMK exceeded 20% between days 10 and 19, whereas this upward trend was observed in group 1 only after day 25 (Fig. 2).

Fig. 1. Amplitude of CR PMK in subgroup 1.
 Fig. 2. Amplitude of CR PMK in subgroup 2.
 Fig. 3. Amplitude of CR PMK in subgroup 3.

The most pronounced fluctuations in the amplitude of CR PMK were observed in the most severe patients of subgroup 3, with values exceeding 30% between days 7 and 11, rising to 70% after day 22 (Fig. 3). These daily fluctuations exceeding 30% indicate a highly unfavorable state of myocardial trophic condition as early as 7 days post-operation in children of subgroup 3. Therefore, it is considered appropriate to supplement pharmacological correction in the 3rd subgroup of children with metabolic and cardiotropic therapy, as well as with myocardial ischemia correction, beginning within the first 10 days of the postoperative period.

Circadian fluctuations in all subgroups of the 2nd group were greater than those observed in the corresponding subgroups of the 1st group. Conservative treatment in children in group 2 was accompanied by an increase in daily amplitude fluctuations of the parameter up to 67% on day 16, and up to 80% on day 26 (Fig. 4). Extracranial surgeries in group 2 caused an increase in daily amplitude fluctuations of PMK up to 73% on day 13 (Fig. 5). Following combined cranial and extracranial surgical interventions, daily fluctuations increased to 86% on day 10 and up to 170% on day 28 (Fig. 6). The myocardium in children in group 2 was in the most unfavorable condition, significantly increasing the risk of myocardial ischemia and acute heart failure.

Fig. 4. Circadian fluctuations in the 1st subgroup, %
 Fig. 5. Circadian fluctuations in the 2nd subgroup, %
 Fig. 6. Circadian fluctuations in the 3rd subgroup, %.

Table 5. Correlation relationships of PMK.

Indicators	10 days						11–30 days					
	Group 1 Subgroup 1	Group 2 1 subgroup	Group 1 2 subgroup	2 group Subgroup 2	Group 1 3 subgroup	Group 2 3 subgroup	Group 1 Subgroup 1	Group 2 Subgroup 1	Group 1 Subgroup 2	Group 2 Subgroup 2	Group 1 3 subgroup	Group 2 3 subgroup
PMK/MVO2	0,92	0,75	0,71	0,02	0,45	0,21	0,77	0,53	0,75	0,03	0,31	0,80
PMK/SV	0,79	0,60	0,29	-0,06	-0,28	0,00	0,55	0,10	0,12	-0,27	0,01	-0,24
PMK/TPR	-0,84	-0,70	-0,67	0,20	0,00	-0,02	-0,76	-0,38	-0,59	0,44	0,04	-0,25
PMK/MAP	-0,26	0,03	-0,30	0,09	0,79	0,45	0,46	0,40	0,37	0,82	0,58	0,88
PMK/DBP	0,62	-0,40	0,71	0,77	0,25	0,44	0,33	0,23	0,60	0,46	0,56	0,85
PMK/ABP	-0,47	-0,11	-0,54	-0,06	0,57	0,54	-0,03	0,30	0,35	0,64	0,42	0,84
PMK/SBP	-0,49	-0,17	-0,45	0,31	0,41	0,61	0,14	0,44	-0,41	0,77	0,32	0,90
PMK/T	-0,61	-0,32	-0,09	0,55	0,63	0,64	-0,27	-0,24	0,59	0,40	0,30	0,50

Out of 72 studied correlations in group 1, 12 were statistically significant, accounting for 16.6%. During the first 10 days, the significance of correlations was 6 out of 24 (25%); during days 11 to 30, 3 out of 24 (16%); and overall, throughout the ICU treatment period, 3 significant correlations out of 24 were identified, representing 12%. During the first 10 days, the increase in PMK was directly dependent on MVO2 parameters in subgroups 1 and 2, on cardiac

output parameters in subgroup 1, and on the MAP level in subgroup 3. While the decrease in systemic vascular resistance was accompanied by an increase in PMK in subgroup 1, this indicates an adverse effect on the myocardial metabolic state associated with the developing hyperdynamic circulation type during conservative treatment of SCTBI in children. To reduce PMK in subgroup 1, it is advisable to limit vasodilatory hemodynamic correction. Out of 72 correlation relationships in group 2, 12 were statistically significant, representing 16.6%. During the first 10 days out of 24, statistical significance was identified in 2 cases (8%), whereas between days 11 and 30, significance was observed in 6 cases (25%). Throughout the entire ICU treatment period, 3 out of 24 correlation relationships were significant (16%). Notably, in the second group, a significant direct correlation of PMK with diastolic arterial pressure (0.77) emerged, as well as with MVO₂ in the third subgroup (0.79) during days 11–30 in the ICU. Unlike the first group, a strong direct dependence was found in the third subgroup between PMK dynamics and mean arterial pressure (0.81), diastolic arterial pressure (0.8), and systolic arterial pressure (0.85) throughout treatment during days 11–30 and across the entire ICU stay. This observed distinction indicates activation of compensatory mechanisms in the circulatory system, concurrent with increases in PMK and, accordingly, a heightened risk of myocardial hypoxia, acute energy-deficient states, and elevated risk of acute heart failure development in children of the second group. These findings support the rationale for implementing preventive therapeutic interventions. targeting the prevention of acute mitochondrial failure in SCTBI in children.

Table 6. Comparative assessment of the duration of CR PMK inversion

Acrophase projection	9–11 hours		12–22 hours		23–8 hours	
Subgroups	1		2		3	
Monitoring	Group 1	Group 2	Group 1	Group 2	Group 1	Group 2
10 days	50%	20%	10%	60%	40%	20%
	20%	10%	40%	50%	40%	40%
	30%	30%	40%	20%	30%	50%
21–30 days	7%	27%	21%	54%	11%	19%
	17%	9%	50%	54%	33%	37%
	23%	17%	54%	49%	23%	34%

Maximum cellular metabolic activity under physiological conditions is reflected by an increase in PMK during the morning hours of the circadian rhythm. However, the longest inversion of the circadian rhythm of the PMK was detected during the first 10 days in the 3rd subgroup of the 2nd group, reaching 50%,

which is 20% higher than the value observed in the 1st group. The longest inversion of the circadian rhythm of the PMK throughout intensive therapy under ICU conditions was observed in children of the 3rd subgroup of the 2nd group (37%), exceeding the respective indicator in the 1st group by 4% (Table 6). The shift of the acrophase peak of the circadian rhythm of the PMK to nighttime hours indicates a pathological myocardial metabolic orientation with a propensity toward myocardial ischemia and increased risk of acute heart failure development, most prominently in children of the 3rd subgroup, somewhat more pronounced in the 2nd group. The findings indicate the advisability of extending stress-limiting correction into the nighttime hours. Considering the inertial nature of the metabolic response, a preventive approach to secondary damage of the CNS and other systems may be more effective when initiated from the first days of comprehensive intensive therapy in severe combined TBI. Given the age-related predisposition to rapid depletion of energy resources in children, supportive early intervention (from the first hours post-injury) against acute mitochondrial insufficiency and energy-deficit conditions at the cellular, tissue, and organ levels is necessary, in conjunction with effective stress-protective correction. The success of this approach will be manifested by the blockade of pathogenetic mechanisms underlying the development of multiple organ failure, as well as by the enhancement of regenerative and reparative processes in the pediatric organism damaged by severe trauma.

Conclusion. In the absence of significant deviations in the mesor CR PMK from physiologically permissible values in both groups, a 6.5% decrease in the mesor CR PMK was observed during the first 10 days in children of group 2. The highest risk of myocardial ischemia in children of subgroup 3 within group 2 was identified on postoperative days 11 to 15. In group 1, a comparative analysis of the severity of injury revealed a stress reaction in myocardial metabolism evidenced by an increase in PMK, which was more pronounced in subgroup 2. The amplitude index of CR PMK and circadian fluctuations in all subgroups of group 2 were greater than in the corresponding subgroups of group 1. The shift of the peak acrophase of CR PMK toward nighttime hours characterized a pathological tendency of myocardial metabolism toward myocardial ischemia and an increased risk of the development of acute heart failure, most pronounced in children of subgroup 3 and somewhat more significant in group 2. The observed data confirm the rationale for conducting preventive interventions aimed at the prophylaxis of acute mitochondrial myocardial insufficiency in SCTBI in children.

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PREVENTIVE MEASURES FOR HYGIENIC CARE OF REMOVABLE DENTURES

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Abstract. *The human oral cavity constitutes a unique ecological system for microorganisms that form a stable microflora. The abundance of nutritional substrates, constant moisture, optimal pH values, and temperature create favorable conditions for adhesion, colonization, and proliferation of various microbial species. The problem of oral hygiene becomes particularly challenging in the presence of removable prosthodontic constructions. This article is devoted to the prevention of complications in patients using dental prostheses with bases made from thermoplastic materials. Given the global challenges in dental health among the elderly, insufficient knowledge regarding hygiene agents, and the specific requirements of oral cavity and removable denture care, the level of oral hygiene is rarely satisfactory. A comprehensive approach aimed at enhancing the hygiene index of removable dentures has been proposed, encompassing oral hygiene maintenance, application of mechanical cleaning methods, rinsing solutions, and disinfectants.*

Keywords: *removable dental prosthesis constructions, thermoplastic polymer materials, oral hygiene, disinfection of removable dentures.*

In dentistry, clinicians' interest in the use of thermoplastic materials has been steadily increasing due to the availability of accessible information, the development of well-designed and comprehensive technologies employing the necessary

equipment, and, most importantly, the favorable properties of these materials alongside specialists' objective to achieve the best possible outcomes for improving the standard of prosthetic care. Base plastics based on nylon currently rank among the most commonly used thermoplastic polymers in the orthopedic dentistry clinic. One of the pertinent challenges in the application of dental prostheses fabricated from this type of polymer is the relative complexity of surface treatment and ensuring the sustained maintenance of adequate hygiene and long-term functioning of removable thermoplastic prostheses. This is associated with the technological properties and structure of polyamide materials, which undergo thermal degradation; in dentistry, the term 'nylon' is employed. At the final stage of fabrication of removable orthopedic constructions with bases made from thermoplastic polymers, due to the occurrence of deformation and the complexity of processing the base surfaces, it is necessary to follow a well-defined polishing protocol to ensure a successful outcome of the procedure [1].

This factor directly influences the 'denture cleanliness index,' the hygienic status of the oral cavity, and the overall dental health level of patients utilizing removable dental prostheses – predominantly elderly individuals who exhibit a range of distinctive features characteristic of this population group. Key issues characteristic of this age group include concomitant somatic pathology and a decrease in the adaptive reserves of the aging organism; the presence of multiple dental pathologies and a high complexity level of dentoalveolar system disorders; a low level of oral hygiene and lack of specialized knowledge regarding hygienic measures and care products for removable prosthetic constructions, as well as peculiarities of psychological development and limited financial capabilities [7].

To ensure the long-term functionality of the dentofacial system utilizing removable dental prostheses fabricated from thermoplastic polymers, it is essential to conduct educational interventions on preventive and hygienic measures during the clinical stages of prosthesis fabrication [6]. During an individualized consultation with the patient at the stage of fitting a removable dental prosthesis, the dentist must possess adequate authority and convincingly inform the patient that, despite the entire spectrum of positive properties of removable dental prostheses made from thermoplastic polymers, the presence of contamination, deposits, and surface roughness can lead to inflammatory and traumatic processes affecting the tissues of the prosthetic bed. The presence of microorganisms on dentures can induce sensitization and alter the body's immunological reactivity, which typically leads to autoinfection and impairment of the oral mucosa function. Therefore, it is essential to address the issue of 'maintaining denture cleanliness' with due responsibility, aiming exclusively at positive outcomes [8].

Taking into account the financial aspect of 'maintaining denture cleanliness,' the most widespread and cost-effective approach remains the treatment of removable

dental prostheses to eliminate microorganisms colonizing the denture base fabricated from thermoplastic polymer, through the application of specialized disinfectants [5].

The dental market offers a wide range of products for the maintenance of dental prostheses. Modern products for cleaning and disinfecting removable dentures vary in composition and dosage form; however, not all disinfectants available on the dental market comply with the current standards required for disinfectants for removable dentures fabricated from thermoplastic materials, nor are they convenient for patient use. In particular, modern disinfectants for removable dentures must have low toxicity; antimicrobial activity at low concentrations; a broad spectrum of activity; no adverse effects on the treated objects, considering the technological characteristics of the materials used; with stability during storage. Moreover, imported drugs are expensive, which limits their accessibility; however, according to the instructions, they have beneficial properties for broad application. On the other hand, there is no confirmed evidence supporting their use for the safe disinfection treatment of removable orthopedic devices with bases made from thermoplastic materials [3].

Consequently, the issue of import replacement remains relevant at present, alongside the search for economically viable and high-quality domestic disinfectants for removable dental prostheses fabricated from thermoplastic materials that comply with contemporary quality standards [2].

Research has confirmed that to achieve optimal cleaning and disinfecting efficacy of agents for removable thermoplastic prostheses, it is essential to utilize an optimal combination of active components within the disinfectant formulation. In recent times, significant attention has been devoted to the utilization of silver ions as a component of disinfecting solutions for oral cavity hygiene and removable dentures. The foregoing underscores the urgency of research focused on the development of a ready-to-use disinfecting solution containing silver ions for the maintenance of hygiene in removable dentures with bases fabricated from thermoplastic polymers [4].

The determination of the composition and investigation of the properties of a novel solution for the disinfection and cleaning of removable dentures fabricated from thermoplastic polymers were performed under the auspices of LLC 'Celit' (Voronezh). The analysis of the literature allowed for the identification of the component composition for the development and evaluation of a disinfectant and cleansing solution required for the treatment of removable thermoplastic dentures. Silver ions represent one of the most potent natural antiseptics. Silver ions demonstrate a broad spectrum of antimicrobial activity against aerobic and anaerobic microflora, including antibiotic-resistant strains; and exhibit antifungal and antiviral properties; They exert an anti-inflammatory effect. Aluminum potassium alum – a double salt of aluminum sulfate and potassium sulfate – is noteworthy from this standpoint due to its pronounced astringent and anti-inflammatory properties. It alleviates pain,

burning, and itching associated with stomatitis and gingivitis, possesses cauterizing, hemostatic, astringent, and disinfectant effects, and remains relatively safe for the human organism [6].

The new disinfectant solution demonstrates the most optimal cleansing and antimicrobial properties, combined with absolute safety for the bases of removable dentures fabricated from thermoplastic materials, when utilized with active components such as 20% silver aqueous solution, Desin (10–15%), and aluminum potassium alum (1–2%). The data obtained from the investigation of active components in the composition of the new domestic disinfectant solution for cleaning and disinfecting removable dentures necessitate further investigation to assess its hygienic efficacy in a comparative context in accordance with the objectives of the scientific study. Undoubtedly, the application of new technologies, developed materials, and agents requires verification over time, and only active clinical practice and the commitment of specialists to achieve the optimal result can enhance the quality of orthopedic care and satisfy demanding patients [3].

Thus, upon completion of orthopedic treatment, the physician must necessarily provide the patient with recommendations concerning the specific aspects of hygienic care for the oral cavity and the fabricated dental prosthetic constructions. It is important to emphasize that hygienic care and disinfection of removable dental prostheses fabricated from thermoplastic materials constitute a critical element in the prevention of mucosal membrane diseases and the development of numerous complications.

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INTRODUCTION OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES INTO THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS OF TRAINING SURGICAL PERSONNEL

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Abstract. Digital education is an integrated educational model based on the use of digital technologies and electronic resources to improve the efficiency and personalization of the learning process. The authors have developed and tested a virtual model program: an Interactive educational VR-complex for training in the performance of laparoscopic pancreaticoduodenal resection. The article outlines the advantages and benefits of training surgeons using this VR complex, which provides opportunities for hyflex learning.

Keywords: *phygital technologies, virtual reality, surgeon training, digital education.*

Relevance. It is indisputable that the era of digital socialization necessitates profound restructuring and reorganization of the educational process, including radical changes in the roles of both the trainee and the instructor, as well as in their

methodological and methodical thinking. Simultaneously, the essence of digital education lies in the transformation of the educational process through technologies to create a more flexible, accessible, and personalized learning system. It is not a replacement of traditional education, but its evolution, taking into account the requirements of the digital environment and the changing needs of students.

Digital education is an integrated educational model based on the use of digital technologies and electronic resources to improve the efficiency and personalization of the learning process [1–3]. Among the components of digital education, virtual and augmented reality technologies (VR/AR) hold particular importance.

Thanks to augmented (AR) and virtual (VR) reality technologies, the educational process acquires an additional dimension. This represents a breakthrough in the domain of data visualization. However, the application of these technologies is not limited to mere visualization. These technologies enable not only observation but also active engagement. For example, conducting experiments or refining skills.

The aim of the study was to develop a full virtual reality model for training in surgical procedures and refining existing skills.

Materials and Methods. For the development of the virtual reality model of the procedure, laparoscopic pancreaticoduodenal resection was selected. Programming languages C++ and Blueprints were utilized. The simulation scenario was developed and verified for compliance with medical standards; coding and user interface development were performed.

Results. Pancreatic surgery, due to its technical complexity and the high variability of anatomical conditions, has long been one of the most responsive areas to the introduction of digital technologies. Experience accumulated to date demonstrates that VR and AR systems have the potential to transform both the surgical training phase and preoperative planning, thereby creating fundamentally new conditions for enhancing the precision of interventions.

We have developed a virtual model program entitled the Interactive educational VR-complex for training in performing laparoscopic pancreaticoduodenal resection. Certificate of the Federal Service for Intellectual Property on the State Registration of Computer Program No. 2024689341 dated 5.12.2024 has been received.

Testing of the program demonstrated that one of the key advantages of virtual reality is the ability to create a fully controllable and consistently reproducible environment for practicing surgeries, including pancreaticoduodenal resection. These simulators generate realistic three-dimensional organ models, replicate their mechanical properties, and enable the surgeon to safely undergo all stages of the procedure repeatedly. Unlike traditional training based on the interpretation of two-dimensional images, VR provides a volumetric representation of tissue topography, enhances spatial cognition, and enables the advance identification of critical areas in the forthcoming surgical procedure (Laga Boul-Atarass I., 2025)

Fig. 1 Educational VR simulators in medical education

.VR assumes a particularly important role in minimally invasive surgery, where comprehensive tactile feedback is absent. Virtual laparoscopic simulators facilitate the development of ‘visual tactility’ – the ability to evaluate tissue resistance and deformation dynamics solely by visual indicators. This significantly reduces the learning curve and enhances surgeons’ confidence in performing delicate stages of the operation, especially those requiring precise dissection within a confined space.

Furthermore, the simulator’s functionality was adapted for use with gloves incorporating force-feedback haptic technology, which resulted in considerable improvements in movement tracking accuracy and enabled the perception of the shape of objects held in the hands. This technology had not previously been applied in surgical simulations and was first tested by us on the SURVREYLINE simulator. The gloves were also developed by the scientific team of LLC ‘X Red Group,’ which included the author of this study, and have no domestic analogues.

The economic impact of implementing the developed product consists in a substantial reduction of costs associated with equipment for simulating surgical interventions. The simulator enables the performance of a diverse range of different types of operations at a single training workstation, which would be impossible to organize using traditional training methods or simulators, as the latter are acquired separately for each specific type of surgical intervention. Thus, the program addresses several tasks simultaneously for the optimal organization of the

educational process: conserving training space and reducing equipment procurement costs, as well as enabling young specialists to practice surgical skills without posing risks to patients.

Fig. 2 External appearance of gloves with force-based tactile feedback

Conclusions. Therefore, phygital technologies are being actively integrated into surgical practice. VR complexes establish a new paradigm in surgical training and planning by combining individualized anatomical modeling, interactive educational environments, and navigation tools. The implementation of these technologies facilitates the reduction of the learning curve, minimizes the risk of intraoperative errors, and enhances the precision of performing the most complex stages of the surgical procedure. As technologies evolve, further deep integration of virtual systems into clinical practice is anticipated, including the development of digital twins and the application of artificial intelligence components to support decision-making processes.

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CLINICAL, LABORATORY, AND STATISTICAL METHODS OF STUDYING ORAL HYGIENE IN PERIODONTAL DISEASES

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All patients were examined at the Derzhavin Dental Department of Tomsk State University. The following were exclusion criteria:

1. Presence of type I and II diabetes mellitus, allergic and infectious diseases, osteoporosis, and other conditions.

2. Presence of conditions affecting bone resorption and gingival hypertrophy, as well as medication use.

In accordance with the objectives of this research, clinical, clinical laboratory, laboratory, and statistical research methods were used.

Keywords: *clinical laboratory, laboratory and statistical methods for studying oral hygiene in periodontal diseases.*

Analyzing my work for the reporting period, I note positive dynamics.

Fig. 1. red first group, blue second group – oral hygiene indices.

Moreover, if treatment and preventive measures were carried out, then it was determined what means and methods were used, and whether oral hygiene was observed to a sufficient extent. The results are in Table 1.

index	age	Group 1		Group 2	
		3 months.	6 months.	3 months.	6 months.
Hygienic					
ИГР-У по J. C. Green – J. R. Vermillion (1964) (OHI-S)	20–35 years	0,37	0,39	0,46	0,49
	35–45 years	0,42	0,44	0,47	0,51
	45–60 years	0,49	0,51	0,52	0,54

The patient’s examination began with anamnestic data collection, focusing on possible predisposing factors for the development of this periodontal pathology [1].

We considered the duration of the disease, its possible cause, development and progression, heredity, previous treatment, and preventive measures (if any) and their results.

Patients were diagnosed based on their medical history, complaints, clinical symptoms, and additional examination data.

Dental status was taken into account when selecting patients for the study; individuals with significant orthodontic pathology were excluded.

The patients were classified by gender and age, and assigned to groups according to the International Statistical Classification of Human Ages. The results are in Table 2.

Age	Group 1 (control)		Group 2 (control)	
	Men	Women	Men	Women
35–45 years	13 (21,6%)	9 (27,27%)	4 (30,76%)	5 (26,31%)
20–35 years	11 (18,3%)	10 (30,30%)	6 (46,15%)	8 (42,1%)
45–65 years	13 (21,6%)	14 (42,42%)	3 (23,07%)	6 (31,57%)

We also used a questionnaire we developed that assessed the following parameters:

Calculation formula: ИГР-У = ИЗН + ИЗК,

Where ИЗН = the sum of plaque indicators of 6 teeth, 6

ИЗК = the sum of the indicators of the stone of 6 teeth, 6

Interpretation of research results **ИЗН и ИЗК**

Limitation of function (LOF) is a disorder of masticatory function associated with the absence of some or most teeth [1].

For statistical analysis and description of the obtained data, basic methods of variation statistics (arithmetic mean, standard deviation, standard error, etc.),

Student's t-test, as well as correlation, dispersion, and regression methods for studying numerical series were used [3].

The applied indicators were calculated using the formulas below:

1) Arithmetic mean (M):

$$M = \frac{\sum v}{n} ;$$

Where: $\sum v$ – the sum of specific values obtained during the examination of each patient, n – number of observations.

2) The standard deviation (σ) of each indicator from the arithmetic mean (M), showing how closely individual values of the series are grouped in relation to M:

$$\sigma = \frac{\sqrt{\sum (v-M)^2}}{(n-1)} ;$$

Where: v is the variant, the specific value of the indicator for each patient;

M is the arithmetic mean of the indicator for the studied group of patients; n is the number of observations.

If the number of observations is less than or equal to 10, then $(n-1)$ is used to calculate the standard deviation.

The experimental study was conducted at the Department of Dentistry at Tambov State University named after G. R. Derzhavin in 2026.

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LEMIERRE'S SYNDROME: A CLINICAL CASE

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Abstract. *The article presents a clinical case of a 20-year-old young man, M., with a rare complication of odontogenic sinusitis – combined arterial and venous thrombosis resulting in hemispheric stroke. According to the anamnesis, the patient underwent tooth extraction followed by the development of infectious and inflammatory complications. Two weeks after tooth extraction, manifestations of thrombosis of the facial veins appeared. Subsequently, thrombosis progressed into the jugular veins, cavernous sinus, and the arterial circulation. Occlusion of the internal carotid artery (ICA) resulted in the development of a hemispheric stroke. During hospitalization, the patient's condition progressively deteriorated, with the onset of sepsis and multiple organ complications. Despite intensive therapy, the patient died. The clinical and pathological diagnoses were concordant. This clinical observation describes an extremely rare complication of odontogenic sinusitis that may be regarded as an atypical variant of Lemierre's syndrome. A risk factor for increased thrombus formation and systemic dissemination of infection was the presence of type II diabetes mellitus in the patient. The absence of clear clinical criteria and low awareness among treating physicians resulted in difficulties with early diagnosis and selection of the optimal therapeutic protocol for this condition. This underscores the importance of systematic monitoring of patients' condition following dental interventions and, when necessary, the implementation of modern imaging techniques for the vessels of the head and neck.*

Keywords: *venous thrombosis, arterial thrombosis, odontogenic sinusitis, ischemic stroke, multislice computed tomography, magnetic resonance imaging.*

Tooth extraction is one of the most frequently performed dental procedures. However, despite its apparent simplicity, as with any invasive intervention, it is not always possible to prevent the development of complications, including those that are life-threatening. One such complication is the development of an infectious-inflammatory process, its generalization, and septic embolism accompanied by thrombosis. Due to the anatomical characteristics of the blood supply to the maxillofacial region, thrombosis of the veins of the face, brain, and sinuses occurs more frequently. The combination of arterial and venous thrombosis is rare [1]. The literature describes isolated cases of combined arterial and venous thrombosis in patients post-COVID-19, oncology patients, as a complication of Lemierre's syndrome (LS), and so forth [1–5].

Low awareness and clinical suspicion among treating physicians regarding the development of this complication, together with the variety of clinical manifestations at onset, hinder the timely identification of this rare pathology. Therefore, the issues of early diagnosis and effective treatment of combined thromboses remain relevant.

Study Objective

To analyze the examination findings of a patient with combined arterial and venous cerebral thrombosis developed on the background of odontogenic infection.

Clinical Observation

The patient M., 20 years old, presented to the dentist at the central district hospital of his place of residence with complaints of destruction and pain in the region of tooth 16, which had persisted for one year. The diagnosis established by the dentist was: Caries of tooth 16 and chronic periodontitis. Extraction was carried out. Two weeks later, the patient again presented to the medical institution with complaints of pain at the site of the extracted tooth socket, swelling and cyanosis of the right buccal region, sensory disturbance of the right hemiface, and headaches of a diffuse nature. To visualize the sinuses and exclude bone-destructive changes, an MSCT scan of the head was performed. According to the investigation, exudative bilateral maxillary sinusitis and edematous catarrhal polysinusitis were identified.

One week later, a teleconsultation was held, and a decision was made to transfer the patient to the regional clinical hospital, where upon examination by an otolaryngologist and a maxillofacial surgeon, the diagnosis was established: Acute odontogenic exudative bilateral polysinusitis. Complication of the primary disease: Thrombosis of the right facial angular vein. Comorbidities: Type 2 diabetes mellitus without complications.

On the day of hospitalization, puncture, drainage, and lavage of the bilateral maxillary sinuses were performed. Purulent material was obtained during the surgical intervention. The patient was transferred to the intensive care unit for continuous monitoring.

The patient underwent MSCT and MRI of the brain. MSCT revealed thickened and edematous mucosa of the nasal sinuses (Fig. 1 A). Fluid levels were noted in the right maxillary, left frontal, and sphenoid sinuses. No pathological changes were identified in the bones of the calvaria and skull base, brain parenchyma, cerebellum, or brainstem. Additionally, MRI findings (Fig. 1 B) revealed thickening and edema of the right lateral rectus muscle and right optic nerve.

Fig. 1 A

Fig. 1 A – head computed tomography, arrow indicates fluid in the right maxillary sinus;

Fig. 1 B

Fig. 1 B – magnetic resonance imaging; the yellow arrow indicates edema of the optic nerve.

Laboratory testing revealed leukocytosis ($21.00 \times 10^9/L$), neutrophilia ($17.84 \times 10^9/L$ — band neutrophils 7%, segmented neutrophils 78%), lymphopenia ($0.89 \times 10^9/L$), erythrocyte sedimentation rate accelerated to 58 mm/h, elevated blood glucose concentration up to 18.43 mmol/L, and increased amylase activity (255.96 U/L). The ketone level in the urine is elevated to 16.00 mmol/L.

Based on the conducted studies, a decision was made to perform a polysinusotomy procedure using videoendoscopic techniques. The first stage of the surgical intervention included the creation of a rhinostomy, drainage of the frontal sinus, bilateral maxillary sinusotomy, and debridement. The second stage, under endoscopic guidance, involved opening the ethmoid labyrinth cells, enlargement of the natural sinus ostia, removal of hyperplastic mucosa, and placement of drainage in the principal sinus. During the operation, pronounced cyanosis and edema of the mucous membrane of the nasal cavity and right maxillary sinus were observed. At

the time of incision and surgical drainage, bleeding on the right side was absent, which was attributed to thrombosis of the vessels. The soft tissues of the right cheek were cold to the touch and gray in color. Postoperative diagnosis: Acute purulent bilateral maxilloethmoidofrontal sinusitis. Thrombosis of the facial veins with ischemia and necrosis of the soft tissues of the right hemiface (Fig. 2). A collegial decision was made not to excise the necrotic zone, and to continue conservative management.

Pathomorphological examination of the biopsy specimen revealed mucosal tissue; scant growth of *Staphylococcus epidermidis* was identified in the exudate.

Fig. 2. Patient M., 20 years old, photograph following surgical intervention. The arrow indicates the expansion of soft tissue necrosis.

After one week, the patient developed central left hemiparesis with plegia of the arm, accompanied by complaints of decreased visual acuity in the right eye and absence of ocular mobility. The area of necrosis increased and extended to the right nasal wing, buccal, infraorbital, and partially temporal regions. The patient was examined by an ophthalmologist and neurologist, who recommended MSCT angiography of the brachiocephalic vessels and contrast-enhanced computed tomography of the head.

Based on computed tomography data (Fig. 3 A, B, C), the conclusion was: post-operative condition. Destruction of the medial and posterior walls of the right maxillary sinus. Infarcts in the right frontal and occipital lobes. Thrombosis of the right internal carotid artery, right jugular vein. Signs of venous hypertension. Absence of blood flow in the arteries and veins of the face and right orbit.

Fig. 3 A

Fig. 3 B

Fig. 3 C

Fig. 3 D

Fig. 3. Patient M., 20 years old.

- A – computed tomography; areas of cerebral ischemia are indicated by white arrows, drainage in the frontal sinus is marked by a black arrow;
- B – contrast-enhanced computed tomography, the left internal carotid artery (ICA) is indicated by a white arrow (normal), the absence of contrast in the right ICA is indicated by a yellow arrow (thrombosis);
- C – CT with 3D reconstruction, the arrow indicates thrombosis of the right ICA and facial vessels;
- D – CT in axial projection, the arrow indicates the ischemic stroke zone.

Additional instrumental and radiological diagnostic methods were performed. Thoracic CT revealed signs of bilateral polysegmental septic pneumonia. Ultrasound triplex scan results: occlusive thrombosis of the right internal carotid artery. Occlusive thrombosis of the jugular veins on both sides. Moderate sinus tachycardia was observed on ECG. According to echocardiography, Doppler ultrasound of the veins of the lower extremities, ultrasound examination of the abdominal organs, kidneys, and pelvic organs, as well as CT of the abdominal organs, no pathological changes were identified.

Despite ongoing treatment, which included antibacterial and anticoagulant therapy, the patient's condition deteriorated; neurological symptoms worsened, ketoacidosis increased, necrosis of the soft tissues of the right face progressed, vision in the right eye was lost, and the lower eyelid exhibited a purplish-cyanotic coloration.

A follow-up MSCT of the head and brachiocephalic vessels was performed after one week, revealing disease progression characterized by the development of thrombosis of the right cavernous sinus and enlargement of ischemic areas in the right hemisphere. The following conclusion was drawn based on the findings: thrombosis of the right internal carotid and middle cerebral arteries throughout their entire course. Thrombosis of the right cavernous sinus. Thrombosis of the right jugular vein. Absence of blood flow in the arteries and veins of the right side of the face and right orbit. Ischemic stroke in the territory of the right MCA, with an ASPECTS score of 3, involving the territory of the right PCA. Thrombosis of the meningeal veins at the level of the ischemic brain region (Fig. 3 G).

Owing to multiple organ failure, septicopyemia, and sepsis, the patient's condition was assessed as critically severe. Cardiac arrest was recorded two weeks after hospitalization. Resuscitation efforts were unsuccessful; biological death of the patient was confirmed. No discrepancies in diagnosis were found upon autopsy.

Discussion. The coexistence of arterial and venous thrombosis in the head and neck is relatively uncommon in clinical practice and represents a life-threatening condition. Such a combination poses several challenges for treating physicians in determining the optimal approach to patient evaluation and management [1, 2].

This clinical case demonstrates the development of combined thrombosis involving the jugular veins, cavernous sinus, right internal carotid and middle cerebral arteries, as well as the vessels of the right side of the face in a 20-year-old male patient, M. The trigger of the massive septic thrombotic process was odontogenic sinusitis that developed after tooth extraction. The capabilities of modern radiological diagnostic methods, such as MSCT angiography and venography, MRI with vascular imaging, and Doppler ultrasound examination, allowed for detection of thrombosis as well as determination of its extent and level of involvement [6, 7]. The challenge in diagnosing thrombotic occlusion at early stages in the male patient can be attributed to the rarity of this complication, low clinical suspicion

among attending physicians, and delayed patient presentation. The situation was further complicated by the absence of a specific clinical presentation at disease onset. One of the risk factors for the fulminant disease course is the patient's uncontrolled type II diabetes mellitus.

The clinical observation presented in this article can be regarded as a particular variant of Lemierre's Syndrome. In its classical course, Lemierre's Syndrome represents a rare and severe complication characterized by septic thrombosis of the internal jugular veins with metastatic spread of the infectious process to organs and tissues, developing on the background of acute purulent oropharyngeal infections. The most common cause is infection of the pharynx, tonsils, and oral cavity, less commonly associated with otitis media or mastoiditis [8]. Cases of Lemierre's syndrome following dental interventions have been reported [5]. The incidence ranges from 0.6 to 3.6 cases per million population per year, with a mortality rate of 2–20% [8, 9].

The causative agent is most frequently an anaerobic infection; various sources identify gram-negative *Fusobacterium necrophorum*, *Fusobacterium nucleatum*, *Bacteroides* spp., among others [8, 9]. The authors note that over the past decade, atypical Lemierre's Syndrome caused by other pathogens has been increasingly observed [8, 10]. In our clinical observation, the microbial agent was *Staphylococcus epidermidis*, a facultative anaerobe and opportunistic pathogen.

One stage in the disease progression is septic embolization to various organs and tissues (lungs, bones, brain, etc.). In this observation, secondary infectious foci were detected in the lungs.

The course of the pathological process was aggravated by the superimposition of complications. Complications of Lemierre's syndrome reported in the literature include thrombosis of the cavernous sinus, stenosis, and/or thrombosis of the internal carotid artery. The pathological changes of the internal carotid artery are attributed to its stenosis caused by thrombotic masses in the cavernous sinus, formation of fistulas between the cavernous sinus and the internal carotid artery, spread of infection to the vascular wall resulting in its necrosis, and subsequent migration of thrombus into the arterial lumen [10, 11]. In our observation, thrombosis of the right cavernous sinus was detected; additionally, a floating thrombus was visualized within the lumen of the right internal carotid artery, which subsequently extended to the middle cerebral artery and ultimately resulted in the development of a hemispheric stroke.

When considering the clinical course of the disease in this patient, particular attention should be given to the presence of type 2 diabetes mellitus. Diabetes mellitus is cited in the literature as one of the risk factors for the development of Lemierre's syndrome, as diabetes increases the tendency toward thrombosis. This is facilitated by several mechanisms, including endothelial dysfunction, coagulation activation, and platelet hyperreactivity [12]. In diabetes mellitus, host

resistance and responsiveness decrease [12], resulting in a sharply increased risk of developing septic complications. It should be noted that following tooth extraction, the patient did not monitor or manage glucose levels, which upon hospital admission were 18.43 mmol/L.

The patient's delayed seeking of medical care contributed to the progression of the disease. The patient ignored clear signs of infection and sought help from a dentist only two weeks later, when facial swelling, skin discoloration, loss of sensation, and headaches appeared, indicating the onset of vascular thrombosis.

The combination of the aforementioned adverse factors led to the progressive worsening of the patient's condition, the addition of complications, development of sepsis, multiple organ failure, and death. This clinical case vividly illustrates the full cascade of pathological reactions – from the trigger (dental intervention) to the development of combined thromboses and fatal outcome.

Conclusion. Thus, the presented clinical case demonstrates that patients with a history of odontogenic infection are at risk of developing combined cerebral thromboses of both arterial and venous vasculature. The variability of clinical manifestations and lack of clinical suspicion among physicians may hinder early diagnosis. This highlights the importance of systematic monitoring of patients' condition following dental procedures and, when indicated, the implementation of a comprehensive set of modern imaging techniques for the vasculature of the head and neck.

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APPLICATION OF RANDOM FOREST IN GYNECOLOGIC ONCOLOGY: CURRENT EVIDENCE AND FUTURE DEVELOPMENT PROSPECTS

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Abstract. *Gynecologic malignant neoplasms remain a significant global public health problem. Early diagnosis, recurrence prediction, and assessment of treatment efficacy are critical for improving outcomes in female patients. In recent decades, machine learning techniques (ML), particularly the Random Forest (RF) algorithm, have been widely employed in gynecologic oncology research [1,2]. RF, as an ensemble learning method, is characterized by high robustness and accuracy in the analysis of multifactorial clinical and molecular data [3]. Gynecologic cancers, particularly breast, cervical, and ovarian cancers, represent significant health challenges affecting women worldwide. For gynecologic oncologists, late detection remains problematic, necessitating accurate and predictive diagnostic tools to enhance survival rates and fertility preservation [8]. Traditional diagnostic methods often lack sensitivity, particularly for early or aggressive subtypes. Responses of patients to standard treatments vary, underscoring the importance of personalized medicine [9].*

Keywords: *gynecologic tumors; machine learning; early cancer detection; artificial intelligence in oncology; personalized medicine; multi-omics integration*

Introduction

Random Forest is composed of multiple decision trees generated using bootstrap sampling, and the final prediction is determined by majority voting or by averaging the results [1,4]. This approach reduces model variance and the risk of overfitting. Furthermore, RF enables evaluation of feature importance, facilitating the identification of key prognostic factors [5]. Random Forest (RF) is an ensemble machine learning method that constructs an ensemble of decision trees, each trained

on subsets of the data, performing a voting process to yield a more accurate and robust prediction [10]. In gynecologic oncology, random forests are employed to predict recurrence and survival of breast cancer (BC) based on genetic and histological features [11]. In cervical cancer, random forests automate the evaluation of Papanicolaou smears with high sensitivity, improving diagnostic consistency and reducing the workload of cytologists [12]. Random forest models are powerful because they can process diverse types of data — including imaging, genomics, and clinical parameters — and detect subtle interactions between variables that may remain undetected by conventional methods [13].

Random Forest algorithms are comprehensible and straightforward tools for predicting gynecologic cancer. Decision trees are simple machine learning models that mimic clinical reasoning by posing sequential yes/no questions (e.g., tumor > 2 cm, HPV positive) until a diagnosis is achieved [14]. Their transparency renders them particularly appealing in oncology, where interpretability is of paramount importance. In breast cancer (BC), mammographic features such as tissue density, shape, and margins are classified [15]. In cervical cancer, Papanicolaou smear results, medical history, and HPV genotype are integrated for risk assessment. In ovarian cancer, these support differentiation between benign and malignant cysts using imaging and clinical data [16,17]. Their ability to explain decisions connects AI outcomes with physician reasoning, which is particularly valuable when discrepancies exist between AI and clinical judgment in scenarios requiring physician review [17].

Overview of gynecological tumors

Cervical cancer

Most types of cervical cancer develop as a result of persistent high-risk HPV infection; Machine learning improves early detection, prevention, and risk assessment [64,65,66]. Machine learning already exerts a lifesaving and paradigm-shifting effect in this domain by enabling a more precise, effective, and personalized methodology for screening and prevention.

HPV and screening statistical analysis

Machine learning algorithms (decision trees, logistic regression, XGBoost) can predict CIN2+ progression with a sensitivity exceeding 85% [18,19,20]. Clinical significance: From a clinical standpoint, this enables gynecologic oncologists to customize screening intervals, identify women at highest risk of CIN2+ progression, and initiate preventive interventions earlier.

Interpretation of Pap smear images

Deep learning models, such as CNN architectures (U-Net, VGGNet), automate the analysis of cytological images, thereby reducing human error and supporting primary diagnosis, particularly in resource-constrained environments [21,22]. Clinical significance: In the field of gynecologic oncology, an SVM-based cytological classifier can promptly identify suspicious Papanicolaou smears, facilitating

expedited colposcopy, decreasing diagnostic delays, and enabling earlier therapeutic intervention. Kolasseri and Venkataramana (2024) demonstrated that the Random Forest (RF) algorithm outperformed traditional survival models in prognostic accuracy during the analysis of SEER database data [1]. Kim et al. (2021) reported that the Random Forest (RF) algorithm achieved the highest AUC value in predicting recurrence using clinical and genetic variables, including markers of Lynch syndrome [2].

Ovarian cancer

Ovarian cancer, commonly referred to as the “silent killer,” is usually diagnosed late due to vague symptoms and frequently presents at an advanced stage. Epithelial ovarian cancer (EOC) is the most common type, accounting for more than 90% of cases. Despite its lower incidence, ovarian cancer accounts for a disproportionately high share of deaths due to the absence of early diagnosis [23]. Although certain gene mutations, including BRCA1/2, are associated with an increased risk, screening remains inadequate. Machine learning is being investigated for the analysis of genomic, proteomic, and imaging data to detect subtle early markers, thereby improving risk stratification and enabling earlier interventions [24]. Yan et al. (2025) developed a Random Forest-based model for predicting recurrence in borderline ovarian tumors, achieving an area under the curve (AUC) of approximately 0.84 and identifying significant clinical factors through SHAP analysis [3]. Nopour (2024) reported high sensitivity of Random Forest in screening models based on risk factors [4].

Breast cancer

Breast cancer is the most frequently diagnosed cancer in women worldwide and remains a major public health challenge. Heterogeneity, characterized by hormone receptor and HER2 status, determines clinical risk stratification and treatment selection. Treatment decisions in breast cancer depend on these molecular subtypes and influence prognosis prediction [25]. Although advances in screening and targeted therapy have significantly increased survival, machine learning (ML) can assist in integrating imaging, genomic, and clinical data to enhance oncological tasks related to prognosis, treatment response, and survival [26].

Uterine (endometrial) cancer

Liu et al. (2022) applied a hybrid Random Forest (RF)–neural network model to predict the localization of uterine cancer recurrence, achieving 88% accuracy, with RF playing a key role in feature selection [5].

Overall trends

Systematic reviews indicate that RF is among the most commonly applied machine learning algorithms in gynecologic oncology, particularly in tasks of prognostic modeling and survival analysis [6,7]. Its interpretability and adaptability to clinical data render it a promising tool for further research and integration into clinical practice. Traditional diagnostic methods often lack sensitivity, particularly

for early or aggressive subtypes. Patient responses to standard treatments vary, emphasizing the importance of personalized medicine [27]. Random Forest, a branch of artificial intelligence (AI), offers powerful capabilities for analyzing complex medical data. In contrast to traditional statistical methods, Random Forest is capable of identifying patterns in large, multidimensional datasets such as clinical records, genomic profiles, imaging, and biosignals. Random Forest is utilized throughout the entire cancer treatment continuum — from disease prognosis and risk assessment to treatment planning and survival prediction [28]. Machine learning models have demonstrated significant potential in gynecologic oncology, including tumor type classification, automation of Pap smear analysis, mammography interpretation, prediction of metastases or recurrences, as well as discovery of novel biomarkers based on genomic data. Such applications support more proactive, precise, and evidence-based oncological care [29].

Advantages and limitations

The most transformative vision of machine learning is a learning healthcare system that continuously improves as new clinical data are integrated. Each patient encounter, imaging study, or laboratory test contributes to the iterative refinement of the model, thereby ensuring continuous real-time improvements in patient care. This feedback generates a dynamic system that becomes increasingly accurate, efficient, and personalized with each cycle [30]. If realized, machine learning could become the cornerstone of future gynecologic oncology [31].

Training in federated and secure data sharing

The development of robust machine learning models necessitates access to diverse and representative datasets, yet data sharing is constrained by privacy and intellectual property limitations. Federated learning (FL) enables training models across institutions without sharing patients' raw data [32]. Owing to its unique advantages, FL can develop models that represent diverse populations, thereby enhancing generalizability in gynecologic oncology [33].

Multi-omics and Real-World Data Integration

The integration of multi-omics with real clinical data represents a new frontier. Integrating multi-omics data — namely genomics, proteomics, transcriptomics, and metabolomics — can yield deeper insights into tumor biology [34]. In combination with real-world data, including lifestyle, environmental data, electronic health records, and wearable sensors, machine learning can identify novel predictors of cancer risk, progression, and treatment response, thereby improving early detection and prognostic modeling in gynecologic tumors [35].

Personalized and Precision Oncology

Machine learning plays a key role in advancing precision oncology by customizing interventions according to the molecular and clinical profile of each patient [36]. These interventions include predictive models that identify patients most

likely to benefit from hormone therapy, chemotherapy, or immunotherapy. They can also predict recurrence risk, assist in fertility preservation decisions for young women, and personalize surveillance schedules. In gynecologic oncology, such personalization improves outcomes by avoiding unnecessary interventions [37].

Clinical decision support systems (CDSS)

With the advancement of machine learning, real-time CDSS will become more widely utilized. These systems can provide practical data at the point of care, highlighting the results of high-risk imaging and pathology during consultations or surgery [38]. Moreover, user-friendly tools (e.g., dashboards, mobile applications, or voice assistance systems) are necessary to optimize workflows without imposing additional burden on clinicians [39].

Points of care and limited resources

In most low-resource settings, there is a shortage of adequate specialists and equipment for gynecologic cancer screening. ML provides scalable solutions that democratize access to healthcare [40]. For example, cervical imaging on smartphones using machine learning or HPV self-sampling assisted by artificial intelligence can help provide underserved communities with vital tools for early detection. In addition to reducing healthcare disparities, these advances may facilitate early intervention, potentially improving survival rates in regions where late-stage diagnosis remains prevalent [41].

Ethical AI and Bias Mitigation

With the increasing integration of machine learning in oncological care, it is critically important to ensure ethical and unbiased AI. Algorithmic bias remains a significant challenge, as models trained on non-representative data may exacerbate disparities [42]. Future development should prioritize diverse datasets, bias detection tools, and validation across all populations to ensure equitable benefits [43].

Development of policy and regulatory frameworks

Robust regulatory frameworks are necessary to ensure the safety, efficacy, and ethical application of machine learning tools. Well-documented guidelines provided by agencies such as the FDA and EMA, alongside universal directives, will enhance clinicians' trust in the implementation of AI [44].

Interdisciplinary Collaboration and Education

Maximizing the role of machine learning requires education and interdisciplinary collaboration. Clinicians require proficiency in artificial intelligence, while data specialists should understand clinical oncology. Medical students, residents, and other healthcare professionals, as well as partnerships among oncologists, bioinformaticians, ethicists, and engineers, should stimulate training programs aimed at bridging this knowledge gap [45].

Key challenges and limitations in implementing machine learning in oncology

Although Random Forest possesses significant potential in gynecologic oncology, its clinical integration remains limited. While it can aid in earlier diagnosis,

risk stratification, and personalized therapy, several systemic barriers hinder its real-world implementation. These include data quality, algorithm reliability, validation, infrastructure, regulatory oversight, ethics, and limited clinical training. Of these, data quality and inconsistency are among the most critical obstacles. In gynecologic oncology, incomplete records, inconsistent annotation, and class imbalance (e.g., the predominance of earlier stages compared to rare advanced cases) reduce the reliability and generalizability of models [46,47].

Challenges related to modeling

In oncology, challenges associated with modeling impede the clinical implementation of machine learning. A primary challenge is interpretability; many machine learning tools function as ‘black boxes,’ generating results without transparent rationale [48]. This limits clinical confidence, particularly in decision-making within gynecologic oncology. Retraining presents another challenge; for example, a Pap smear model trained in one laboratory may fail in other settings due to staining variability [49]. Furthermore, most machine learning tools lack prospective validation and are evaluated only retrospectively, thereby reducing trust in their practical oncological application [50].

Clinical integration and infrastructural barriers

Workflow disruptions constitute an additional barrier. Even highly accurate models may fail to integrate effectively if they are poorly incorporated into electronic medical records or contribute to increased clinician workload [51]. Regulatory uncertainty further delays implementation, as agencies such as the FDA and EMA do not have well-defined approval pathways for oncology tools based on AI [52].

Ethical, legal, and social considerations

The application of machine learning in gynecologic oncology raises significant ethical, legal, and social issues. Algorithmic bias can exacerbate inequalities, especially for underrepresented groups [53]. Lack of transparency regarding how machine learning influences diagnosis and treatment also threatens informed consent and patient trust [54].

Resource limitations and educational gaps

The development and maintenance of machine learning models require expensive infrastructure and expertise, which are often unavailable in resource-constrained environments [55]. Clinicians also have insufficient expertise in AI, which limits their ability to interpret and trust machine learning tools. The slow integration of digital health into medical education further exacerbates this gap [56].

Responsible and equitable integration

Random Forest presents a unique opportunity to revolutionize gynecologic oncology; however, its effective practical implementation largely depends on overcoming various multifaceted challenges. Only by addressing these stages can ML become a reliable and equitable instrument in gynecologic oncology for diagnosis, personalized treatment, and improvement of patient outcomes [57,58].

Conclusions

ML is beginning to assist in early diagnosis by detecting subtle biomarker signatures and performing radiodiagnostic scanning of these markers [60]. Beyond enhancing diagnostic accuracy, ML models can refine risk stratification, predict treatment outcomes, and personalize care pathways for patients with breast, ovarian, and cervical cancers [61]. For gynecologic oncologists, the integration of ML into routine practice offers tangible advantages – earlier detection of ovarian cancer through biomarker integration, fertility-preserving treatment planning for young patients with breast and cervical cancers, as well as risk-adapted surveillance in cases of recurrent disease. By integrating computational advances with clinical workflows, ML holds the potential to provide more individualized, equitable, and patient-centered gynecologic oncology care.

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ADDITIONAL OPPORTUNITIES OF THE PSYCHOLOGICAL AND PSYCHIATRIC SERVICE IN EMERGENCY SITUATIONS OF VARIOUS NATURE

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Abstract. *The number of emergencies involving a significant number of injured and fatalities is increasing annually. Risk factors for accidents and industrial disasters at economic sites, along with the possible mechanisms of their occurrence and the resultant magnitude and structure of sanitary losses, necessitate a comprehensive analysis of the healthcare system capabilities within administrative regions to provide medical assistance to those affected by large-scale emergencies with mass casualties. The increase in the number of emergencies results in a sustained growth in the number of individuals within society experiencing various mental disorders induced by exposure to diverse stressogenic factors.*

The organization and delivery of medical care, including psychiatric and psychological support to the population during emergencies, represents a complex and pressing challenge for disaster medicine services at the present stage.

Keywords: *AHOV (accidental hazardous chemical substances), emergencies, risk zones, potentially hazardous facilities, casualties, psychological and psychiatric assistance.*

Mass disasters caused by factors unusually strong and significant provoke, among other effects, the most adverse impact — they injure the human psyche and impair social adaptation. According to domestic and international psychiatric studies, the prevalence of severe mental disorders in disaster-affected zones is estimated at 10%. Even in the classical works of the domestic psychiatric school, it has been demonstrated that these types of mental reactions develop in individuals with an adverse premorbid background (psychopathy, character accentuations,

pre-existing neurotic disorders, latent endogenous diseases, etc.). Acute stress reactions are identified by pronounced changes in consciousness, attention, disorientation, psychomotor agitation, or stupor (F43.0, ICD-10 codes). Disorders classified under category F44 (dissociative [conversion] disorders) are of particular significance, namely: F44.0 — partial or complete amnesia, F44.1 — dissociative fugue (motor agitation), F44.2 — dissociative stupor, F44.3 — trance and possession, F44.5 — dissociative convulsions. These disorders are accompanied by motor disturbances and present a hazard, as they may provoke the phenomenon of psychic induction; consequently, they necessitate the implementation of therapeutic and evacuation interventions.

Approximately 10–15% of affected individuals require inpatient care in psychoneurological facilities, while at least 50% require outpatient and polyclinic treatment. The primary objective in these cases is to identify individuals exhibiting psychomotor agitation, ensure their safety and that of others, eliminate conditions of confusion, and prevent the occurrence of mass panic reactions. [1]

Provision of psychological and psychiatric assistance to the population primarily entails the implementation of preparatory activities, which ultimately aim to minimize casualties and material damage resulting from emergencies. The organization and delivery of psychiatric and psychological assistance to the population in emergencies at the present stage constitute a complex and pressing task for disaster medicine services, necessitating the involvement of specialist medical professionals and the training of EMERCOM medical personnel in the relevant skills to provide this type of care. The number of individuals seeking psychological and psychiatric assistance in emergencies is determined not by the actual demand for such care but by the location of the psychiatrist's office. Therefore, it is necessary to carefully determine the location where the psychiatrist (psychotherapist) should carry out consultations. Psychiatrists (psychotherapists) should also provide outpatient reception. Experience indicates that the number of individuals seeking psychological and psychiatric assistance during emergencies is influenced not by the actual demand for this type of assistance, but by the location of the psychiatrist's office. Therefore, it is necessary to carefully determine the location where the psychiatrist (psychotherapist) should carry out consultations. In some cases, it is advisable to conduct consultations in the same building (or, if possible, in the same ward) where medical care is provided to the victims. [2]

This study employs calculations of potential sanitary losses in accidents at chemical industry facilities, exemplified by the Republic of Tatarstan. The territory of the Republic of Tatarstan possesses substantial economic potential and a developed industrial sector, with leading industries including oil extraction, petrochemicals, mechanical engineering, energy, transport and communications, alongside a relatively stable agricultural sector.

Although the capacities with AHOV substances used for prognostic calculations are several times smaller (due to storage technology) in emergencies involving chlorine as a harmful agent, health casualties are significant, and correspondingly, the incidence of mental disorders is substantial.

Estimated indicators of those requiring psycho-neurological assistance during potential chlorine accidents by risk zones in the Republic of Tatarstan among the adult population

Risk zones emergency situations	Amount of AHOV, tons	Total affected	Including	
			Requiring inpatient treatment in a psy- choneurological medical institution	Requiring assis- tance in outpatient and polyclinic facilities
Kazan	0,8	6247	937	3123
Almetyevsk	0,8	7830	1174	3915
Bugulma	0,05	3423	514	1712
Zelenodolsk	0,05	4204	630	1104
Leninogorsk	0,05	1946	292	973
Naberezhnye Chelny Chelny	0,96	7929	1189	3965
Nizhnekamsk	1,0	7265	1090	3633
Chistopol	0,05	4303	645	2152

Considering the emergence of a mass number of psychiatric-profile casualties during emergencies, it is advisable to establish specialized psychotherapeutic medical teams and to allocate dedicated space for their activities. Their responsibilities include providing urgent specialized psychiatric care in the emergency zone and transporting patients with mental disorders who require psychiatric treatment in inpatient facilities.

The creation of such teams enables the deployment of personnel and resources as close as possible to the disaster site in cases of mass casualties, as well as the prompt resolution of reinforcement issues,

and delivering qualified care incorporating elements of specialized assistance in the most

In the early stages, it is essential to understand the structure of mental disorders and the psychological and psychiatric consequences of emergencies, as well as to ensure the continuity and succession of therapeutic and preventive measures at all levels.

The provision of medical assistance, including psychological and psychiatric care, can to some extent be addressed by employing sanatorium-resort and preventive institutions, as well as health centers, for the medical treatment and

rehabilitation of victims of accidents and disasters of various etiologies, provided that the system is pre-planned and their organizational-functional operations are adapted for emergency conditions.

Justification for providing qualified and specialized medical care in sanatorium-resort and other health promotion institutions:

Firstly. The inability to ensure timely and adequate bed capacity in medical institutions for accommodating the affected.

Secondly. The inability to discharge patients. Under actual conditions, therapeutic inpatient facilities are occupied at 85–95 % capacity by severely ill patients who are not eligible for discharge to outpatient care.

Thirdly, within risk zones or in their immediate vicinity, there are medical and preventive institutions equipped with an adequate number of beds, as well as with necessary equipment and facilities, and all essential conditions for organizing nutrition and sanitary-hygienic support. These resources can be utilized through timely planning, reorganization of their functioning under emergency conditions, and reinforcement with appropriate forces and means.

Fourthly, a portion of medical institutions may be located within the emergency zone and thus unable to receive casualties.

In this context, the question is resolved regarding the possible placement of the psychological and psychiatric assistance department, the psychological and psychiatric assistance office, and the mobile consultative psychological and psychiatric assistance team. [3]

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MEDICAL AND SOCIAL CHARACTERISTICS OF PATIENTS WHO UNDERWENT BREAST PLASTIC SURGERY

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Abstract. *A questionnaire survey was conducted among 97 patients who underwent mammoplasty. The questionnaire was compiled in accordance with the recommendations proposed for assessing the satisfaction of patients who underwent breast plastic surgery, developed by the Memorial Oncology Center named after Sloane-Kettering and the University of British Columbia. Patients generally evaluate the outcomes positively and have a favorable perception of their body image, regardless of age. At the same time, younger-age patients, when self-assessing their experiences, are more frequently oriented towards relationships with those around them, whereas older-age patients focus more on their own sensations and their identification with their gender. When interacting with a patient receiving medical services, it is essential to consider their medical-social and demographic characteristics, which enable specifying each patient's expectations and thereby ensure a personalized approach that accounts for their individual needs and specific features.*

Keywords: *mammoplasty, medical-social characteristics, self-assessment of plastic surgery patients*

Relevance

In recent decades, there has been an increase in demand for plastic surgeries and cosmetic procedures due to various factors, including the aging of the population, advances in surgical technologies, and evolving societal perceptions of aesthetics [1–3]. Understanding epidemiological trends and the economic impact of plastic surgical procedures is essential for plastic surgeons, healthcare

policymakers, and hospital administrators to optimize resource allocation and patient care strategies [4].

Objective of the study: to examine the medical and social characteristics of female patients undergoing plastic surgery, including the evaluation of postoperative outcomes achieved, which is essential for enhancing the efficiency of organizing paid medical services in the field of plastic surgery.

Materials and methods of the study

The study included 97 female patients who underwent mammoplasty. The survey was carried out according to the recommendations proposed for assessing the satisfaction of patients who underwent breast plastic surgery, developed by the Memorial Oncology Center named after Sloan-Kettering and the University of British Columbia, 2017. The Spearman rank correlation method was employed to determine the relationships between the studied phenomena. The significance of differences between group mean values in the analysis of the results obtained for the compared study groups was assessed by calculating Student's t-test.

Results

A total of ninety-seven patients who underwent breast plastic surgery were under observation. Among them, 71 had higher education, 14 had secondary vocational or incomplete higher education, and 12 had secondary education. Based on the data analysis, female patients undergoing plastic surgery significantly predominantly have higher education ($p < 0.005$).

Sixty-three respondents were married (including 20 in cohabiting relationships); 34 women participating in the study were unmarried at the time of the survey.

The mean age of the respondents was 35 years (34.99 ± 1.12), median = 32, standard deviation (σ) = 11.02. It should be noted that there is a statistically significant predominance of young patients among women undergoing plastic surgery (group 1), $p < 0.005$. Differences between groups regarding marital status, according to the results of the Student's t-test calculation, are not significant ($p > 0.05$). In subsequent studies, the severity of the analyzed indicators was evaluated both for all patients as a whole and comparatively depending on the respondents' age group.

According to the completed questionnaire, the following parameters were assessed: body image as perceived by the patients during self-assessment of their appearance; feelings about oneself in society, including the desire to attract attention; daily self-care; the sense of being happy; feelings experienced by the patient regarding her own breast or breast area; satisfaction with her breast; presence of any discomfort in the breast (pain sensations, movement difficulties, altered sensitivity in the breast area, possibly swelling of the arm on the side of the breast surgery); presence of any discomfort in the abdomen; satisfaction with the appearance of the abdomen, abdominal scars, and navel position; perception of one's own sexuality (both clothed and unclothed); as well as a number of other indicators.

The body image analysis was performed based on the self-assessment results of patients who underwent plastic surgery. Patients were asked to evaluate their feelings according to the proposed parameters using a scoring scale ranging from ‘-3’ to ‘3’. The results obtained for all studied patterns are presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1 – Mean scores of patients’ body image self-assessment by groups
 Group 1 – young women; Group 2 – middle-aged and elderly women

Based on the presented data, across all analyzed indicators, body image is relatively more favorable in the group of young women (group 1), without statistically significant differences in any of the 19 indicators. At the same time, members of group 1 assigned relatively higher ratings to such indicators as ‘relationships with family members,’ ‘feeling happy,’ ‘interaction with members of the opposite sex,’ and ‘desire to engage in behaviors that could attract attention to their appearance.’ Members of group 2 (middle-aged and elderly women) reported the highest scores

for the following parameters: ‘sense of conformity to one’s gender,’ ‘interaction with members of the same gender,’ ‘interaction with members of the opposite gender,’ ‘experiences at work or study,’ and ‘ability to control the quality and quantity of food.’ Since statistical significance of differences between groups 1 and 2 is absent, the distribution of response frequencies to questions 1–19 is presented for the overall cohort of respondents. The distribution of responses regarding the assessment of the ‘Sense of Self-Worth’ is presented in Figure 2. The mean score for the response to question 1 was 1.77 ± 1.062 .

Figure 2 – Distribution of responses to question 1 ‘Sense of Self-Worth’ with possible score values ranging from ‘-3’ to ‘3’.

The majority of respondents generally perceive their self-worth positively: only 2 out of 98 patients selected the answers ‘-1’ and ‘-2’, while 8 respondents chose the score ‘0’ ($p < 0.05$).

The distribution of scores assigned by respondents to question 2, ‘Sense of conformity to their gender,’ was 1.84 ± 0.102 .

It is also important to note the generally positive perception by respondents regarding ‘conformity to their gender’: only 2 out of 98 respondents answered this question negatively, and 5 respondents selected the response ‘0’. The remaining 91 respondents (92.86%) evaluated their conformity to their gender positively, with responses predominantly grouped in the scores ‘2’ and ‘3’— the highest attainable values.

A similar analysis was performed by us across all patterns. The limitations of this communication do not allow for their complete presentation.

Conclusions

Patients who underwent plastic surgery generally assess the outcomes positively and maintain a positive perception of their own body image, regardless of age. At the same time, younger-age patients, when self-assessing their experiences, are more frequently oriented towards relationships with those around them, whereas older-age patients focus more on their own sensations and their identification with their gender. When interacting with a patient receiving medical services, it is essential to consider their medical-social and demographic characteristics, which enable specifying each patient's expectations and thereby ensure a personalized approach that accounts for their individual needs and specific features.

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FACTORS OF THE NEED FOR IVF INTERVENTION: THE MAIN CLINICAL CAUSES OF INFERTILITY

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Abstract. *The causes of infertility determine the prognosis. Analysis of the distribution of infertility causes among the examined patients demonstrated a marked predominance of the male factor; constituting approximately 60% of cases. This distribution aligns with global trends, where the contribution of the male factor to the infertility structure is gradually increasing. Success rates were higher in cases of tubal-peritoneal factor, whereas pregnancy was rarely achieved in patients with endometriosis and adenomyosis. Associated conditions — fibroids, uterine scarring, obesity, and decreased ovarian reserve — further limited treatment effectiveness. Analysis of the causes of infertility enables the development of targeted prevention strategies for this pathology.*

Keywords: *infertility, causes of infertility, utilization of In Vitro Fertilization services*

Relevance: essential understanding of the epidemiology and factors contributing to infertility. Infertility statistics continue to be a cause for concern. In Russia, one in every six women of reproductive age is affected by this issue, which aligns with data from the World Health Organization. Furthermore, several studies report even higher prevalence rates – ranging from 8% to 29% of married couples experience difficulties conceiving [98,100,105]. These data underscore the relevance of the issue and the necessity for further advancement of reproductive technologies.

The aim of the study was to analyze the structure of infertility causes based on patient visits to the In Vitro Fertilization service.

Materials and Methods. The study is comprehensive and interdisciplinary, encompassing clinical, sociological, and technological components. The study design involved, at the initial stage, a retrospective approach, followed by prospective,

comparative, and cohort methodologies. Conducted during the period from 2021 to 2024. Based at the specialized assisted reproductive technology center – the ‘Generation NEXT Grozny’ Clinic. This report addresses the clinical component of the study. A total of 186 patients presenting with infertility were examined. The collected data were analyzed using classical statistical methods of variation.

Research results. Analysis of the distribution of infertility causes among the examined patients demonstrated a marked predominance of the male factor, constituting approximately 60% of cases. This distribution corresponds to global trends, wherein the contribution of the male factor to the infertility profile is progressively increasing. It is pertinent to emphasize that in such cases, the application of the ICSI methodology has become the principal approach for overcoming spermatogenic impairments, underscoring the significance of employing advanced technologies in clinical practice. Although more complex laboratory procedures are required, the outcomes in this category were not significantly inferior to those observed in other forms, demonstrating the relative efficacy of compensatory techniques.

The tuboperitoneal factor accounted for the second highest prevalence (12% of the sample). In these women, the effectiveness of treatment protocols was somewhat higher than in cases involving endocrine and combined forms, which can be attributed to the preservation of ovarian reserve and the possibility of utilizing a complete pool of oocytes. However, the presence of adhesions (1%) further impaired the prognosis, necessitating preliminary surgical interventions and increasing the risk of recurrent failures.

Endometriosis as a cause of infertility was documented in 10% of women. This pathology was associated with worse clinical pregnancy outcomes and a higher frequency of complicated results (biochemical pregnancies, early losses), which may indicate a detrimental effect of endometriosis on implantation and endometrial quality.

A reduction in ovarian reserve was identified in 4% of patients. This category exhibited an extremely unfavorable prognosis – the number of positive outcomes was minimal, and in certain cases, complicated pregnancy outcomes were observed (for example, ectopic implantation). This factor is distinctly associated with age over 40 years, indicating a correlation between clinical-demographic characteristics and In Vitro Fertilization outcomes.

The group ‘other and mixed factors’ (13%) encompassed endocrine disorders, combined forms (tubal + endometriosis, male + endocrine, etc.), as well as rare causes (metabolic syndromes, immunological factors). Patients within this group exhibit heterogeneous outcomes, ranging from successful conception to complicated clinical presentations, highlighting the challenges in prognosis and the necessity for an individualized approach.

Additional analysis of infertility duration revealed that women, on average, experienced infertility for 5.8 ± 3.9 years (median: 5 years; range: 1 to 20 years). The most frequently observed clinical histories ranged from 3 to 8 years. Infertility duration exceeding 10 years was observed less frequently but was associated with a markedly reduced probability of conception, potentially due to the accumulation of pathological alterations in the reproductive system and diminished oocyte quality.

The structure of infertility causes in the studied sample demonstrates a significant predominance of male factor infertility, whereas in women, tubal-peritoneal disorders and endometriosis were predominant. The most unfavorable prognostic indicators were observed with decreased ovarian reserve and endometriosis, while the tubal factor was associated with relatively better outcomes. These data underscore the importance of precise identification of the cause of infertility and individualization of the treatment strategy.

Figure 3.4 depicts the distribution of patients by duration of infertility. Most women reported infertility lasting several years prior to seeking medical consultation.

Figure 3.4 Duration of infertility

According to the presented data, the most common duration of infertility ranged from 2 to 8 years, with peaks at 2 and 5 years. Longer durations (exceeding 10 years) were less frequent, with the maximum recorded duration being 20 years.

The distribution of infertility causes identified a male factor in 60% of cases. The tubal-peritoneal factor accounted for 12%, endometriosis for 10%, diminished ovarian reserve for 4%, and adhesions for 1%. Other or mixed causes were recorded in 13% of cases. Figure 3.5 illustrates the distribution of infertility causes.

The most frequent cause was male factor infertility (60% of cases), whereas tubal-peritoneal factor and endometriosis occurred less frequently (12% and 10%, respectively). Other causes constituted a smaller proportion.

Figure 3.5 – Causes of infertility in the overall sample

Conclusions. Infertility remains a relevant medical and social problem requiring a comprehensive approach for its resolution. The causes of infertility determine the prognosis. In cases of the tubal-peritoneal factor, success rates were higher, whereas pregnancy was rare in endometriosis and adenomyosis. Associated conditions – fibroids, uterine scarring, obesity, and decreased ovarian reserve – further limited treatment effectiveness. Analysis of the causes of infertility enables the development of targeted prevention strategies for this pathology.

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CLINICAL AND STATISTICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF PATIENTS WITH PHANTOM PAIN

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Abstract. *The high incidence of tissue scarring following gunshot, burn, surgical, and household injuries makes this issue a priority in modern restorative medicine. Furthermore, pathological scarring has a significant social dimension – it restricts working capacity, hinders social adaptation, and diminishes patients' quality of life. The clinical and statistical characteristics of patients revealed the leading symptom: phantom pain was a significant factor of functional insufficiency and could hinder the establishment of a stable load regimen and prosthesis adaptation. Subjective sensations and load tolerance were closely related to the condition of the stump tissues and scar changes, therefore the evaluation of phantom pain management was considered part of comprehensive post-traumatic rehabilitation. The obtained information served as the basis for developing a rehabilitation program for this patient cohort.*

Keywords: *phantom pain, tissue scarring, post-traumatic rehabilitation.*

Relevance. Tissue scarring following combat injuries represents a complex biological process involving inflammation, reparative connective tissue growth, and collagen remodeling. Under normal progression, this process ensures defect closure and restoration of the integrity of skin and soft tissue structures. However, in some cases, a pathological scar — either hypertrophic or keloid — develops, accompanied by disruption of tissue architecture and functional impairments. The high incidence of such complications following gunshot, burn, surgical, and domestic injuries makes this issue a priority in contemporary restorative medicine. Furthermore, pathological scarring has

a significant social dimension — it restricts work capacity, complicates social adaptation, and diminishes patients' quality of life [1].

An effective strategy for the management of pathological scarring requires the coordinated efforts of specialists from diverse specialties [2, 3].

Aim of the study: to examine the baseline characteristics of patients with phantom pain in order to subsequently develop a modified rehabilitation program.

Materials and methods. The analysis of phantom pain syndrome included 70 patients with limb amputations following traumatic injury, in whom scar tissue changes in the stump had developed by the time of the initial examination (Stage I). The subgroup analysis was descriptive and aimed to characterize the baseline clinical and anamnestic features before assessing the dynamics of phantom pain during subsequent follow-up stages.

Results. The mean age of the patients was 42.0 ± 12.0 years. The subgroup was predominantly male—66 men versus 4 women; amputations of the lower limbs were present in both genders. Regarding amputation sites, lower limb amputations predominated—54 cases (77.1%), while upper limb amputations accounted for 16 cases (22.9%). Notably, all upper limb amputations in this subgroup were observed exclusively in men ($n = 16$). Among lower limb amputations, transtibial levels were the most frequent ($n=30$; 42.9%), followed by transfemoral ($n=16$; 22.9%) and amputations at the foot/ankle joint level ($n=8$; 11.4%). Among upper limb amputations, transradial levels predominated ($n=10$; 14.3%), with transhumeral amputations accounting for 6 cases (8.6%).

The time since amputation/trauma at the time of inclusion was 12.0 ± 9.0 months: less than 6 months — 10 (28.6%), 6–12 months — 12 (34.3%), 12–24 months — 8 (22.9%), more than 24 months — 5 (14.3%). At the time of enrollment, a prosthesis was used by 44 (62.9%) patients, with scar localization in the zone of potential or actual prosthetic load noted in 40 (57.1%). Regarding the morphotype of stump scars, hypertrophic scars predominated—44 (62.9%), while keloid scars were observed in 26 (37.1%). Concomitant pain in the stump was reported by 38 (54.3%) patients.

At inclusion in the study (Stage I), the intensity of phantom pain on the 10-point VAS/NRS scale (0–10 points) in the subgroup $n=70$ averaged 6.4 ± 1.7 points, with a median of 6 [5; 8] points. Thus, most patients were characterized by moderate to severe baseline pain intensity.

When analyzing the distribution by severity levels (0–3 points — mild, 4–6 — moderate, 7–10 — severe), it was found that mild phantom pain was present in 8 (11.4%) patients, moderate in 24 (34.3%), and severe in 38 (54.3%) (Table 4.2). Thus, the proportion of patients with severe phantom pain (≥ 7 points) was 54.3%, necessitating targeted pain management from the early stages of rehabilitation.

Table 4.1 – Clinical and anamnesis characteristics of the patient subgroup with phantom pain (n=70), Stage I

Parameter	Value
Age, years (M±SD)	42,0 ± 12,0
Men, n (%)	66
Women, n (%)	4
Lower limb amputation, n (%)	54 (77,1)
Upper limb amputation, n (%)	16 (22,9)
Amputation level – transtibial, n (%)	30 (42,9)
Amputation level – transfemoral, n (%)	16 (22,9)
Amputation level – foot/ankle, n (%)	8 (11,4)
Amputation level – transradial, n (%)	10 (14,3)
Amputation level – transhumeral, n (%)	6 (8,6)
Time since amputation/trauma, months (M±SD)	24,0 ± 9,0
< 6 months, n (%)	20 (28,6)
6–12 months, n (%)	24 (34,3)
12–24 months, n (%)	16 (22,9)
> 24 months, n (%)	10 (14,3)
Uses prosthesis at inclusion, n (%)	44 (62,9)
Scar in the prosthetic load area, n (%)	40 (57,1)
Stump scar morphotype – hypertrophic, n (%)	44 (62,9)
Stump scar morphotype – keloid, n (%)	26 (37,1)
Associated pain in the stump, n (%)	38 (54,3)

Baseline severity of phantom pain according to VAS/NRS (Stage I)

Table 4.2 – Initial severity of phantom pain according to VAS/NRS (n=70), Stage I

Parameter	Value
VAS/NRS, points (M±SD)	6,4 ± 1,7
VAS/NRS, points (Me [Q1; Q3])	6 [5; 8]
Mild pain (0–3), n (%)	4 (11,4)
Moderate pain (4–6), n (%)	12 (34,3)
Severe pain (7–10), n (%)	19 (54,3)

At Stage I of the observation, phantom pain in the majority of patients was recurrent in nature and characterized by a combination of high episode frequency and significant duration of painful paroxysms. Daily occurrences of phantom pain were reported by 46 (65.7%) patients, episodes 3–6 times per week by 16 (22.9%), and 1–2 times per week by 8 (11.4%). Several episodes per day were typical for some patients, accompanied by pronounced subjective discomfort and reduced tolerance to functional load.

Regarding the duration of a typical episode, attacks lasting 10–30 minutes predominated in 28 (40.0%) patients; episodes up to 10 minutes were observed in 16 (22.9%), 30–60 minutes in 18 (25.7%), and more than 60 minutes in 8 (11.4%) patients. Thus, phantom pain had a tendency toward a prolonged course in 37.1% of patients (episodes lasting 30 minutes or more).

The most common triggers were mechanical load on the stump or contact with the prosthesis — 40 (57.1%), change in body position combined with motor activity — 36 (51.4%), change in ambient temperature — 32 (45.7%), as well as emotional stress — 26 (37.1%). Less frequently, patients reported symptom exacerbation at night and during sleep disturbances; at the same time, triggers often combined, forming an individual ‘provocation profile’, which should be considered when planning the load regimen and evaluating treatment outcomes at subsequent stages.

Moreover, phantom pain exerted a significant influence on patients’ daily activities and the quality of their nocturnal sleep. Sleep disturbances (difficulty falling asleep and/or nocturnal awakenings due to pain) were observed in 48 (68.6%) patients. In this group, 28 (40.0%) patients experienced pain accompanied by regular nighttime awakenings, whereas 20 (28.6%) primarily had difficulty falling asleep caused by anticipation or intensification of pain sensations in the evening.

Functional activity was also limited—52 (74.3%) patients reported reduced tolerance to everyday physical activity due to phantom pain. Limitation of active exertion time during the day was observed in 36 (51.4%) patients, while in 16 (22.9%) phantom pain caused significant avoidance of exertion, negatively impacting rehabilitation potential.

Of the 44 patients using a prosthesis at the time of inclusion, 30 (68.2%) reported restricted prosthesis wearing time due to pain (including that caused by a combination of phantom pain and discomfort in the stump/scar area under load). In 18 (40.9%) patients, there was a need for frequent removal of the prosthesis during the day, and in 12 (27.3%) — episodes of refusal to use the prosthesis on days with severe pain.

Conclusions. Thus, even at the initial stage, phantom pain was a significant factor of functional failure and could hinder the establishment of a stable loading regimen and prosthetic adaptation. In patients with amputations, subjective sensations and load tolerance were closely associated with the condition of the stump

tissues and scar alterations; therefore, the assessment of phantom pain relief was considered an integral part of comprehensive post-traumatic rehabilitation. The obtained information served as the basis for developing a rehabilitation program for this patient cohort.

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THE CASE OF ATYPICAL FORM OF KASABACH-MERRITT SYNDROME

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Abstract: *Lymphatic malformation of the trunk is rare, commonly involving neck and axillary region. A neonate presented with giant cystic swelling on the right and left sides of trunk and right upper limb. The MRI showed that lymphangioma is multicystic mass, which contains both micro- and macrocysts on the right side and microcystic structures on the left side of the chest. Moreover, the localization and the structure of lymphatic malformation are unusual. Aspiration and blood transfusion were done, but the baby died of sepsis postoperatively. On autopsy cytological structure of this swelling was similar with Kasabach-Merritt phenomenon.*

Keywords: *Lymphatic Malformation (LM), cavernous lymphangioma, cystic hygroma, macrocystic lymphatic malformation, microcystic lymphatic malformation, Kasabach-Merritt Syndrome.*

Introduction

Lymphatic malformations are rare. Non-malignant masses consisting of fluid-filled channels or spaces thought to be caused by the abnormal development of the lymphatic system. These malformations are usually apparent at birth or by the age of two. Lymphatic malformations can affect any area of the body, but most commonly they affect the head and neck. When evident at birth, lymphatic malformations tend to be soft, spongy, non-tender masses. The specific symptoms and severity of lymphatic malformations vary depending on the size and specific location of the malformation. Some lymphatic malformations can be massive. Lymphatic malformations, regardless of size, can potentially cause functional impairment of nearby structures or organs and disfigurement of affected areas. Lymphatic malformations are not cancerous and there is no known risk of malignant transformation [1]. The exact cause of lymphatic malformations is unknown. Lymphatic malformations

result from abnormalities in the development of the lymphatic vascular system during embryonic growth. In a large number of patients, the lymphatic malformations are positive for an activating mutation in the PIK3CA gene [2]. Lymphatic malformations affect males and females in equal numbers. Most lymphatic malformations are evident at birth or within two years. However, in some cases lymphatic malformations may not become apparent until adulthood. The exact prevalence of lymphatic malformations in the general population is unknown, but is thought to be 1:4000 live births [3].

Case Report

B.V., male, was born at term (38 weeks) after first pregnancy which was complicated by Pityriasis rosea. The lymphatic malformation was found at 24 week during ultrasound investigation. This baby presented normal auxological parameters at birth (weight 3905 g (50th centile), length 49 cm (50th centile), head circumference 34cm (5–10thcentile), chest circumference 48 cm because of lymphangioma. The patient had respiratory problems as giant lymphatic malformation compressed child's chest. Clinical examination of the swelling revealed a soft, cystic, tense, non-tender swelling which measured in length – 15cm and in width-20 cm, which occupied right side of chest, and extended to the right shoulder, at the same time it involved left upper limb. It also displaced the right and left axillary areas. Diameter of right lumps is around 2cm, size of left lumps is about 1cm. Fluctuation of both bulges was noted. It is significant to note that the structure, size and localization of this phenomenon are not typical for lymphangioma malformation. The mother and father were aged 17 and 22 years respectively at the time of conception. The baby cried immediately after birth, his Apgar score was 7–8 points. He was admitted to the NICU for respiratory distress and hyperbilirubinemia. After intravenous infusion of glucose with electrolytes and respiratory therapy, his condition stabilized. He was admitted in pediatric department in 2 days. On examination in our department, we observed some unusual peculiarities in this case of lymphatic malformation. The karyotype was a normal 46, XY. Coagulation profile demonstrated hypercoagulation for three weeks. The other samples of blood tests did not show any abnormalities. The result of tests on TORCH infections: Toxoplasma, Rubella, Cytomegalovirus, Herpes simplex virus were negative. Serum tests for hepatitis B, C, HIV and syphilis, tuberculosis were negative. A histopathology examination of biopsy material confirmed the diagnosis of a cystic lymphangioma. This swelling spread to the nearby structures of body thus computed tomography scans and magnetic resonance imaging were used for a better understanding of the anatomy and adjacent vital structures. Needle aspiration was done and there was no reduction in the size of swelling. Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) of upper limbs and

chest: on the right side of chest and right shoulder a multicystic mass was found which contains both micro- and macrocysts. The cysts contain fluid levels. Although neighboring anatomic structures were compressed due to the mass effect of the lesion. It significantly changes the architectonic of vessels and nerves of this region. On the left side of chest and upper shoulder a microcystic mass was located. There was no considerable compression effect.

CT scan of brain: all structures of brain are without deformations and malformations. Bone structures of skull and brine are normal. Echocardiography proved congenital heart disease (ventricular septal defect). No malformations were present in other organs on ultrasound investigations. Neurologist, surgeon, oncologist, ophthalmologist, audiologist, immunologist, geneticist and cardiologist checked up this patient. Surgeon diagnosed congenital bilateral clubfoot additionally. Any abnormalities in vision or hearing were not found. After treatment, the child's condition improved and stabilized. Patient was discharged from hospital with the further medical supervision from a local surgeon. Then this child at three months was admitted into surgical department with complaint of increased temperature, dyspnea, a progressive increasing swelling on right side of chest from 1 to 7 ribs, which was there since birth. His case history showed that needle aspiration was done after 2 months and evacuated 200 ml lymphatic liquid. Child was discharged from hospital in stable condition. Surgeon recommended putting elastic bandage on lymphoma every day and taught parents to do this. Clinical examination of the swelling revealed a soft, cystic, tense, swelling, which occupied right side of chest, and extended to the right arm, at the same time it involved left upper limb. Skin under lymphangioma became crimson and cyanotic. Regions of desquamation around body were detected. Other systemic examinations and complex laboratory investigations show secondary thrombotic microangiopathy. A histopathology examination of biopsy material confirmed the diagnosis of a cystic lymphangioma. He was transferred to resuscitation department because his condition was unstable and was getting worse due to multiple organ dysfunction syndrome because of tissue compression around lymphatic malformation and sepsis. In spite of intensive therapy and cardiopulmonary resuscitation the child died.

After autopsy clinical diagnosis was proved by histological conclusion: cavernocystical hemlymphangioma with anterior-lateral-posterior localization on the right side of the chest and right shoulder, which was complicated by blood circulation problems, secondary thrombotic microangiopathy and renal failure. This led to child's death. A cytological and morphological description of lymphangioma: right anterior (9–10 sm), lateral (8–9 sm), posterior (8–10 sm) scapular area and right shoulder (diameter 7 sm) have a brown-red area with jagged and clear border. On the left anterior surface of chest and left shoulder there was a growth.

Cytological characteristic: a formation is located in hypoderm and spreads into transverse muscular tissue. It presents a great number of cavities with heterogeneous endothelial lining; some were empty spaces, others were filled with blood, leukocyte and lymphocyte. The cavities were divided with edematose septa containing hemorrhages and necrosis.

After analyzing clinical symptoms, results of examinations and hystopatological conclusion, we came to conclusion that this case can be Kasabach-Merritt phenomenon (KMP). It is a rare condition associated with a coagulopathy including features such as profound thrombocytopenia, hypofibrinogenemia, and anemia. Two unusual vascular tumors, kaposiform hemangioendotheliomas in association with lymphatic-like vessels and tufted angiomas, can accompany this phenomenon. The condition can be life threatening with the risk of bleeding and progression to disseminated intravascular coagulopathy.

General Discussion

Our interdisciplinary team decided that this case can be unique example of atypical form Kasabach-Merritt phenomenon. Initially a vascular lesion is spotted on the skin. It can be firm, indurated or purpuric [4]. Around the lesion there can be areas of petechiae which can also appear on other parts of the body. If the vascular lesion is internal, these petechiae can be observed on the skin. There can be bruising and spontaneous bleeding. These tumors are not hemangiomas. The areas where the tumors like these can develop include the extremities, chest, neck, abdomen and pelvis. They spread across tissue plans and can be aggravated by interventions, infection and trauma. The tumors with KMP that are internal, for example in the pleural or retroperitoneum, can cause significant morbidity and mortality which is the result of bleeding [5]. Our patient death because of DIC and bleeding. It is unknown what causes the Kasabach-Merritt phenomenon. Sequestration or trapping of platelets into the tumor is thought to lead to it. These tumors consist of abnormal endothelial cells (spindle cells) and lymphatic malformation. It is unclear why the KMP occurs and whether it is caused by the spindle cells or the lymphatic component [6]. Coagulopathies with low platelet counts and other coagulation proteins resulting from large malformations such as venous or venous lymphatic lesions and multiple lesions are not Kasabach-Merritt phenomenon. In the past the infrequent vascular tumors associated with Kasabach-Merritt phenomenon were misdiagnosed as hemangiomas. Hemangioma is a benign tumor with endothelial proliferation. They are not present at birth but proliferate and grow over a 4 to 6 month period of time with subsequent stabilization and involution. Hemangiomas are not associated with any coagulopathy or thrombocytopenia [7]. Among others mistakenly diagnosed as Kasabach-Merritt phenomenon are vascular tumors and malformations with low platelets. There is no known standard therapy

for Kasabach-Merritt phenomenon. Medical management includes corticosteroids, interferon, chemotherapeutic agents such as vincristine, aspirin, and antiplatelet drugs such as Ticlopidine. Sometimes a combination of medications is used. Other adjuvant therapies include interventional embolization. If the lesion can be surgically removed that is the treatment of choice. Patients diagnosed with these conditions need to be treated at multidisciplinary vascular anomaly centers. Furthermore, if we know about atypical form Kasabach-Merritt syndrome the management and treatment of this child would be in another way. So this article add new information to this phenomenon which never have been described before in literature and will be useful for different medical specialties.

Conclusion

The diagnosis of Kasabach-Merritt phenomenon is based on the diagnosis of kaposiform hemangioendothelioma/tufted angioma and the coagulopathy as noted above. If this diagnosis is suspected blood work including a CBC with differential and platelets, fibrinogen, D-dimer, PT, and PTT should be ordered. The best imaging modality to assess the extent of the lesion is an MRI with contrast. A biopsy will confirm the diagnosis. However, in our practice, biopsy and MRI were not informative for clarifying diagnose. Coagulopathy and others blood problems were demonstrated after surgical treatment. Therefore, when child was in a neonatal period swelling had features similar to limfangioma but after surgical treatment condition of tumor completely changed. Autopsy results proved that huge lymphatic malformation was Kasabach-Merritt phenomenon.

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THE DETECTION OF SPEECH DISORDERS USING ELECTROENCEPHALOGRAPHY MARKERS IN PREMATURE BABIES

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Premature infants are at risk of delayed expressive and receptive speech compared to other children. The development of early diagnostic algorithms for speech disorders in premature children is an urgent problem that requires detailed research. The purpose of this work is to identify the EEG features in children with speech disorders for early diagnosis and treatment. The EEG of children with expressive speech disorders showed the following features: predominance of alpha-like activity, kate waves, and vertex sharp potentials. EEG changes in children with receptive speech disorders demonstrated the following bioelectric characteristics: desynchronization of the theta rhythm, frontal asymmetry of the alpha rhythm, and predominance of the high-frequency beta rhythm in the occipital regions. Our research focuses on automating early diagnosis and dynamic monitoring during therapy, as well as predicting and correcting long-term consequences through rehabilitation measures.

Keywords: *speech development disorders, electroencephalography, rehabilitation, neural networks*

According to a report by UNICEF, the number of children with disabilities worldwide was estimated at almost 240 million, with the largest and most diverse group consisting of children with mental and speech delays [1]. According to the World Health Organization, approximately 5% of children worldwide suffer from speech and language disorders [2]. Premature babies are at risk of developing speech problems. These children may have difficulty understanding words and phrases, reduced ability to speak, and underdeveloped phonemic perception and other language skills. Premature babies may also have pronunciation issues, limited vocabulary,

and difficulty forming grammatically correct sentences [3]. Diagnostic methods for these disorders are not sufficiently developed, and the clinical manifestations are variable, so timely diagnosis and rehabilitation are not carried out, which leads to a deterioration in the child's quality of life and socialization. The development of early diagnostic algorithms for speech disorders in children is an urgent problem that requires detailed research.

The purpose of this work is to identify the features of the bioelectric activity of the brain in children with speech disorders for early diagnosis.

Materials and methods

The main study was conducted on the basis of the Alushta Central City Hospital. The study involved 300 premature children aged 6 years with specific language development disorder. The number of girls (190, 63.3%) exceeded the number of boys (110, 36.7%). The children were examined using general clinical, neurological, and instrumental methods. EEG registration, processing, and analysis were carried out using a conventional method using an automated system consisting of electroencephalograph (Neurosoft) and a personal computer. EEG potentials were recorded monopolarly from frontal (F3, F4, Fz), central (C3, C4, Cz), parietal (P3, P4, Pz), temporal (T3, T4), and occipital (O1, O2) locations using the 10–20 system. The reference electrode was a combined contact attached to the earlobes. The digitization frequency of the EEG signals was selected to be average for the studied age of children – 250 Hz. The EEG was recorded in children with open eyes in a state of motor rest. For processing, EEG segments without artifacts were taken, which were divided into epochs of 2.56 s. The sample included EEG containing a number of segments with a total duration of at least 30 seconds [4]. The MacArthur Early Language and Communication Development Inventory helped identify speech disorders in children. The studies were conducted in accordance with the international moral and ethical standards and provisions of the International Code of Medical Ethics, the Good Laboratory Practice [5].

Results

In the study, specific speech deviations were distributed in the following ratios by the group of speech disorders: expressive speech disorder — 130 patients (43.3%), receptive speech disorder — 100 examined (33.4%), specific speech articulation disorder was observed in 70 children (23.3%). After the analysis of the data obtained, the following EEG changes were allocated for each type of specific speech disorder.

On the EEG, children with expressive speech disorders showed the following features: predominance of alpha-like activity, kali-wave and vertex sharp potentials. Alpha-like activity — mu rhythm with a frequency of 13 ± 0.5 Hz, an amplitude of 60.5 ± 0.5 μ V was noted in all children with expressive speech delay. Mu rhythm was

recorded in predominantly frontal and temporal areas and was suppressed during photostimulation. It should be noted that the prevalence of slow-wave activity in the delta range in the anterior regions of the brain was observed in 60 (20%) of the examined children, compared to the age-related norm. These nonspecific changes may be associated with possible synaptic disorders in cortical neurons. In 40 (12.3%) children, there was a predominance of 5.5 ± 0.5 Hz, 50.5 ± 0.5 μ V amplitude waves recorded from the central and temporal regions, which had a pronounced monophasic character. In 30 (10%) of the examined children, there were changes in the form of vertex sharp potentials with a frequency of 7.5 ± 0.5 Hz and an amplitude of 70.5 ± 0.5 μ V, which were detected in the frontal and parietal regions.

The EEG changes in the examined children with receptive speech disorders demonstrated the following characteristics: desynchronization of the theta rhythm, frontal asymmetry of the alpha rhythm, and a predominance of high-frequency beta rhythm in the occipital regions. In children with receptive speech disorders, specific EEG features were identified, which were clinically manifested by impaired understanding of speech utterances and behavioral deviations, despite normal hearing, vision, and intact intelligence.

In 60 (20%) of the examined children, the theta rhythm was represented by a diffuse increase in the frontal and central regions with a frequency of 6.5 ± 0.5 Hz and an amplitude of 100.5 ± 0.5 μ V. 30 (10%) children showed frontal asymmetry of the alpha rhythm, which manifested itself as a difference in the frequency and amplitude of the alpha rhythm between the left (7.5 ± 0.5 Hz and 60.5 ± 0.5 μ V) and right (8.5 ± 0.5 Hz and 70.5 ± 0.5 μ V) cerebral hemispheres by $65.5\pm 0.5\%$, with an average alpha rhythm activity index of $30.5\pm 0.5\%$. In 10 (3%) children, there was a predominance of high-frequency beta rhythm (35.5 ± 0.5 Hz and 3.5 ± 0.5 μ V) in the occipital regions, which increased in amplitude (45.5 ± 0.5 Hz) and frequency (4.5 ± 0.5 μ V) after the photostimulation test.

In 70 (23.3%) of the examined children with speech disorders associated with specific changes in the articulatory apparatus, there was a diffuse predominance of a low-frequency beta rhythm (frequency of 15.5 ± 0.5 Hz and amplitude of 35.5 ± 0.5 μ V) with the acquisition of an alpha-like rhythmic sinusoidal pattern in the frontal and temporal regions. It is particularly noteworthy that there is an asymmetry between the hemispheres in terms of amplitude of more than $75.5\pm 0.5\%$, which increases during photostimulation and persists for a long time after the test.

It is important not only to identify speech delay, but also to perform a differential diagnosis to determine whether the delay is benign (tempo) or pathological, requiring urgent speech therapy and medication. This can be achieved using the EEG markers that we identified in our study. After diagnosing speech development disorders in premature infants, the following areas of correction are recommended: speech development, development of fine and gross motor skills, stimulation of

communication. Speech development included classes with a speech therapist-defectologist, which develop speech from the first level of general speech underdevelopment to the second and third. Development of fine and gross motor skills for premature children are significantly important since the speech center is located close to the hand movement center in the brain.

Conclusion

The main directions of our developments based on the following EEG characteristics: automation of early diagnosis and dynamic monitoring against the background of the carried out therapy, forecasting the consequences of speech disorders and their correction through abilitation and rehabilitation measures. In premature infants with expressive speech disorders, the following EEG markers were noted: prevalence of alpha-like activity, kalitichnyh waves and vertex acute potentials. The following EEG changes were observed in children with receptive speech disorders: desynchronization of the theta rhythm, frontal asymmetry of the alpha rhythm, and predominance of high-frequency beta rhythm in the occipital regions. It should be noted that speech delay in premature infants requires comprehensive treatment, which includes diagnosis, medication, and speech therapy. Prematurity negatively affects speech development due to the lack of time for the formation of neural connections and interaction with the world. Early diagnosis is essential for timely correction and treatment of speech disorders in premature infants.

Currently, in pediatrics, the EEG does not have unified normative tables of the main signal parameters and graph elements, so the data set among patients with speech disorders will be continued to form the corresponding normative indicators. It should be remembered about the limitation of the operation of neural networks, which is that not all EEG phenomena can be classified in automatic mode, so it is advisable not to fully automate the process of EEG analysis, but to select EEG markers intended for further viewing by an expert and verification of the diagnosis.

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EARLY DIAGNOSTICS OF THE ETIOLOGY OF UVEITIS IN PATIENTS OVER 18 YEARS OLD

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Abstract. *The article describes in detail a method for early diagnosis of the etiology of uveitis in patients older than 18 years. In a patient older than 18 years with inflammatory pathology of the vascular tunic of the eye, venous blood is drawn for complete blood count analysis. Based on the leukogram analysis, integral hematological indices are calculated as follows: the blood leukocyte shift index (CMV) = (eosinophils% + basophils% + band neutrophils% + segmented neutrophils% + myelocytes% + metamyelocytes%) / (monocytes% + lymphocytes%); the viral infection marker (MHV) = neutrophils% / monocytes%; the neutrophil-to-lymphocyte ratio index (EBV) = neutrophils% / lymphocytes%; adapted platelet-to-lymphocyte ratio index (TLA) = platelets (absolute count) / lymphocytes%; adapted systemic inflammatory response index (HSV) = neutrophils% × monocytes% / lymphocytes%; adapted systemic immune inflammation index (VZV) = neutrophils% × platelets (absolute count) / lymphocytes%, with values of CMV above 2.3; EBV above 3.0; TLA above 13.0; and HSV above 13; HSV levels above 794 indicate uveitis of bacterial etiology; with MHV indices above 6.02; EBV below 2.64; TLA below 12.7; HSV ranging from 4.16 to 12.0; HSV levels up to 793 indicate uveitis of herpetic etiology, requiring antiviral therapy.*

Keywords: *uveitis, early diagnosis, etiology, viral, bacterial*

Relevance

Inflammation of the vascular layer of the eyeball – uveitis – is one of the leading causes of ophthalmological complications in the working-age population [1,2,3]. Several diagnostic methods are available for this pathology based on the localization of the pathological process (peripheral, generalized, posterior) and the presence of systemic involvement (tuberculosis, rheumatic diseases), but these methods are not designed for the early diagnosis of uveitis etiology regardless of the localization of the process [3,4,5].

The purpose of the study is to determine the early etiology of inflammatory pathology of the vascular membrane of the eyeball (bacterial or herpetic), regardless of the localization of the process, in patients over 18 years old at the outpatient stage, including the admission and diagnostic department, as well as specialized ophthalmological and infectious departments, to enable the timely initiation of empirical treatment, reduce unnecessary prescriptions of antibacterial drugs, and prevent antibiotic resistance.

Materials and Methods: Integral hematological indices were determined based on the analysis of 115 patients diagnosed with uveitis who were treated at the adult ophthalmology department of the State Budgetary Healthcare Institution of the Tyumen Region 'Regional Clinical Hospital No. 2' in Tyumen from 2020 to 2024. Of these, 85 patients had a confirmed non-viral etiology of the pathological process (group 1), and 30 patients had confirmed herpetic infection caused by herpes simplex virus types 1 and 2, IgM 2.3 [1,2:3,0] (group 2). Venous blood is collected from the patient to perform a complete blood count, and based on the leukogram results, the aforementioned integral indices of peripheral blood are calculated.

Formulas for calculating integral blood indices are taken from sources (D. O. Ivanov, N. P. Shabalov, N. N. Shabalova et al. Leukocyte indices of cellular reactivity as an indicator of hypo- and hyperergic variants of neonatal sepsis (Electronic resource: access mode <http://www.medlinks.ru/article.php?sid=22330>); Speransky I. I., Samoylenko G. E., Lobacheva M. V. Complete blood count — have all its capabilities been exhausted? Integral intoxication indices as criteria for assessing the severity of endogenous intoxication, its complications, and the effectiveness of treatment administered // Health of Ukraine. — 2009. No.6 (19). pp. 51–57.)). However, to optimize the use of formulas, this study employs only one parameter of the complete blood count in absolute numbers — platelets, while leukogram parameters are entered as percentages for calculation convenience.

In cases of inflammatory pathology of the vascular tunic of the eyeball in adults over 18 years old, determining the integral hematological indices: $CMV = (\text{eosinophils}\% + \text{basophils}\% + \text{band neutrophils}\% + \text{segmented neutrophils}\% + \text{myelocytes}\% + \text{metamyelocytes}\%) / (\text{monocytes}\% + \text{lymphocytes}\%)$; $MHV = \text{neutrophils}\% / \text{monocytes}\%$; $EBV = \text{neutrophils}\% / \text{lymphocytes}\%$; $TLA = \text{platelets}$

(absolute count) / lymphocytes%; HSV = neutrophil percentage \times monocyte percentage / lymphocyte percentage; VZV = neutrophil percentage \times platelet count (absolute numbers) / lymphocyte percentage.

Results and discussion

The integral index indicators for group 1 / group 2 are as follows: MHV 3.0 [1.5:4.7] / 6.59 [4.7:9.6]; CMV 2.7 [2.3:3.4] / 1.4 [0.8–2.27]; EBV 4.5 [3.0:5.26] / 1.55 [0.76–2.64]; TLA 15.6 [13.0:21.6] / 9.0 [3.92–12.56]; HSV 19.9 [13.0:48.2] / 8.53 [4.16:12.9]; VZV 1160.1 [794:1930.5] / 503.74 [156:796.8].

At ISL values above 2.3; EBV above 3.0; TLA above 13.0; HSV above 13.0; VZV above 794 is diagnosed as uveitis of bacterial etiology. At MHV values above 6.02; EBV below 2.64; TLA below 12.7; HSV from 4.16 to 12.0; VZV up to 793, uveitis of herpetic etiology is diagnosed.

Example 1

Patient G. I.S., male, 49 years old.

He was hospitalized from 01.09.2024 to 11.09.2024.

Complaints of pain in the left eye, floaters, and photophobia. The history indicates that the complaints appeared about a week ago for the first time. He did not seek medical assistance. After the pain in the eye increased, he presented to the admission department of GBUZ TO “OKB No. 2” on 01.09.2024. He was hospitalized in the ophthalmology department for urgent reasons. Medical history: stage 2 hypertensive disease, stage 1 chronic heart failure, continuously on antihypertensive therapy. Denies diabetes mellitus, tuberculosis, hepatitis, and venereal diseases. Allergic history unremarkable according to the patient. Objective status. General condition: satisfactory. Skin of physiological coloration, clean. Breathing vesicular, no wheezing. Blood pressure on the right arm 120/80 mmHg, on the left arm 120/80 mmHg. Heart sounds clear, rhythmic. The abdomen is soft and painless. Stool is of normal color. Diuresis is adequate. Local status: Visual acuity OD = 1.0, OS = counting fingers at face distance. OD — calm. IOP 15 mmHg. Cornea is transparent, anterior chamber of medium depth, aqueous is clear, pupil medium-wide, reactive, fundus reflex pink. OS — mixed injection of the globe. IOP 26 mmHg, pronounced ciliary tenderness. Multiple small ill-defined precipitates on the corneal endothelium. The anterior chamber is of moderate depth; at its base, there is exudate with a level up to 2 mm and flakes in the aqueous humor. The iris is edematous, the pupil is narrow, with a circular posterior synechia. Strands of exudate in the pupil. The fundus reflex is absent. Diagnosis: Acute iridocyclitis of the left eye of unknown etiology, ocular hypertension. A complete blood count, ELISA for herpes simplex virus (HSV) types 1 and 2, and cytomegalovirus (CMV) have been ordered. Complete blood count dated 01.09.2024: Platelets — 303x10⁹/l; Hematocrit — 46%; Erythrocytes — 5x10¹²/l; Hemoglobin — 156 g/l; Leukocytes — 12x10⁹/l;

Eosinophils — 1.0%; Lymphocytes — 15%; Monocytes — 4%; Segmented neutrophils — 78%; Band neutrophils — 2%.

The values of integral hematological indices were determined by the formulas: $CMV = (1\% + 0\% + 2\% + 78\%) / (4\% + 15\%) = 4.26$; $EBV = 80\% / 15\% = 7.2$; $TLA = 303 / 15\% = 25.25$; $HSV = 80\% \times 4\% / 15\% = 21.33$; $VZV = 80\% \times 303 / 15\% = 2020$. According to the declared method, when the indices CMV exceed 2.3; EBV exceed 3.0; TLA exceed 13.0; and HSV exceed 13; VZV above 794 is diagnosed as uveitis of bacterial etiology.

ELISA results dated September 10, 2024. Determination of class M antibodies to herpes simplex virus (HSV) types 1 and 2 — negative.

Thus, the presented clinical case indicates that in a 49-year-old patient, with values CMV 4.26; EBV 7.2; TLA 25.25; HSV 21.33; and VZV 20.20, uveitis of bacterial etiology is diagnosed, necessitating the initiation of antibacterial therapy.

Example 2

Female patient G.A.K., 64 years old.

Hospitalized from October 16, 2024, to October 26, 2024.

Complaints of redness, pain, and decreased vision in the left eye. The medical history indicates that the complaints began 4 days prior; she had not sought medical care or undergone treatment. On October 16, 2024, she independently presented to the emergency department of the State Budgetary Healthcare Institution of the Tula Region 'Regional Clinical Hospital No. 2' and was admitted to the ophthalmology department on urgent indications. Anamnesis vitae: according to the patient's report, rarely experiences acute respiratory infections; among chronic diseases, has arterial hypertension, pharmacologically compensated. Denies tuberculosis, hepatitis, and venereal diseases. Allergic history is unremarkable. Objective examination findings. General condition satisfactory. Skin of physiological coloration, clean. Vesicular breath sounds, no rales. Heart rate 68 beats per minute. Blood pressure in the right arm 120/80 mmHg. Blood pressure in the left arm 120/80 mmHg. Heart tones clear, rhythmic. Abdomen soft, non-tender. Stool formed, normal color. Urination free. Diuresis sufficient. Local status: Visual acuity OD = 1.0, OS = counting fingers at face. OD — calm. Intraocular pressure normal. Cornea transparent, anterior chamber of medium depth, aqueous humor clear, pupil moderately dilated, mobile, fundus reflex pink. OS — mixed injection of the eyeball, Tp within normal limits, moderate ciliary tenderness. Numerous precipitates on the corneal endothelium, anterior chamber of medium depth, aqueous humor opalescent, iris edematous. Pupil narrow, slow pupillary light reflex. Fundus reflex pink, diminished. Fundus exhibits flare. Diagnosis: Acute iridocyclitis of the left eye of unknown etiology. A complete blood count, ELISA for herpes simplex virus (HSV) types 1 and 2, and cytomegalovirus (CMV) have been ordered. Clinical blood test dated 16.10.2024: Platelets — $313 \times 10^9/L$; Hematocrit — 38%; Erythrocytes — $4.9 \times 10^{12}/L$;

Hemoglobin – 123 g/L; Leukocytes — 12.7x10⁹/L; Eosinophils — 1%; Basophils — 1%; Lymphocytes — 45%; Monocytes — 7%; Segmented neutrophils — 46%; Band neutrophils — 0. Integral hematological indices were calculated using the formulas: MHV = 46% / 7% = 6.43; EBV = 46% / 45% = 1.02; TLA = 313 / 45% = 6.96; HSV = 46% × 7% / 45% = 7.16; VZV = 46% × 313 / 45% = 319.96. According to the declared method, when MHV values are above 6.02, EBV below 2.64, TLA below 12.7, and HSV ranges from 4.16 to 12.0; and VZV up to 793, uveitis of herpetic etiology is diagnosed, indicating the necessity of antiviral therapy in treatment.

ELISA results dated 25.10.2024. Detection of class M antibodies to herpes simplex virus (HSV) types 1 and 2 — positive (1.4).

Thus, the presented clinical case demonstrates that in a 64-year-old patient, with MHV values above 6.02; EBV below 2.64; TLA below 12.7; and HSV ranging from 4.16 to 12.0; and VZV up to 793, uveitis of herpetic etiology is diagnosed, thereby necessitating empirical antiviral therapy upon admission without waiting for ELISA results.

Conclusion

For the diagnosis of herpesvirus infections in patients with uveitis, the method of immunofluorescent blood analysis is used, which involves time delays (in some healthcare facilities, issuing results takes from 2 up to 7–10 days) and imposes a financial burden both on the patient and the healthcare system as a whole. At present, the method for early diagnosis of the etiology of uveitis in patients over 18 years old has sufficient grounds for clinical application in practical healthcare (simplicity, low cost, accessibility). Moreover, a crucial aspect of the proposed method is the ability for early diagnosis of the etiology of the pathological process during outpatient visits at polyclinic settings, at the time of admission to the emergency diagnostic department, as well as in specialized infectious and ophthalmological departments of round-the-clock inpatient facilities. The accessibility of the method (complete blood count is included in the scope of care under compulsory medical insurance) and its informativeness enable the timely initiation of adequate empirical antibacterial or antiherpetic therapy to improve disease outcomes, aiming to prevent uveal complications and chronic progression of the process, without having to wait, sometimes for up to two weeks, for the costly results of ELISA.

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FUNDAMENTALS OF PERSONNEL POLICY IN THE AGRICULTURAL SECTOR OF THE RUSSIAN ECONOMY

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Abstract. *This article examines the fundamental principles and current challenges of personnel policy in the agricultural sector of the Russian economy. Based on official data from the Ministry of Agriculture and the Federal State Statistics Service, the authors analyze the scale of labor shortage in the agro-industrial complex, which amounts to 130–160 thousand specialists annually. The study identifies key factors influencing the formation of human resources potential, including demographic trends in rural areas, wage disparities between agricultural and industrial sectors, and the transformation of qualification requirements amid digitalization. The article presents results of the analysis of federal programs «Personnel in the Agro-Industrial Complex» and «Agroprofessionalitet» implemented within the framework of the national project «Technological Support for Food Security». The authors conclude that effective personnel policy requires an integrated approach combining early career guidance, modernization of professional education, targeted training mechanisms, and improvement of rural social infrastructure.*

Keywords: *personnel policy, agricultural sector, labor resources, agro-industrial complex, personnel shortage, targeted training, agricultural education, rural territories.*

The agricultural sector of the Russian economy faces strategic tasks set by the President of the Russian Federation: by 2030, it is necessary to increase agricultural production by 25% and export volumes by 1.5 times compared to 2021. Achieving these ambitious goals directly depends on the availability of qualified personnel capable of working with modern technologies and ensuring innovative development of the industry.

Personnel policy in the agricultural sector is a system of principles, methods, and mechanisms for the formation, development, and rational use of human resources in the agro-industrial complex. Its relevance is determined not only by the scale of current tasks but also by the critical state of the labor market in rural areas. According to the Ministry of Agriculture of the Russian Federation, about 6.4 million people are currently employed in the agro-industrial complex, and this number must be maintained while simultaneously increasing labor productivity.

The purpose of this study is to analyze the current state of personnel policy in the Russian agricultural sector, identify key problems, and evaluate the effectiveness of government measures aimed at providing the industry with qualified specialists. The research is based on official data from government bodies, statistical information, and analytical materials from scientific publications.

Analysis of statistical data indicates a critical shortage of personnel in the Russian agro-industrial complex. According to the Ministry of Agriculture, the annual need for new workers is 160 thousand people, of which 150 thousand is replacement demand (due to natural attrition of personnel) and 10 thousand is additional demand necessary for industry development in accordance with strategic objectives.

The Federal State Statistics Service confirms the severity of the problem: according to data for the second quarter of 2025, the need of medium and large businesses for employees in the Russian economy reached a record high since 2008, amounting to 7.6% of available jobs. The highest vacancy rate is observed precisely in ture – 13% of jobs remain unfilled, which is the maximum indicator among all sectors of the economy.

At the same time, various official sources provide different estimates of the absolute shortage. Data from the Ministry of Agriculture indicate a deficit of about 160 thousand people, while according to information published by the industry portal «Agrarian Science», the shortage of workers is estimated at 240 thousand. In January 2026, Prime Minister Mikhail Mishustin announced the need to attract more than 130 thousand new specialists annually to the agro-industrial complex. These discrepancies may be due to different calculation methodologies, but the main conclusion remains unchanged: the industry is experiencing an acute shortage of personnel.

The situation is aggravated by demographic factors. Research by scientists from the Higher School of Economics shows that rural areas are characterized by depopulation processes, population aging, and migration outflow, which leads to

a reduction in labor resources in agriculture. The lack of developed social infrastructure, including healthcare, education, and cultural institutions, reduces the attractiveness of living and working in rural areas, especially for young people.

The analysis allowed us to identify several systemic problems of personnel policy in the agricultural sector.

First, there is a significant wage gap compared to other sectors of the economy. According to research, the average offered salary in agriculture at the end of 2024 was 60.8 thousand rubles for milkmaids and 70.2 thousand rubles for livestock specialists. For comparison, the average offered salary in industry was 81.3 thousand rubles, which is 35% higher than in agriculture. Although the growth rate of wages in the agricultural sector (36% per year) outpaces industrial dynamics (26%), maintaining such a pace will require at least three years to eliminate the gap.

Second, there is a structural imbalance between the training of specialists and the real needs of production. The rapid digitalization of agriculture and the introduction of precision farming technologies require personnel with fundamentally new competencies. Agriculture Minister Oksana Lut notes that it is necessary to «free people from routine work and engage them in more intellectual work» through digitalization. However, the vocational education system does not always keep up with technological changes, training specialists according to outdated standards.

Third, there is a territorial unevenness in the provision of personnel. Agricultural production is concentrated in regions with different demographic situations and levels of socio-economic development, which requires a differentiated approach to personnel policy [3].

In response to the identified challenges, the Government of the Russian Federation is implementing a set of measures aimed at providing the agro-industrial complex with qualified personnel. The key instrument is the federal project «Personnel in the Agro-Industrial Complex», included in the national project «Technological Support for Food Security».

An important direction is the creation of a unified system for training specialists, starting from school. In 2025, more than a thousand agro-technological classes were created in the country, and in the near future it is planned to double their number. Such classes are designed to interest schoolchildren in agricultural professions at the stage of obtaining secondary education, forming a conscious choice of future profession.

In the vocational education system, the «Agroprofessionalitet» project has been launched since 2026. Within its framework, the Ministry of Agriculture selected 18 projects from 13 regions, developed jointly with agribusiness. Winning colleges receive grants for updating the material and technical base, purchasing modern equipment and software. This mechanism is designed to ensure that the training of mid-level specialists meets the real needs of employers.

For higher education, priority is given to expanding targeted training mechanisms and actively involving employers in the educational process. According to the Government's decision, subsidies are provided for targeted training of students of agricultural universities, expenses for their accommodation, as well as incentive payments to specialists of key projects in the agro-industrial complex.

In September 2025, by Order of the Government of the Russian Federation No. 2411-r, more than 1.3 billion rubles were additionally allocated to 24 regions that declared the need for funding to implement programs to improve the personnel security of agro-industrial complex enterprises. The list of recipients includes Altai, Stavropol, Khabarovsk Territories, Amur, Volgograd, Kaliningrad, Leningrad, Lipetsk, Nizhny Novgorod, Novgorod, Omsk, Smolensk, Tver, Tomsk, Chelyabinsk, Yaroslavl Regions, as well as Kabardino-Balkaria, Bashkortostan, Karelia, Tatarstan, Udmurtia, Mari El and Sakha (Yakutia). These funds are directed to support targeted training and incentive payments to specialists.

Based on the analysis, it is possible to identify key directions for improving personnel policy in the agricultural sector of Russia.

A strategic priority should be increasing the attractiveness of living in rural areas. Without solving the infrastructure problem, any measures for personnel training will be insufficient, since graduates will not remain to work in the countryside. It is necessary to develop housing construction, healthcare, education, and transport accessibility [4].

Equally important is the synchronization of personnel training with the real needs of employers. The «Agroprofessionalitet» mechanism, which involves business participation in the development of educational programs and updating the material base of colleges, has proven itself positively and requires further scaling.

It is necessary to continue work on reducing the wage gap between agriculture and other sectors. The existing positive dynamics (wage growth by 36% per year) must be maintained, but it is also important to develop a system of non-material incentives: providing service housing, social guarantees, opportunities for professional growth [2].

Digitalization of agriculture should be accompanied by the creation of a system of continuous professional education that allows workers to acquire new competencies. This will solve two problems: increasing labor productivity and making agricultural labor more attractive to young people accustomed to working with digital technologies.

The study allows us to draw the following conclusions. The personnel policy in the agricultural sector of the Russian economy is being formed in conditions of an acute shortage of labor resources. The annual need of the agro-industrial complex for new specialists, according to various estimates, ranges from 130 to 160 thousand people. The situation is complicated by demographic problems of rural areas, lower

wages compared to other industries, and the increasing requirements for personnel qualifications due to digitalization [5].

The Government of the Russian Federation is implementing a set of measures to address the personnel problem, including the federal project «Personnel in the Agro-Industrial Complex» and the «Agroprofessionalitet» system. More than 1.3 billion rubles have been allocated for the implementation of these programs in 2025. A unified system of personnel training is being formed, including pre-professional training in agro-technological classes, secondary vocational education within the framework of the new project, and higher education with an emphasis on targeted training.

The results of the analysis show that the most effective approach is an integrated personnel policy that combines educational, social, and economic measures. Promising directions include the development of rural infrastructure, reduction of wage disparities, creation of a system of continuous professional education, and active involvement of employers in the formation of educational programs [1].

The solution to the personnel problem will determine the possibility of achieving the strategic goals set for the agro-industrial complex to increase production and exports by 2030. Further research may be devoted to regional features of personnel policy and analysis of the effectiveness of specific support measures.

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THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THE IMPLEMENTATION OF AGRARIAN POLICY IN KRASNODAR KRAI

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Abstract. *The article presents a comprehensive analysis of the implementation of state agrarian policy in Krasnodar Krai – a leading agro-industrial region of the Russian Federation. It examines the target indicators of government programmes, the dynamics of agricultural production, and the level of state support and its impact on the economic efficiency of the agro-industrial complex (AIC). Particular attention is paid to regional specifics, including import substitution, the development of small-scale farming, and technical modernisation. The study identifies existing challenges and proposes directions for improving the efficiency of agrarian policy under conditions of sanctions restrictions and new economic challenges.*

Keywords: *agrarian policy, Krasnodar Krai, efficiency, state support, agro-industrial complex, subsidies, food security.*

The relevance of the research topic is determined by the key role of Krasnodar Krai in ensuring the country's food security. The region traditionally holds leading positions in the production of grain, sugar beet, sunflower, fruits and berries, as well as livestock products. In the context of geopolitical instability and the focus on import substitution, the effectiveness of regional agrarian policy becomes a determining factor not only for the economic growth of the federal subject, but also for the stability of the national food market.

The aim of this work is to assess the effectiveness of the implementation of agrarian policy in Krasnodar Krai based on an analysis of the dynamics of production indicators and state support measures, as well as to identify reserves for the further development of the sector.

The region's agrarian policy represents a system of economic, legal and social measures aimed at the sustainable development of agriculture and rural areas, ensuring the population with high-quality food, and supplying the processing industry with raw materials. The effectiveness of policy implementation is assessed through the ratio of achieved results (gross output, profitability, self-sufficiency level) to the resources expended (budget funds, administrative efforts).

In Krasnodar Krai, the main instrument for implementing agrarian policy is the state programme «Development of Agriculture and Regulation of Agricultural Products, Raw Materials and Food Markets». Within the framework of the programme, the following instruments are applied: subsidies, grant support, and market regulation.

Krasnodar Krai demonstrates steady growth in its agro-industrial complex, showing positive production dynamics year on year. The sector is developing progressively, successfully adapting to changing external economic conditions.

Crop production has traditionally been the foundation of the region's economy. Over the past few years, the harvest of grain and leguminous crops has been steadily increasing thanks to the expansion of sown areas, the introduction of new high-yielding varieties, and the intensification of production. This enables the region to maintain its leading position in the country and make a significant contribution to the national harvest.

In contrast, sugar beet production is subject to fluctuations, which is linked to market conditions and adjustments in the crop structure. Farmers redistribute acreage in favour of the most profitable crops for the current season and also take into account crop rotation requirements to preserve soil fertility.

The livestock sector also shows positive, albeit more moderate, dynamics. Live-stock numbers and meat production volumes are growing due to the modernisation of existing facilities and the opening of new farms, supported by regional programmes. The dairy sector is developing steadily, but its growth rate is constrained by the high cost of projects and their long payback periods, which necessitates continued state support measures.

Overall, the region's agro-industrial sector ensures a high level of food security: the region fully meets its own needs in all major food categories. At the same time, Kuban remains a key food supplier both to the domestic Russian market and to international markets, confirming its reputation as one of the most competitive agrarian regions in the country.

The volume of funding for the agro-industrial complex from budgets at all levels (federal and regional) remains significant. Annually, approximately 8–10 billion roubles are allocated to support the agro-industrial sector of Kuban.

The efficiency of budget funds utilisation can be assessed through the indicator of «output per rouble of support». In the region, this figure stands at around 100–120 roubles of gross output per 1 rouble of subsidies, which is a high indicator compared to the national average. The profitability of agricultural organisations (including subsidies) remains at the level of 20–25%, which enables expanded reproduction.

However, the analysis also reveals structural imbalances. The bulk of support (up to 70%) is traditionally directed towards crop production, while livestock farming – especially dairy farming – requires additional incentives to maintain growth rates.

A key indicator of the success of agrarian policy is investment activity in the region. Krasnodar Krai traditionally ranks among the top three leaders in terms of investment in fixed assets in agriculture. Over the past five years, the average annual inflow of investments into the region's agro-industrial complex has amounted to approximately 45–50 billion roubles. This has become possible thanks to the creation of a favourable investment climate: the introduction of an investment tax deduction mechanism and the provision of land plots without tenders for large-scale projects.

The effectiveness of policy implementation in the investment sphere is assessed through the multiplier effect. Each budget rouble invested in infrastructure development (gasification, water supply, land reclamation) attracts between 5 and 10 roubles of private investment. An example of successful policy implementation is the construction of large greenhouse complexes (more than 100 ha of protected ground introduced over three years) and dairy farms using the mechanism of preferential investment lending.

However, an analysis of the efficiency of budget funds utilisation reveals the problem of uneven distribution across the municipalities of the region. For instance, northern districts (Kushchevsky, Krylovsky, Pavlovsky), which have a strong raw material base, receive a significantly lower volume of support for processing development compared to suburban areas of Krasnodar and the Black Sea coast, where viticulture is actively developing. This indicates the need to adjust the distribution of subsidies in favour of creating full-cycle clusters in raw material areas.

Krasnodar Krai is a leader in establishing intensive orchards. Thanks to the regional programme for the development of horticulture and nursery production, the region establishes more than 1,5 thousand ha of new orchards annually, including intensive-type orchards. This enables an increase in the production of domestic apples and pears, replacing imported products. The effectiveness of this sub-programme is assessed as high, as the payback period for investments in intensive orchards occurs within 3–4 years [2].

Krasnodar Krai has more than 13 thousand peasant (farmer) households (PFH) and over 1 million personal subsidiary plots (PSP). The region's policy towards small-scale farming is implemented through grants and subsidies. Every year, dozens of farmers receive «Agrostartup» grants. The effectiveness of this initiative lies in the growth of marketability of small farms, the creation of new jobs in rural areas, and an increase in the production volumes of niche crops (vegetables, berries, greens) [3].

The level of technical equipment among Kuban farmers remains one of the best in the country. Energy supply per 100 ha of sown area is significantly higher than the national average. The machinery fleet renewal programme is implemented both through direct subsidies to machinery manufacturers and through preferential leasing. However, despite this, machinery wear and tear in some categories of farms reaches 50%, indicating the need to continue preferential lending programmes for the purchase of expensive import-substituting tractors and combines.

In the context of implementing the federal project «Export of Agro-Industrial Complex Products», Krasnodar Krai plays a flagship role. In the structure of Russian agro-exports, the share of Kuban products accounts for about 15%. The export base traditionally consists of grain crops (wheat, barley), oil and fat products (sunflower oil), as well as products of the food and processing industries [5].

The effectiveness of policy in this area is assessed not only by foreign exchange earnings but also by the diversification of supplies. Under conditions of sanctions pressure and logistical constraints, regional authorities, together with the federal government, promptly redirected export flows from the European direction to markets in the Middle East, North Africa (Egypt, Algeria, Saudi Arabia), and Southeast Asia. Support was provided in certifying products according to the standards of importing countries (halal, organic products), which helped maintain export volumes [1].

However, the analysis reveals insufficient effectiveness in promoting products with high added value. The share of processed products in the region's exports accounts for only about 35%, while the bulk consists of raw materials (grain). Recent policy has been aimed at correcting this imbalance by stimulating the construction of deep grain processing plants (production of lysine, gluten, amino acids) and oil processing facilities. The launch of such facilities will allow increasing export revenue per unit of grown raw material by 2–3 times, which will serve as a qualitative indicator of the effectiveness of agrarian policy.

Despite obvious successes, the analysis identifies a number of systemic problems that reduce the potential effectiveness of the implemented policy:

1. Price disparity. The rise in prices for fuel and lubricants (Fuels and Lubricants, FL), fertilisers, spare parts, and machinery outpaces the growth of purchase prices for agricultural products. This requires increased «emergency» support and offsets the effect of investment subsidies.

2. The procedure for obtaining subsidies and grants remains bureaucratised, which is especially acutely felt by small-scale farms that do not have accountants and lawyers on staff.

3. Personnel shortage.

4. Sanctions risks.

Despite the successes of import substitution, dependence on imported seed material (for certain crops — maize, sunflower, sugar beet) and breeding stock remains.

To improve the effectiveness of agrarian policy in Krasnodar Krai, the following measures should be implemented:

1. The region needs to accelerate the development of its own breeding base to reduce dependence on imported hybrids. Funding for scientific agricultural centres and experimental production farms is required.

2. Addressing the personnel shortage is impossible without improving the quality of life. It is necessary to synchronise agrarian policy with policies in the areas of housing construction, road development, schools, and rural primary healthcare units (FAPs -federal ambulatory posts) through integrated development programmes.

3. The introduction of digital platforms for submitting reports and applications for subsidies, as well as support for projects on precision farming and field digital twins, will help reduce costs and improve management efficiency.

In addition to current measures, the agrarian policy of Krasnodar Krai should focus on long-term strategic priorities aligned with the goals of the Food Security Doctrine of the Russian Federation and the new Strategy for Socio-Economic Development of the Region until 2030.

The first priority is the transition to organic and biologised farming. Under conditions of intensive use of chernozems, their degradation and a decrease in humus content are observed. The effectiveness of future policy will be measured not only by gross yields but also by the environmental friendliness index of production. It is necessary to encourage the adoption of biological methods of plant protection, green manure fallows, and resource-saving soil cultivation technologies.

The second priority is the deep digital transformation of agro-industrial complex (AIC) management. Establishing a unified digital platform for the AIC of Krasnodar Krai will enable real-time monitoring of budget funds flows, crop conditions, yield forecasting, and detection of improper land use. This will increase transparency in the sector and improve the targeting of support measures.

The third priority is the development of agricultural cooperation in marketing and processing. Currently, small-scale farming entities (peasant (farmer) households — PFH, personal subsidiary plots -PSP) produce a significant share of potatoes, vegetables, milk, and meat, but face marketing challenges due to the dominance of retail chains and the lack of modern storage facilities. Regional policy should encourage the creation of supply and marketing cooperatives and cooperative

markets (weekend fairs), which will increase the profitability of small agribusinesses without a multiple increase in budget expenditures.

The study of the effectiveness of agrarian policy implementation in Krasnodar Krai leads to the conclusion that the region demonstrates a balanced approach to managing the agro-industrial complex. Key target indicators of government programmes are being met, food independence has been ensured, and high export potential is being maintained. State support instruments –from credit subsidies to the grant system –have proven their effectiveness, delivering a multiplier effect for the region’s economy.

However, the analysis has identified systemic constraints, the neglect of which could lead to stagnation of the sector in the medium and long term. These include: a growing shortage of qualified personnel, high dependence on imported technologies in breeding and seed production, an imbalance in the export structure, with a predominance of raw materials.

Improving the effectiveness of agrarian policy in the new realities requires a shift from an extensive development model (more land, more fertilisers) to an intensive and innovative one. The key drivers of this transition should be: accelerated development of the region’s own breeding and genetic base to ensure technological sovereignty, digitalisation of all processes, synchronisation of agrarian policy with the spatial development policy for rural areas.

Only a comprehensive solution to production, social, and environmental challenges will enable Krasnodar Krai to maintain its status as Russia’s main breadbasket and ensure the country’s food security in the face of global challenges.

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MODELING AND INVESTIGATION OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF NEURAL NETWORK APPROACHES TO SOLVING COMBINATORIAL OPTIMIZATION PROBLEMS ON CENTRAL AND GRAPHICS PROCESSORS

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Abstract. *The article is devoted to investigating the effectiveness of an approach based on emulating homogeneous computing environments (HCE) on central and graphics processors for solving classical combinatorial optimization problems such as the traveling salesman problem and similar production planning tasks. Two groups of neural network models are considered: Hopfield networks and Kohonen self-organizing maps. The results of a comparative analysis of these methods' efficiency across different types of computational architectures are presented, demonstrating the advantages of using graphic processing units (GPUs) in handling high-dimensional complex routing problems. It is proposed to use the Compute Unified Device Architecture (CUDA) technology to increase data processing speed and reduce time costs when searching for optimal routes.*

Keywords: *neural networks, CUDA technology, traveling salesman problem, production scheduling, route optimization, Hopfield model, Kohonen map.*

Introduction

Combinatorial optimization problems play a key role in logistics, manufacturing, and the management of complex technical systems. A classical example of such a problem is the traveling salesman problem, which requires minimizing the total length of a route passing through a set of nodes. Similar problems also arise in production management, where it is necessary to plan the most efficient sequence of job switches on equipment.

The effectiveness of modern methods for solving such problems is often associated with the ability to rapidly process large volumes of data and the scalability of the computational resources employed. The utilization of parallel data processing technologies provided by graphics processing units (GPUs) leads to

a significant reduction in the time required to find an optimal solution compared to traditional approaches using central processing units (CPUs).

This article is devoted to investigating the capabilities and advantages of employing homogeneous computing environments (HCE) based on Hopfield neural networks and Kohonen maps for solving combinatorial optimization problems. The aim of this study is to demonstrate the superiority of GPU architecture over CPU in the context of the optimization of routing and production scheduling processes.

Methods and Materials

Problem Statement

The problem is formulated as follows: given a set of objects VV (cities, products, machines) connected by a set of relations PP that characterize the costs (cost or time) associated with moving from one object to another. It is required to construct a route passing through all objects exactly once, such that the total sum of movement costs is minimized.

The aim of this work was to develop and analyze software utilizing Hopfield neural networks and Kohonen maps to determine the optimal route within the CUDA parallel computing platform on graphics processors.

Simulation of Hopfield Neural Networks on GPU

To simulate the Hopfield network, based on the generalization and extension of the materials from the works by Anderson J. A., Hopfield J. J., and Kohonen T. [1–3], the following methodology was developed:

- **Step 1:** Formulation of the problem using Boolean variables, for example, indicating the visitation of a city in a specific sequence.
- **Step 2:** Definition of the energy functional, including penalty terms for constraint violations.
- **Step 3:** Transformation of the energy expression into a form suitable for parallel execution on the GPU.
- **Step 4:** Implementation of a parallel neuron state update method on the graphics processor using a multiple-thread strategy.

The parallel kernel applies a strategy of distributing the workload across a large number of threads. For example, each thread is assigned to a separate neuron responsible for computing its portion of the matrix multiplication.

The application of Kohonen maps

Self-organizing Kohonen maps serve as a tool for clustering and sorting large datasets. In the context of routing problems, this technique is used to group similar directions of movement and subsequently form optimal paths (Fig. 1). The methodology is based on the following approach:

- Initial quantization of input data to represent the problem in a binary format.
- Creating a layer of neurons, each corresponding to an individual route point.

- Sequential training of the network by approximating neuron weights to the closest input data.

Figure 1 – Dependence of the route ‘optimality’ metric (%) on the number of training iterations of the Kohonen map for varying numbers of route points

Experimental Results

The experimental studies were conducted on two types of computing platforms: desktop PCs equipped with modern Intel Core i7 processors and high-performance NVIDIA GeForce RTX series graphics cards.

Analysis of the effectiveness of Hopfield network emulation

The results demonstrate a significant improvement in performance when executing algorithms on GPUs compared to traditional CPU solutions. In particular, acceleration reaches up to several hundred times even for problems of medium size.

Data processing in Hopfield networks showed that the use of CUDA technology considerably reduced the time to solve the problem due to the efficient utilization of the GPU’s parallel cores. The optimal configuration of the computational process demonstrated steady performance growth with increasing problem size.

Analysis of the Application of Kohonen Maps

Research has demonstrated that Kohonen maps are effective for preliminary clustering and simplifying routing problems. However, they typically require more iterations to stabilize the result, especially in cases of high dimensionality. Nevertheless, implementing this procedure on the GPU reduced the overall time expenditure by nearly half compared to execution solely on the CPU.

Discussion

The obtained results confirm the hypothesis of a significant improvement in solution quality for optimization problems when utilizing graphics processors.

A key factor for success is the ability to perform a large number of homogeneous operations concurrently, which is characteristic of the neural network approach.

However, certain characteristics should be noted:

- GPU accelerators provide significant performance gains only for problems with sufficiently large dimensionality. In simple scenarios with a small data volume, the acceleration effect is negligible.

- Porting algorithms to GPUs complicates program development and debugging; however, the substantial performance improvements justify these efforts.

Therefore, it is advisable to further develop parallel computing methodologies on GPUs to optimize resource-intensive tasks in industrial automation and transportation planning.

Conclusion

The conducted studies confirmed the high effectiveness of homogeneous computational environments on graphics processors for solving combinatorial optimization problems such as the traveling salesman problem. The application of Hopfield neural networks and Kohonen maps, adapted for parallel computations using CUDA technology [4], proved to be particularly promising.

Key findings:

- Simulating Hopfield neural networks on GPUs achieves computational acceleration by orders of magnitude compared to traditional CPU implementations.

- Kohonen maps provide effective preliminary data partitioning, enhancing the speed and accuracy of subsequent optimization stages.

- The most substantial improvements are observed when processing large datasets typical of real-world industrial applications.

Future directions include adapting the proposed approach to specific domains, such as industrial production automation.

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INDIRECT EVALUATION OF THE OIL WELL FLOW RATE EQUIPPED WITH SUBMERSIBLE ELECTRIC CENTRIFUGAL PUMPS

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Abstract. *Oil well flow rates are traditionally measured using automated group measuring units (AGMUs), in which connected wells are measured in turn. If any problems occur with the AGMUs, it is advisable to use indirect flow rate evaluation based on telemetry data. The article discusses three algorithms for indirect evaluation, presents the results of their testing on a conditional well, and provides practical recommendations for the application of each algorithm.*

Keywords: *submersible electric centrifugal pump, automated group measuring unit (AGMU), flow rate, indirect measurement method*

Introduction

The flow rate of production wells is the main characteristic by which their operational efficiency can be assessed. The traditional method of determining the flow rates of production wells is based on the use of an automated group measuring unit (AGMU). Each well is sequentially connected to the AGMU measuring line for a specific period of time, as determined by the technological process, where flow meters determine the amount of gas and liquid produced. The main disadvantage of this approach is the discrete nature of measuring the amount of fluids produced over time. Since each well is connected to the AGMU measuring line sequentially and for a specific period of time, so-called 'blind zones' are formed, during which all wells in the cluster site, except for those connected to the AGMU, are not being measured. The same gaps in obtaining operational information on well flow rates occur when the AGMU fails. In such cases, it is advisable to determine the flow rate by some indirect method, for example, using telemetry data from sensors located on any well equipped with submersible electric centrifugal pump units (SECPU). Such software and mathematical complexes, installed

in a data acquisition system (SCADA) or in the cloud, are called “virtual flow meters”. They are in high demand in conditions where direct flow measurement is impossible or difficult due to low measurement resolution in time [1]. Therefore, the development of algorithms for indirect flow rate estimation is a relevant scientific and practical task.

Materials and methods

The use of AGMU is a practical, effective and cost-effective solution for stable wells, but it should be noted that measurement accuracy increases with time. This is because AGMU records an integral parameter (flow rate/mass over a period of time), so in order to ensure the relative measurement error value established by regulatory documents [2], the measurement time may be quite long. Thus, for low-flow wells, especially those operating in periodic mode, it can reach up to 24 hours [3]. As noted above, the other wells are ‘unattended’ during this time, which can lead to abnormal and emergency situations. In such cases, it is advisable to use indirect flow rate evaluation methods based on available well telemetry data.

It should be noted that in hydrocarbon production, indirect measurement methods are used not only to evaluate the flow rate, but also for many other measurement tasks in order to obtain the maximum amount of useful information from a minimum number of sensors, for example, using a pressure sensor in a well to additionally measure the temperature in it or determine water saturation based on changes in thermobaric conditions in the well [4–6].

There are various approaches to determine the flow rate of wells equipped with electric submersible pumps (Fig. 1) [7, 8].

Flow rate evaluation		
Based on the difference between buffer and line pressures	Based on the electrical parameters of the submersible electric motor (SEM)	Based on the flow-pressure characteristics of the electric submersible pump (ESP)

Figure 1. Parameters used for indirect flow rate evaluation

In the first case, the pressure difference is calculated based on the readings of pressure gauges installed on the buffer (buffer pressure) and the wellhead (linear pressure).

The main equation for calculating the flow rate of a multiphase flow through a nozzle is Bernoulli’s equation:

$$P_1 - P_2 = \frac{\rho u^2}{2\mu^2}, \quad (1)$$

where P_1 and P_2 are the pressures of the fluid before and after the nozzle (buffer and linear, respectively); ρ is the density of the multiphase flow; u is the flow velocity; μ is the flow coefficient. Then the volumetric flow rate of the fluid will be equal to

$$Q = \frac{\pi d_c^2 u}{4}, \quad (2)$$

Where d_c is the diameter of the fitting.

Formulas (1) and (2) allow us to determine the volumetric flow rate of a multiphase flow through a fitting if the value of the flow coefficient μ is known. For pure liquids, it is determined experimentally or using nomograms and is usually in the range of 0.5–0.8.

In practice, the calculation is performed in two stages. In the first stage, the fluid velocity is calculated for a known fluid flow rate using formula (2), and then the flow coefficient μ is calculated from equation (1), taking into account the known values of the buffer pressure P_1 and linear pressure P_2 . Next, the flow coefficient is fixed, and the new value of the fluid flow rate for the well is determined by sequentially solving equations (1) and (2) for the known measurements of the buffer and linear pressure values.

The second method is based on the equality of the useful power of the submersible electric motor and the power consumed by the electric submersible pump. As a result, by calculating the useful power of the submersible electric motor, it is possible to calculate the fluid flow rate through the pump from the energy characteristics of the electric submersible pump, i.e. the dependence of the flow rate on the power, and use it to determine the fluid flow rate. At the first stage of the calculation, the useful power of the submersible electric motor is calculated based on the known values of the current and the passport characteristics of the submersible electric motor. Next, based on the known measured liquid flow rate on the reference date, the power consumption of the pump is determined. The ratio of the calculated power consumption of the submersible electric centrifugal pump and the useful power of the SECP is recorded as the power degradation coefficient of the SECP:

$$K_{pow} = \frac{N_{pump}}{N_{mot}}, \quad (3)$$

where $N_{pump} = N(Q)$ is the power consumption of the SECP; $N_{mot} = N_{mot}(I)$ is the useful (developed) power of the SECP.

In the second stage, for the new date, the power consumption of the SEM is first calculated, and then, taking into account the previously found degradation coefficient for the power of the SECP, the flow rate of the mixture through the pump is recalculated using the energy characteristics of the SECP.

The third algorithm is based on the fact that the flow rate of the fluid flowing through the SECP is uniquely related to the useful head created by the pump, using the rated flow-head characteristic (FHC) with a correction for frequency and head degradation due to the influence of fluid density and wear.

To calculate the effective head, the measured pressure at the inlet P_{in} and the calculated pressure at the pump discharge line P_{out} are used. The pressure at the pump discharge line is determined by the buffer pressure according to the hydrostatic law:

$$P_{out} = P_1 + \rho g H_{tub} \cos \varphi, \quad (4)$$

where ρ is the density of the liquid; g is the acceleration due to gravity; H_{tub} is the depth of the pump-compressor pipe (PCP) suspension; φ is the inclination angle of the well to the vertical.

At the first stage of calculation, based on the known operating mode of the installation and the known measured fluid flow rate at surface conditions on the selected (reference) date, the actual pressure-flow characteristics of the electric submersible pump (corresponding to the pumping equipment operating in the well) are refined by selecting the degradation coefficient:

$$K_{degr} = \frac{H_{fact}}{H_{calc}}, \quad (5)$$

where $H_{fact} = \frac{P_{out} - P_{in}}{\rho g}$ is the actual pressure of the SECP; $H_{calc} = H(Q)$ is the calculated value based on the flow-pressure characteristics for the measured flow rate $Q_{flow-head}$ of the electric submersible pump.

In the second stage, for the same parameters of the electric submersible pump operation, but with the measured value P_{in} obtained on a new date, the fluid flow rate through the pump is restored using the value of the electric submersible pump head degradation coefficient due to wear according to the flow-head characteristic curve found in the first stage.

Purpose of the study

The purpose of this paper is to test various algorithms for indirect evaluation of the flow rate of an oil well equipped with a submersible electric centrifugal pump unit and to develop practical recommendations for their use.

Results and their discussion

The algorithms were tested on five data sets obtained synthetically using the model of the unsteady state of an oil well operation presented in [9]. This model takes into account the multiphase nature of the flow, including gas separation from oil, various flow regimes (laminar-turbulent, bubble-projectile), phase slippage, heat and mass transfer, and other effects that allow numerical solutions close to field data to be obtained and can therefore be used as a simulator for generating ‘field’ information.

The SECP5–60–2000 with a nominal flow rate of 60 m³/day was selected as the SECP, and the SEM32–117 with a nominal power of 32 kW and a nominal current of 35.5A was selected as the SEM.

The following reference parameters were adopted for the conditional well:
 fluid flow rate — 74.29 m³/day;
 pressure at the pump inlet — 68.53 atm;
 buffer pressure before the nozzle — 11.43 atm;
 SECP current — 25.98 A.

To generate new values for the parameter sets that will be used to evaluate the accuracy of the algorithms, the well productivity coefficient, which is 0.816 (m³/day)/atm for the reference set of values, was varied in the range from 0.6 to 1.0 (m³/day)/atm.

The values obtained for the five parameter sets are shown in table 1.

Table 1 – Sets of initial data

Parameter	Data set				
	1	2	3	4	5
Productivity coefficient, (m ³ /day)/atm	0.6	0.7	0.8	0.9	1.0
Liquid flow rate, m ³ /day	65.83	70.57	75.76	79.89	80.97
Pressure at pump inlet, atm	46.97	57.53	64.47	71.02	79.37
Buffer pressure, atm	10.57	10.95	11.36	11.78	12.16
Current, A	25.09	25.57	25.92	26.24	26.50

Based on the generated synthetic data, fluid flow rate calculations were performed using three different algorithms. The following data were used as input for the calculations:

- for the first algorithm, only buffer pressure;
- for the second algorithm — buffer pressure and pressure at the pump inlet;
- for the third algorithm — buffer pressure and current.

The calculation results are presented in Table 2.

As can be seen, the third algorithm showed the best results for the considered conditional well. For this algorithm, the average absolute error in determining the liquid flow rate was 1.85 m³/day, and the average relative error was 2.5%. The results for the second algorithm were slightly worse: the absolute error was 4.21 m³/day, and the relative error was 6.2%. Finally, algorithm 1 demonstrated the least accurate results: the absolute error was 9.12 m³/day, and the relative error was 15.3%.

When working with real field data, the results are likely to be worse, since no model is capable of taking into account all the nuances of a physical object or process.

Table 2 – Results of liquid flow rate calculations

Parameter	Data set					Average value
	1	2	3	4	5	
Liquid flow rate, taken as actual, m ³ /day	65.83	70.57	75.76	79.89	80.97	74.60
Algorithm 1						
Calculated fluid flow rate, m ³ /day	46.90	60.55	72.45	82.88	91.30	70.82
Absolute error, m ³ /day	18.93	10.02	3.31	2.99	10.33	9.12
Relative error, %	40.4	16.5	4.6	3.6	11.3	15.3
Algorithm 2						
Calculated fluid flow rate, m ³ /day	60.45	65.13	72.32	75.28	78.78	70.39
Absolute error, m ³ /day	5.38	5.44	3.44	4.61	2.19	4.21
Relative error, %	8.9	8.4	4.8	6.1	2.8	6.2
Algorithm 3						
Calculated fluid flow rate, m ³ /day	68.07	71.64	74.76	76.79	79.14	74.08
Absolute error, m ³ /day	2.24	1.07	1.00	3.10	1.83	1.85
Relative error, %	3.3	1.5	1.3	4.0	2.3	2.5

The following are examples of situations where it is necessary to evaluate the flow rate using indirect indicators.

Absence or malfunction of the AGMU – for example, it may be temporarily absent from the well cluster after repair, during installation, or may fail due to malfunctions in process equipment, control equipment, electrical equipment, or software. In these cases, the telemetry data from the SECP control station (current, intake pressure, buffer pressure, temperature) is the only source for estimating flow rate.

Furthermore, such an assessment is necessary for frequent operational control between measurements at the AGMU, since the AGMU measurement is an ‘instantaneous’ flow rate value at a specific moment, which is taken at certain intervals (several times a day, a week). The characteristics of the SECP and pressure values are transmitted in near real time. For example, it is possible to see remotely that the current is gradually increasing over several hours, which may indicate gradual waxing or a change in viscosity. This allows measures to be planned before the problem becomes critical and affects the measured flow rate.

When operating in unstable mode (especially with a high gas factor), the AGMU measures average values over a period of time. If the well operates with periodic gas plugs or in an unstable supply mode, the AGMU readings may be distorted. In this case, analysing the current graph for sharp peaks and dips and the pressure at the SECP inlet gives a much clearer picture of the dynamics of the process and the degree of gas influence on the pump operation.

Practical significance of indirect flow rate evaluation algorithms

In practice, in addition to metrological characteristics, it is also necessary to take into account the areas of application of each of the algorithms considered, shown in fig. 1, and the risks associated with their use.

The first algorithm, based on the difference between buffer and line pressures, is based on the laws of hydraulics: the well flow rate is related to pressure losses in the discharge line from the wellhead to the point of entry into the measuring unit's manifold. The higher the flow rate, the greater the friction of the fluid against the pipe walls and the greater the pressure drop in this section. Knowing the diameter of the pipe, its length, the properties of the fluid and the pressure difference, it is possible to calculate the flow rate. The accuracy of the flow rate evaluation is significantly affected by unknown fluid properties: it drops sharply if the actual viscosity, density and gas content of the mixture are unknown. Even a small error in viscosity results in a large error in the calculation of friction losses. The unevenness of the pipeline relief or internal deposits also have an impact; for example, paraffin accumulation creates additional, unaccounted for pressure drops. Because of this, the algorithm requires frequent calibration based on accurate measurements from the AGMU. In general, it can be recommended as a rough, trend-based method for wells with a simple, short throw line and stable, well-studied production.

The algorithm for evaluating the flow rate based on electrical indicators of SECP (current, power) implements the energy method. It is based on the fact that the power consumed by the electric motor is directly related to the hydraulic power transmitted to the fluid by the pump. The active power consumed by the submersible electric motor is measured. Knowing the efficiency of the motor, the efficiency of the pump (from the certificate) and the developed pressure (according to pressure sensors), it is possible to evaluate the flow rate. The main risks are the unknown values of the motor and pump efficiency, which are not constants. They vary depending on the load, frequency, temperature and wear. This introduces significant uncertainty into the flow rate evaluation. In addition, there is ambiguity in the interpretation of SECP indicators: high current can mean high flow rate, high fluid viscosity (e.g., due to increased water content and emulsion formation), and mechanical problems (friction in the pump). It can be recommended as an operational diagnostic tool for tracking dynamics and trends. It allows you to see changes in the well's operating mode in real time.

The algorithm for evaluating flow rate based on the head-flow characteristic (H-Q) of the SECP implements the classic hydrodynamic method, which often forms the basis of virtual flow meters. It is based on the specified curve of the dependence of the pressure developed by the pump on its flow rate (H-Q). Based

on data from sensors (pressure at the intake and discharge lines), the actual pressure created by the pump is calculated. Then, using the H-Q curve, the flow rate is 'restored' based on this pressure.

The main risk when using the algorithm is that the pump's specified characteristics may not match its actual characteristics. The specified curve is measured for water under stable conditions. In a well, the pump operates on an emulsion with gas, and its actual characteristics may differ significantly. Pump wear also distorts the characteristics. The second source of error is the uncertainty of the fluid properties at the inlet. For an accurate conversion of head to flow rate, it is necessary to know the density of the mixture at the pump inlet, which depends on water content and gas content, and its value is usually unknown. It can be used as a basis for qualitative evaluation and trends. Modern virtual flow meters attempt to adapt the specified curve by feeding data from the AGMU for calibration and accounting for the actual properties of the fluid. Without such adaptation, accuracy is low.

Conclusion

The results obtained confirm that evaluating the flow rate based on indirect indicators of the submersible electric centrifugal pump's performance is not a substitute for accurate measurements using an AGMU, but rather an essential tool for operational analysis and diagnostics used in specific situations requiring speed, diagnostics, or when direct measurements are not possible. AGMU data is always used for balancing and commercial accounting, but analysis of the SECP's performance is absolutely necessary to ensure stable and efficient well operation.

The most preferable approach is to use not just one algorithm, but a combination of them within a monitoring system, i.e. a virtual flow meter. In the authors' opinion, the following indirect evaluation algorithm is the optimal option. Accurate flow measurements from AGMU are used as reference points for calibrating all indirect methods. In between measurements, a mathematical model is used that combines data from pressure sensors on the receiving and discharge lines of the SECP, temperature, electrical parameters of the SECP (current, power) and the adaptive pressure-flow characteristic of the pump, which is adjusted according to the latest measurements from the AGMU. This combination allows us to obtain a calculated flow rate with an acceptable error margin for operational control and, most importantly, to track changes in real time.

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DEVELOPMENT OF THE ELECTRIC VEHICLE DESIGN PROCESS WITHIN AN AUTOMOTIVE MANUFACTURER'S QUALITY MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

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Abstract. *The development of new vehicle designs, particularly amid the transition to electromobility and technological sovereignty, entails increasing system complexity, stricter functional safety requirements, and shortened product lifecycle timelines. Under these conditions, traditional quality management approaches centered on reactive defect correction [3] become economically inefficient. This study examines the interrelationship among test results, project maturity level, and the structure of quality costs, with emphasis on the cost of nonconformance – encompassing both internal (rework, retesting) and external (warranty obligations, reputational damage) components. Defects identified at later stages necessitate significant budget and schedule revisions: the average cost to resolve a single critical failure ranges from 1.5–2 million rubles, and project delays can extend up to three weeks. A management model is proposed, grounded in early assessment of project maturity through an Integrated Product Lifecycle Matrix (IPLM) and a proactive reallocation of quality costs toward prevention activities (up to 33% of the total quality budget). The results demonstrate that a systematic approach to test planning and risk management can reduce nonconformance costs by 20–30% and ensure a sustainable market launch of competitive products.*

Keywords: *cost of quality, nonconformance costs, project maturity, vehicle testing, quality management, ANPQP (Advanced New Product Quality Planning), IPLM (Integrated Product Lifecycle Matrix), electric vehicle (EV), functional safety, ROI (Return on Investment), budget adjustment, schedule revision, preventive investments.*

The central element of this article is the concept of “cost of nonconformance,” which represents a comprehensive category of costs arising from the inability of a product or service to meet established requirements. In the context of developing and producing complex cyber-physical systems (CPS), such as electric vehicles,

unmanned systems, or industrial robots, the concept of nonconformance costs becomes particularly acute. This is due to the high degree of hardware and software integration, as well as the presence of strict functional safety and cybersecurity requirements, which impose additional liabilities and risks on the manufacturer.

The traditional classification of nonconformance costs divides them into two major groups: internal and external. Internal costs arise within the organization before the product is delivered to the customer and include all expenses associated with detecting and eliminating defects. For CPS, this may involve reassembling an electronic control unit (ECU) due to a soldering error, re-simulating a powertrain control algorithm after a failed bench test, or modifying mechanical drive components following strength validation tests. These actions directly lead to consumption of raw materials, labor time, and equipment usage, forming the basis of operational losses.

External nonconformance costs arise after the product has been delivered to the customer or released to the market. They are often substantially higher and more diverse than internal costs. These include direct financial losses, such as the cost of warranty repairs or replacement of faulty components. For example, according to industry estimates, the annual cost of warranty service for lithium-ion battery-based energy storage systems can reach 0.8% of the initial equipment cost starting from the third year of operation. Another type of external cost comprises penalty payments for failure to meet contractual obligations regarding deadlines or technical specifications, as well as regulatory fines for non-compliance with legislation.

However, the most serious consequences are often non-financial yet extremely destructive – namely, reputational damage and loss of trust from consumers and partners. In the era of digital media, even a single failure of a critical CPS component, such as the autopilot of an autonomous vehicle or a life-support system in a medical device, can trigger widespread public outcry and long-term brand damage.

The concept of nonconformance costs in the CPS domain is further complicated by the introduction of specialized functional safety and cybersecurity standards. The ISO 26262 standard for the automotive industry and the DO-178C standard for aviation software introduce the concepts of Safety Integrity Level (SIL) or Automotive Safety Integrity Level (ASIL) [1]. Compliance with these levels is not merely a matter of meeting technical requirements but a fundamental requirement to ensure human safety. Thus, any nonconformance identified during testing may be classified not only as a defect but also as a violation of safety requirements. This implies a specific set of associated costs, including not only direct correction expenses but also potential legal liability, litigation, and even criminal responsibility in cases involving harm to life or health.

Similarly, the IEC 62443 series standards, focused on security for industrial automation and control systems (ICS), define a methodology for risk analysis and

implementation of protective measures. Detection of a cybersecurity vulnerability during CPS testing – one that could be exploited to compromise the system – constitutes a form of nonconformance, the consequences of which may include not only financial losses from a cyberattack but also severe reputational damage, particularly in cases involving leakage of confidential data.

In the context of ensuring technological sovereignty, managing nonconformance costs acquires a new dimension. Sanction-related pressures and restrictions on the supply of foreign components, software, and design tools (CAD/CAE/PLM) compel companies to seek alternatives. Transitioning to domestic analogs or open-source solutions, while strategically sound for achieving independence, introduces challenges that themselves may become sources of nonconformance costs. Integration of components from different suppliers operating under varying standards and protocols complicates certification and traceability processes. The lack of mature supply chains and standardized interfaces – characteristic of sanction conditions – increases the likelihood of physical and logical nonconformities during assembly and testing. Moreover, using non-trivial digital platforms without adequate documentation and support may lead to loss of data traceability, making accurate impact assessment of changes impossible and increasing the risk of latent defects identified only at late testing stages.

Thus, within the modern paradigm of technological sovereignty, nonconformance costs must be evaluated through the prism of three key factors: (1) operational costs for defect correction; (2) financial and legal consequences of violating regulatory safety and cybersecurity requirements; and (3) costs associated with overcoming technological dependence and integrating components under limited access to global cooperation networks.

The cause-and-effect relationship between CPS test results and subsequent budget and schedule adjustments represents a fundamental mechanism governing the project lifecycle. This process can be represented as a clearly structured chain of events, each stage possessing specific characteristics and consequences. The first link in this chain is the testing process itself. CPS testing is multi-level and comprehensive, as it aims to verify not only individual components but also their interaction within the entire system. This process includes hardware testing for compliance with technical specifications, software testing for errors and bugs, as well as compatibility and integration validation. Additionally, reliability and durability testing are critical for CPS, conducted over extended periods to identify performance degradation or premature component failure. Functional safety testing according to standards such as ISO 26262-which verifies the system's ability to maintain a safe state during component failures – occupies a special place. Cybersecurity testing is also conducted to identify vulnerabilities that could be exploited by attackers to compromise the system.

Identification of nonconformities at the testing stage launches the second, most critical phase: consequence assessment. Any nonconformance – whether an algorithm logic error, a component dimension mismatch, or a security vulnerability – immediately becomes an object of analysis. This analysis follows two main directions: financial and temporal. Financial consequences are directly reflected in the project budget. The most obvious and significant component is the cost of rework – expenses incurred to correct the defect. All this leads to the necessity of increasing the total project budget.

The final stage in this chain is management decision-making and plan adjustment. Based on the assessment, project leadership decides how to proceed: whether to eliminate the defect immediately, revise requirements, or accept commercial risks. If the decision is made to eliminate the defect, the formal change management process begins. This process includes formal approval of modifications, resource reallocation, and – most importantly – adjustment of the project’s baseline plans. Budget adjustment involves increasing it by an amount equivalent to the estimated nonconformance costs, including expenses for rework, retesting, and other related expenditures. Schedule adjustment entails extending project timelines by the period necessary to complete all correction work. These changes are documented in updated versions of the project management plan and communicated to all stakeholders regarding the new project status.

Thus, the event chain “testing → nonconformance identification → consequence assessment → plan adjustment” represents a continuous feedback loop that enables the project to adapt to identified problems – but always at the cost of additional time and financial resources.

To visually demonstrate the considered cause-and-effect chain, let us apply it to a hypothetical yet realistic scenario based on experience developing modern cyber-physical systems such as electric vehicles. Suppose the project is at the final testing stage of a new electric vehicle’s braking system, which includes passing standard test cycles on a closed proving ground. One such cycle is the emergency braking test on a wet surface, designed to verify anti-lock braking system (ABS) performance. During one such test, the test driver records atypical vehicle behavior: during an attempt at sharp braking, the ABS begins generating false signals, leading to deactivation of acceleration assist and loss of traction. The data acquisition system and video recorder capture the entire event sequence. After test completion, sensor data and video archives are analyzed by engineers. Analysis of the brake controller software code reveals the root cause: a rounding error in the algorithm processing wheel speed sensor data, which manifests only at very low speeds (below 5 km/h) combined with high braking force. This nonconformance was not identified during earlier bench testing stages, as test benches did not fully reproduce the complex dynamic conditions of real-world driving. This nonconformance is critical, as it

directly affects driving safety and contradicts ISO 26262 requirements for ASIL C-level components.

The identified nonconformance immediately triggers the process of assessing its project impact. Within an adapted quality management methodology similar to ANQP [2], the assembled team evaluates all aspects of the problem. The assessment reveals the need to reprogram the ECU across the entire upcoming serial batch of 100 units. This includes developing new code, testing it in repeatability cycles, implementing the flashing procedure on the assembly line, and conducting post-flashing quality control. After deploying the corrected software, a full cycle of braking system tests must be repeated on the bench and under field conditions to confirm defect elimination and obtain the corresponding certification. These costs are estimated at over 500 thousand rubles. Development, testing, and deployment of the new software will take approximately two weeks. Additional testing will require another week. Thus, the total project delay will amount to three weeks.

The safety and marketing teams assess external risks. The probability of recalling already-sold vehicles in case of releasing a defective batch is estimated as high. This could lead to substantial financial losses associated with logistics, repairs, and customer compensation, as well as serious reputational damage that would be extremely difficult to restore. The risk of fines for missing the planned market launch deadline is also high, as the contract with distributors contains strict conditions. Given the critical importance of the issue for safety and brand reputation, project management decides to eliminate the defect. The project budget is increased by 2 million rubles. The current project schedule is revised. The release date for the first serial batch of electric vehicles is postponed by three weeks. The project critical path is adjusted, and new tasks for software modification and retesting are integrated into the schedule. The change management procedure is activated. All changes to software requirements, the development plan, and the project schedule are formally registered, approved, and communicated to all teams involved in the project. Three weeks after work commencement, the system successfully passes repeated testing. The problem is eliminated, and the system fully complies with ISO 26262 requirements. The project, although delayed and over budget, continues to progress in a safe and controlled manner. The final project budget exceeded the original by 2 million rubles, and release timelines were postponed by three weeks. This example clearly illustrates how a test result (discovery of a software error) initiated a full chain of reactions leading to specific financial and temporal adjustments – an inevitable aspect of quality management for complex cyber-physical systems.

The conducted analysis of the relationship between CPS test results and nonconformance costs enables formulation of several strategic conclusions and practical recommendations crucial for project management under conditions of technological sovereignty.

First, the study unequivocally confirms that defect prevention is far more effective than subsequent correction. The cost of eliminating a defect identified at the testing stage exceeds by multiple times the costs of preventing it at early lifecycle stages, such as risk analysis (e.g., FMEA), model-based verification, or thorough micro-level testing. Under conditions of limited resources and sanction-related restrictions — which make every ruble and every day especially valuable — investments in proactive quality management methods ensure the greatest economic and strategic effect [5]. This necessitates shifting focus from reactive crisis management toward building resilient problem-prevention systems.

Second, the experience of transitioning to proprietary digital platforms for lifecycle management, such as a Digital Thread based on open-source tools, is a double-edged sword. On one hand, this is a strategically sound step toward achieving digital independence and reducing reliance on foreign vendors. On the other hand, it creates new challenges for quality management, data traceability, and certification. Integration of heterogeneous systems, lack of standardized interfaces, and lower maturity of certain open-source solutions may become sources of new, previously unknown nonconformities. Therefore, the priority should not be merely transferring existing processes to new platforms, but reviewing and adapting them considering the specifics of the chosen tools. This requires developing new, adapted quality management methodologies — similar to ANPQP — that account for both technical and organizational aspects of operating under conditions of digital independence.

Third, for CPS it is impossible to effectively manage quality by treating hardware and software components as separate entities. A single point of failure — whether a microcontroller, device driver, or control algorithm — can cause failure of the entire system. This underscores the absolute necessity of deep integration of development, testing, and quality management processes at all levels. Application of model-based systems engineering (MBSE) methodologies [4] can facilitate this by ensuring a single, consistent system model throughout its lifecycle and enabling early identification of integration issues. Testing processes must be end-to-end, covering both software and hardware, and their results must promptly influence all related project management processes.

Finally, under sanctions — when access to the most advanced global components and technologies is limited — quality becomes one of the few remaining strategic advantages. A product that not only functions but also demonstrates high reliability, safety, and guaranteed quality is capable of occupying its market niche. Consequently, quality management in the CPS domain must be regarded not as a cost center but as a key investment asset determining the success of national industrial projects and contributing to the achievement of technological sovereignty.

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**DEVELOPMENT OF THE MATHEMATICAL MODEL OF SHAPING
INTERNAL SURFACES WITH BLADE TOOLS FOR ADAPTIVE
INTELLIGENT DESIGN OF SUBTRACTIVE PROCESSES
USING DIGITAL COUNTERPARTS**

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Abstract. Problem Statement (Relevance of the Work). The current level of digitization in the manufacturing of high-tech metalworking parts necessitates the development of advanced production technological preparation using digital twins of processes and artificial intelligence. The practical implementation of this concept requires a profound understanding of the dynamics of physical processes fundamentally similar to hole drilling. Mathematical (simulation) modeling enables forecasting machining accuracy at the operation design stage, thereby eliminating machining inaccuracies, design errors, and reducing production preparation costs. **Objective of the work.** Development of a mathematical model of the digital twin for the hole formation process using rotating multi-blade end tools. **Methods applied.** The models presented in this article are derived from analytical methods based on fundamental physical laws and the core principles of cutting mechanics and vibrational mechanics, as well as the theory of plastic deformation of the material in the chip formation zone. The scientific novelty of the research presented in this article lies in the development of a mathematical model of a digital twin for the shape formation of the machined surface, which, for the first time, accounts for the interrelation of machining accuracy with respect to cutting regimes and tool vibration displacements. **Result.** The article presents a portion of the methodical and mathematical support developed for the first time for the digital twin of hole formation by rotating end multi-blade tools. The application of

the digital twin in manufacturing holds significant practical value, as it allows for precise verification of control programs for CNC machines.

Keywords: *hole formation, rotating end multi-blade tools, chip removal, simulation modeling, precise verification of control programs, digital twin.*

Introduction

Achieving the required surface accuracy parameters, such as those for holes in engineering products [1–3], necessitates advanced technological production preparation that enables the elimination of machining inaccuracies, design errors in operation transitions, and errors in control programs (UP) [4,5]. Consequently, the advancement of digital technologies significantly enhances the importance of digital twins for computer modeling at every stage of designing manufacturing technologies in industry, allowing for increased efficiency, reduction in the scope and number of physical tests by substituting them with digital experiments, thereby reducing the costs associated with the creation and operation of the manufactured product, particularly its internal surfaces [3–6].

The shaping of internal surfaces (IS) using rotating multi-blade end tools (VKMI) such as drills, countersinks, reamers, mills, and similar tools is a complex task. The complexity of the process is due primarily to the influence of static factors (geometry of the tool's cutting part, sharpening errors, wear, cutting regimes, etc.) on the cutting forces, and consequently on the areas of the sliced layers and on surface formation errors, which is well studied and easily eliminated in practice [7]. Secondly, dynamic factors, which are not always taken into consideration, also significantly influence the formation of errors in machined surfaces. In particular, we have established that the working process of any VKMI lacks inherent radial stability; that is, its cutting part, forming a nonholonomic connection with the cutting surface, undergoes radial vibrations [4]. Vibrations of the VKMI arising during the formation of the hole surface in the workpiece cannot be completely eliminated, but their parameters can be controlled, thus enabling prompt influence on the redistribution of the cross-sections of the removed layers and, consequently, on the size and shape of the formed surface. That is, the layers to be cut must be redistributed on each tooth by adjusting the tool's vibration parameters so that the entire set of cut layers can ensure the required size and shape of the formed surface. At the same time, it is necessary to associate the layers to be cut with a coordinate system corresponding to the cutting blades, which have a rigid coordinate linkage to the tool axis and perform a complex motion together with the tool (rotational motion around the tool axis and quasi-circular oscillations relative to their own axis of rotation). Then such cut layers can be called coordinated, and their entirety represents an array of removed material, whose dimensions and surface shape reflect the formed surface of the part. That is, if, having calculated the parameters of cut layers removed by each tooth of the

VKMI, one geometrically subtracts them from the workpiece volume, then without resorting to cutting force calculations, it becomes straightforward to determine the dimensions and shape of the formed surface.

Obtained results and their discussion

Thus, previously we described mechanisms [8] of redistribution of cross-sections of cut layers due to radial (transverse) and axial self-oscillations of the rotating multi-blade end milling tool. Axial and torsional-axial self-oscillations of VKMI combined with transverse self-oscillations lead to violations of machining accuracy, since during the hole-forming process there is a redistribution of the sheared layers; moreover, for each complete oscillation of the tool center, the tooth, which at that moment has an actual zero velocity, shifts by a discrete angle.

Physically, the forming process proceeds in such a way that one of the blades does not cut but compresses the material, for example, metal, with its rear surface; that is, the actual velocity at this blade is zero. The increase in the crushing force will continue until it balances the total positively directed tangential cutting force on the remaining teeth. This results in a nonholonomic constraint between the tool and the cutting surface, with the tool performing a kind of “planetary rolling” by its teeth over the cutting surface, leaving characteristic “marks.”

Analyzing the motion of the VKMI from the viewpoint of spherical motion of a rigid body [9] and determining the velocities and accelerations of VKMI points, also denoting: Z — the axis of the fixed cone and transfer motion; Z_1 — axis of relative displacement of the movable cone; O — center of gravity of the drill; O_1 — point of intersection of Z_1 and the projections of cutting edges on the ZOX plane; Y_0 — angle of drill axis deflection; Y — angle between the generatrix and the Z_1 axis of the movable cone; l — drill overhang length (segment BO_1); z — distance from the drill axis to the center of gravity of the drill (segment OO_1); D_{in} — drill diameter; φ — half of the drill point angle; ω_{vr} — angular velocity of the drill rotation about its own axis Z_1 ; ω — angular velocity of the drill rotation; hA — distance from point A to the instantaneous axis of rotation; point ΩB — stationary point around which the drill moves; point K_1 — stationary point on the drill cutting edge lying on the instantaneous axis and the intersection point of the drill cutting edge with the generatrix of the moving cone; ΩA — point of the cutting edge of the drill, not lying on the instantaneous axis; $\omega\Omega k$ — frequency of VKMI oscillations; ρ — radius of VKMI oscillations; pF — inertial force of the drill due to high-frequency oscillations; P_{ax} , P_{rad} — axial and radial components of cutting forces; P_{up} — elastic force of the drill (Figure 1a); the radius of VKMI oscillations is determined p

$$\rho = \frac{\omega \cdot D_{in} \cdot \sin(Y + \varphi)}{\omega_e \cdot 2 \cdot \sin \varphi} = \frac{\omega \cdot D_{in} \cdot \sin(Y + \varphi) \cdot \sin Y_0}{\omega \cdot 2 \cdot \sin Y \cdot \sin \varphi} = \frac{D_{in} \cdot \sin(Y + \varphi) \cdot \sin Y_0}{2 \cdot \sin Y \cdot \sin \varphi}. \quad (1)$$

Fig. 1. Spherical motion of VKMI:

- a) diagram for determining VKMI velocities and accelerations;
- b) hodograph of the angular velocity vector \vec{u} ; c) force scheme acting on VKMI

Considering the forces acting on the drill along the axis Z_1 , directed along the drill axis, and performing the corresponding trigonometric transformations, we determine the drill axis deflection angle Y_o

$$Y_o = \arccos \left[\frac{P_{oc}}{\sqrt{(P_{yn} - P_{pxz})^2 + P_{oc}^2}} \right] \pm \arccos \left[\frac{F^{\omega} \cdot \cos Y}{\sqrt{(P_{yn} - P_{pxz})^2 + F_{oc}^2}} \right], \quad (2)$$

$$\operatorname{tg} Y = \frac{D_{mm}}{2 \cdot l - D_{mm} \cdot \operatorname{ctg} \varphi}. \quad (3)$$

In accordance with Ishlinsky's theorem [9], we determine the solid angle of the movable cone.

$$\Omega_1 = 2\pi(1 - \cos Y) = 2\pi \left(1 - \frac{2 \cdot l - D_{mm} \cdot \operatorname{ctg} \varphi}{\sqrt{(2 \cdot l - D_{mm} \cdot \operatorname{ctg} \varphi)^2 + D_{mm}^2}} \right). \quad (4)$$

Since the generatrix of the cone BK_1 rotates around the Z axis with angular velocity ω , and its projection of angular velocity onto it is zero, the angle by which

the conical surface describing the main cutting edges (cone) of the drill rotates after one revolution is φ_1 . Meanwhile, the rotation period of the drill cone is T_1 , and the rotation period of the drill's center of mass is T_2 per one revolution. $\varphi_2 = 2\pi$.

$$T_2 = \frac{\sqrt{1 + \frac{\sin Y \cdot \sin(Y - Y_o) \cdot \cos Y}{\sin Y_o} - 1}}{b \cdot \frac{\sin Y \cdot \sin(Y - Y_o)}{\sin Y_o}} = \frac{\sqrt{1 + \frac{\sin Y \cdot \sin(Y - Y_o) \cdot \cos Y}{\sin Y_o} - 1}}{\frac{\omega_{sp} \cdot \text{tg} Y}{\sin Y_o} \cdot \frac{\sin Y \cdot \sin(Y - Y_o)}{\sin Y_o}} \quad (5)$$

The value of the angle φ_2 by which the drill axis rotates after one revolution is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi_2 &= \Omega_2 + \omega_e T_2 + \varepsilon \cdot \frac{T_2^2}{2} = \\ &= 2\pi(1 - \cos Y_o) + \sqrt{1 + \frac{\sin Y \cdot \sin(Y - Y_o) \cdot \cos Y}{\sin Y_o} - 1} + \frac{\omega_{sp}}{4 \cdot \cos Y_o} \cdot \left[\frac{\sqrt{1 + \frac{\sin Y \cdot \sin(Y - Y_o) \cdot \cos Y}{\sin Y_o} - 1}}{\frac{\omega_{sp} \cdot \text{tg} Y}{\sin Y_o} \cdot \frac{\sin Y \cdot \sin(Y - Y_o)}{\sin Y_o}} \right]^2 \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

, where Ω_2 – the solid angle of the cone formed by the rotation of the Z_1 axis relative to the Z axis, which is defined analogously Ω_1

Fig. 2. Simulator tasks: a) visualization of the influence of axial vibration amplitude on the magnitude of hole deviation; b) measured data of the hole axis deviation magnitude

The derived mathematical model proves the existence of a discrete angle by which the VKMI blade shifts during each complete transverse oscillation of the tool center, with an actual instantaneous zero velocity. This model allows determining the tool position at any given moment, as well as the velocity and

acceleration of any point on the tool at the current time, the angle of deviation of the drill axis from the rotational axis of symmetry, and the discrete rotation (displacement) angle of each tooth (blade) of the VKMI. Moreover, it is used in programs as the initial basis for calculating the areas of the layers removed by the teeth of the VKMI during their redistribution caused by the transverse vibrations of the tool.

Programs [6] are intended for high-precision modeling, verification, and real-time visualization of dynamic hole formation processes using the ISO 7-bit language. Before running the UP on a real CNC machine, its optimization for dimensional accuracy and longitudinal hole shape is carried out using the same precision subtractive simulator. Optimization is performed by redistributing the volumes of material layers removed by the tool's teeth, which accordingly and promptly influences the geometric parameters of the resulting surface of the part, namely the dimensional accuracy and the longitudinal profile of the hole (Figure 2a). The simulator enables visualization of the combined impact of the tool's axial and radial vibrations on the accuracy of the hole's longitudinal profile. When axial vibrations of the tool occur, the hole axis begins to deflect laterally during machining. Moreover, the greater the amplitude of VKMI vibrations, the greater the deviation of the hole axis (Fig. 2a). The numerical values of the longitudinal section profile geometry of the hole can be recorded using measurement tools within the software (Fig. 2b). By adjusting the cutting parameters, the amplitude of the tool's axial vibrations is altered until the distortion magnitude of the hole's longitudinal section falls within the prescribed tolerance; this can be done either manually step-by-step or automatically. The simulator also includes a function to calculate the volume of material removed over any time interval, taking into account the axial vibrations of the tool.

Conclusion

1. A digital model of VKMI displacements during the formation of circular holes has been developed, which made it possible to establish the physical essence of the shaping process and the main patterns of the operation of rotating multi-blade end tools. This operation is characterized by the fact that the cutting part of such tools, regardless of their design, lacking their own radial stiffness and forming a nonholonomic constraint with the cutting surface, undergoes oscillations. Vibrations of the multi-tooth tool cause fluctuations in the cutting forces on each tooth and complexity in the collective behavior of all teeth. Consequently, changes in the thickness of the cut layers per tooth, and thus in the chip elements at the vibration frequency, lead to alterations in the shape of the drift trajectory of the cutting part of the VKMI. The trajectory shape determines the dimensions and geometry of the resulting surface.

2. Theoretical foundations of the method for real-time control of the dimensions and shapes of the surfaces formed on parts and chips have been developed. The method is based on redistributing the areas of the cut layers on the VKMI teeth by controlling vibration parameters.

3. The digital twin based on the developed mathematical model enables simulation of UP that adequately represents real processes within 2D and 3D modeling systems, accounting for dynamic factors to perform design calculations of output parameters of transitions (operations) directly during CNC program development and its verification, for example, using *Vericut*.

The developed methodology for designing machining processes of internal surfaces with various VKMI, implemented as subtractive simulators, is applicable in metalworking and mining, and is valuable for specialists in production technological preparation when developing and verifying UP for CNC machines, as well as for developers of ASTPP (automated system for technological production preparation), being effectively utilized in production.

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O THE QUESTION OF THE EMERGENCE AND DEVELOPMENT OF ADAPTIVE FACADES

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Abstract. *The article provides a retrospective overview of the development of adaptive façade systems in architecture. Distinctive types of adaptive façades employed at the current stage of architectural development are identified, and their operational principles are examined through examples of existing structures. A brief analysis of the prospects for their use in contemporary architecture within the framework of the bionic design concept is provided, along with a demonstration of the indisputable advantages of their application in Russia.*

Keywords: *adaptive systems, ventilated facades, sun-dependent facades, microclimate parameters, St. Petersburg*

Introduction

Throughout the historical development of the architectural and construction sectors, people have consistently sought optimal methods for organizing comfortable living conditions in different climatic environments.

Structural systems and mechanisms for regulating indoor temperature were developed even in ancient times. At the current stage of architectural development, a comprehensive approach is required to address both technical and aesthetic challenges. In this regard, the objective of the research was established as identifying the structural and architectural characteristics of adaptive façades at different stages of their development.

The theoretical foundation for the study was the synthesis of information obtained from various sources (bibliographic, scientific, internet resource, photographic documents). The works dedicated to resolving the aesthetic challenges of

adaptive systems (Luahdi M.Sh.) [1] were examined; and to transformable façades (A. V. Bervinova, N. N. Leontieva) [2]; prospects for development (Kalinin E. K.) [3], as well as the operational principles and applications of transformable façades (Kolesnikov A. V.) [4]; a new generation of adaptive systems (Spiridonova A. V., Shubina I. L., Gerashchenko R. V.) [5].

Retrospective Analysis of the Development of Adaptive Systems

The table below examines several variants of structural systems that regulate the temperature and humidity conditions within interior spaces and create a distinctive architectural expression (Table 1). The analogies drawn between historical structural schemes and modern adaptive systems have demonstrated that their development was directly dependent on the construction materials used, advancements in construction and technical fields, as well as the progression of scientific and technical thought.

Table 1. Structural systems regulating indoor temperature and humidity conditions

Period name	Time frame	System description	Modern analogue
Ancient times	3000 BC. up to 476 AD.	Badgirs are wind towers that channeled cool air into residential spaces	Ventilated façades
		Application of vegetation. The cooling of the air was facilitated by the leaves and branches of plants through the process of moisture evaporation.	Vertical greening, ‘bioclimatic’ (or ‘green’) façades
		Egyptian civilization. Materials with high thermal mass were employed – bricks and stone that accumulated coolness during the night and released it during the day. As well as the building orientation, which considered the directions of the sun and wind	Chromogenic façades
The Middle Ages	476 AD until the late 15th – early 16th centuries	In Scandinavia, double walls were used to reliably retain heat inside rooms, with sand or ash poured between them to provide thermal insulation under harsh climatic conditions	Thermochromic glazing
Modern times	late 15th – early 20th centuries	In hot and humid climates, a dome was often constructed, serving as a ventilation shaft	Ventilated façades

Period name	Time frame	System description	Modern analogue
Contemporary Period	1914–1918 to the Present	Adaptive design is a comprehensive approach to the development of architectural structures, involving the use of materials responsive to temperature.	Solar shading screens. Natural ventilation. Heat-reflective building envelopes.

At the current stage of construction and architectural practice, several types of adaptive systems have been developed and are applied, demonstrating significant potential for the next 20–30 years; these include sun-dependent, dynamic, chromogenic, and ventilated façades.

Ventilated façades are the most prevalent type. The external glass layer protects against wind and precipitation, while the air gap between it and the inner glazing acts as a thermostat, reducing the load on air conditioning and heating systems. Air circulation is regulated by the distribution of airflow. This type of façade comprises movable elements such as shutters, roller blinds, and louvers.

Chromogenic façades are classified into electrochromic, liquid crystal, and thermochromic glazing. The essence of this glazing lies in the ability of the elements to vary their degree of transparency, thermal conductivity, and to regulate the amount of light transmitted through them. These changes depend on the voltage applied to the element (electrochromic), the temperature (thermochromic), and brightness and illumination levels (liquid crystal).

Solar-responsive façades. There are types equipped with photovoltaic panels, external green façades, and light-concentrating façades that collect solar light for interior illumination.

‘Dynamic’ or ‘adaptive’ façades. In this context, changes to the building’s exterior address issues related to establishing a favorable microclimate (lighting regime, air conditioning, natural ventilation, etc.).

The application of adaptive systems in architecture (international and domestic experience).

The development of innovative lighting and heating methods, combined with advanced thermal insulation materials capable of dynamically altering their properties in response to environmental changes without additional energy consumption, currently enables expanded opportunities for improving the energy efficiency of architectural structures. The application of new systems in enclosing constructions impacts form formation and the creation of new architectural expressions in buildings of various functional purposes (Table 2).

The analysis of foreign and domestic experience has enabled the identification of characteristic building types where adaptive systems of various kinds have been implemented during construction, including:

- **residential buildings** (Singapore — EDEN residential complex [4], Spain, Germany — façade of the BIQ House building [4], Moscow, St. Petersburg, and others);
- **high-rise business center buildings** (Al Bahar Towers, Abu Dhabi [4]; Moscow [6]; Saint Petersburg; etc.);
- **educational buildings** (Institut du Monde Arabe — France [4]; RMIT School of Design — Melbourne, Australia [7]; SDU Campus Kolding — Kolding, Denmark [8]; etc.)
- **hospital buildings** (Eskenazi Hospital — Indianapolis, USA; Torre de Especialidades — Mexico City [9]; etc.)
- **exhibition halls, art museums** (exhibition hall of the Kiefer Technic company — Styria, Austria [2]; Ordos — Inner Mongolia, PRC; Kunsthaus — Graz, Austria [10]; etc.);
- **glasshouse buildings** (England [11] et al.).

Table 2. Analysis of foreign and domestic experience in the application of adaptive systems in architecture.

№	Name	Year of construction	Photograph	Façade type	Purpose	Description
FOREIGN EXPERIENCE						
1	Institut du Monde Arabe	1987 France Paris		Sun dependent	Regulates the amount of sunlight entering the building	The façade employs mechanical membranes that open and close according to the time of day
2	Kiefer technic show-room	2007 Austria		Ventilated façades	Regulates the microclimate inside the building	Dynamic façade equipped with movable panels
3	Al Bahar Towers	2012 UAE, Abu Dhabi		Ventilated façades	Regulates the microclimate inside the building	The façade comprises 2098 elements projecting 2 meters outward

№	Name	Year of construction	Photograph	Façade type	Purpose	Description
4	EDEN residential complex	2019 Singapore		Sun dependent	Permanent change of the building's exterior appearance	Vertical greening. Green walls extend the garden situated at the base of the building
5	Bio House	2020 Germany		Sun dependent	Dynamic shading, heat generation	The façade incorporates algae that are automatically combusted, thereby producing heat.
6	Kinetic Glass-house	2022 West Sussex, England		Sun dependent	Maintains the required micro-climate throughout the day and across seasons.	On warm days, the greenhouse opens via a hydraulic mechanism (providing access to sunlight and ventilation); during cold weather, the structure remains closed.
DOMESTIC EXPERIENCE						

№	Name	Year of construction	Photograph	Façade type	Purpose	Description
7	Polyustrovo Business Center	2009 Saint Petersburg Russia		double-skin ventilated façade	The outer envelope (glass, aluminum panels) serves as a thermal buffer, reducing the building's energy consumption	The ventilation system of the cavity between the façades is regulated, adapting to seasonal conditions
8	Evolution Tower	2014 Moscow Russia		a prominent example of adaptive geometry	The tower's form (a 90° rotation) necessitated the use of unique curved glass panels	The façade functions as an integrated system, providing panoramic glazing and resistance to wind loads.
9	Italian Quarter Residential Complex	2017 Moscow Russia		Ventilated façade	Automatic blinds (light and temperature sensors). Elimination of interior overheating, regulated insolation	One of the first residential buildings in Moscow to implement elements of adaptive façades – “smart” blinds

Implementation of adaptive façade technology in Saint Petersburg

It is important to highlight several factors that make the application of adaptive façade technology pertinent to the development of contemporary architecture in Russia overall, and in Saint Petersburg in particular:

1. **Climatic** — Saint Petersburg has a moderately continental climate, characterized by cold winters and moderately warm summers, along with a substantial amount of precipitation, high humidity, and a limited number of sunny days. The combination of these circumstances necessitates an enhanced level of thermal insulation, protection against moisture and wind during winter, and ventilation in summer;

2. **Psychological** — adaptive systems contribute to the formation of favorable microclimatic conditions as well as to the psycho-emotional state of occupants

throughout the year, enabling the integration of greenery into the architectural structure;

3. **Economic** — adaptive systems enhance the energy efficiency of architectural structures and reduce operational costs through automatic regulation of heat exchange and ventilation;

4. **Aesthetic** — adaptive systems facilitate the emergence of new architectural forms that promote the creation of a memorable, iconic appearance of the building, both externally and internally;

5. **Social** — the enhancement of the status of both an individual district and the city as a whole.

For the implementation of adaptive systems in the architecture of Saint Petersburg, several directions can be distinguished: new construction, reconstruction of the city's historical heritage, as well as the integration of natural elements into architectural objects serving various functional purposes.

Conclusion

The analysis of worldwide experience has demonstrated the active use of adaptive systems beyond Russia, specifically in countries with hot arid climates that necessitate maintaining cool indoor environments. Domestic experience with the application of these systems is limited; however, interest in them is growing. In Russia, examples of the use of adaptive technologies can be found in Moscow, Kazan, and Saint Petersburg (the Skolkovo building, the Vostok multifunctional complex in Moscow, the Lotos building in Saint Petersburg, and the Harmony Center in Kazan).

Several factors have been identified that define the advisability of integrating adaptive façade technology into the construction of modern architectural buildings and structures in Saint Petersburg:

1. addressing challenges related to the complex climatic conditions of the city;
2. creating an attractive and memorable appearance both for individual buildings and for the recognizable character of specific urban districts;
3. showcasing advancements in construction and engineering.

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